

Evidence about the epidemiology, aetiology, treatment, and experiences of PANS/PANDAS: an evidence and gap map

Febrey S¹, Nunns M¹, Sharma P¹, Wilson T¹, Stitt A¹, Whear R^{1,2}, Abbott R^{1,2}, Boddy K^{1,2}, Bethel A^{1,2}, Hindson K³, Liew A^{4,6}, Lim M^{4,5}, Shaw E¹, Melendez-Torres G.J¹, Thompson Coon J^{1,2}

¹Exeter Evidence Synthesis Centre, University of Exeter Medical School, University of Exeter, St Luke's Campus, Exeter, Devon, EX1 2LU

²NIHR Applied Research Collaboration South West Peninsula (PenARC), University of Exeter Medical School, University of Exeter, St Lukes Campus, Exeter, Devon, EX1 2LU

³PANS PANDAS UK, Greville House, 10 Jury Street, Warwick, CV34 4EW

⁴Children's Neurosciences, Evelina London Children's Hospital at Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust, Westminster Bridge Road, London, SE1 7EH

⁵Department of Women and Children's Health, School of Life Course Sciences (SoLCS), King's College London, London, WC2R 2LS

⁶National and Specialist CAMHS, South London and Maudsley NHS Foundation Trust, Denmark Hill, London, SE5 8AZ

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
Foreword.....	4
Abstract	6
Plain English summary.....	8
Background.....	11
Aims and objectives	13
Methods.....	14
Identification of studies	14
Inclusion/exclusion criteria	16
Process for applying inclusion criteria.	17
Critical appraisal	17
Framework development and data extraction.....	18
Methods for mapping and presentation	22
Interest holder and PPI Engagement.....	23
Aim of the PPIE activity	23
Methods used for involvement/engagement	23
Outcomes of the PPIE activities	25
Next steps for PPIE.....	25
Funding.....	25
Results.....	26
Study selection.....	26
Characteristics of studies in the map	28
Overview of studies in the Diagnosis research topic	36
Overview of studies in the Epidemiology research topic	41
Overview of studies in the Aetiology/pathophysiology research topic.....	47
Overview of studies in the Symptoms research topic	49

Overview of studies in the Treatment research topic	55
Overview of studies in the Treatment Aims research topic	60
Overview of studies in the Access to services research topic	61
Overview of studies in the Experiences research topic	63
Overview of Conference Abstracts	71
Ongoing studies.	73
Guidelines	73
Impact of Public and Patient Involvement and Engagement	74
Discussion	80
Main findings	80
Comparison to previous systematic reviews.....	83
Implications.....	84
Limitations.....	85
Conclusion	87
Acknowledgements	88
References.....	89
Appendix I	96
Search Strategies.....	96
Undermind.ai prompts/report:.....	104
Appendix II	109
Inclusion/Exclusion criteria	109
Appendix III	111
Research topic codes in the map.....	111
Appendix IV	113
Reasons for exclusion at full text screening	113
Appendix V	132
Free text symptoms coded under <i>other</i> in symptoms filters.....	132

Foreword

As a parent of a child with PANS, I want to recognise the extraordinary amount of work that has gone into bringing this evidence together. This report gathers research from worldwide sources and offers a valuable starting point for understanding a complex and often misunderstood condition. Importantly, it does not only highlight what we currently know—it shines a light on what is still missing. That matters, because clearly identifying gaps is one of the most powerful ways to guide better-quality research, improve clinical understanding, and ultimately strengthen support for children and families.

I hope this report is used as a practical tool: to inform researchers and funders about priority questions, to help clinicians and services reflect on current practice, and to support families and schools seeking clearer, evidence-informed pathways.

Parent of child with PANS

As a parent and someone who has experienced PANS/PANDAS myself, I'm really grateful to have been involved in this research synthesis. It's been a privilege to be part of the process and to see the voices of parents, children, and adults recognised as such an important part of the work.

From the very start, I was struck by how the family stories and experiences had touched the research fellows on a human level as well as a scientific one. I had a strong sense that we were in very safe hands, which meant so much to me. It has been fascinating to see the level of detail in the work!

I have found the evidence map and the accompanying report clear and easy to follow. Having access to robust international research brought together in one place is invaluable for families. Many of us spend long nights searching for answers, trying to make sense of complex and sometimes conflicting information. Not everything we find is reliable, and as a community we can be particularly vulnerable to misinformation. The evidence map will also help as a point of reference when treatments are offered, and big decisions must be made.

While the formal research evidence is still developing, the report sets out clearly what is known and where gaps remain. It's exciting to see how this work will shape future research and

contribute to better understanding and support for families. There is also a huge amount of understanding outside of published research and I'm excited that future work will focus on this anecdotal evidence, helping to build a fuller picture of PANS and PANDAS and ensuring that these lived experiences continue to inform understanding alongside ongoing research.

I hope this work helps to shape the way healthcare professionals approach children and adults who present with these symptoms included in the synthesis. I would like to see physical causes thoroughly ruled out before symptoms are labelled as mental health, or somatic symptoms labelled as "in your head" which unfortunately was my own experience. I hope this research helps GPs, paediatricians, neurologists, urologists, psychiatrists, and other clinicians recognise how physical and psychiatric symptoms can appear together, and approach families with understanding, care, and curiosity.

Lorna Nicholls. Adult with, and parent of child with PANS/PANDAS

Abstract

Introduction

Paediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) and Paediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) are related disorders whereby young people experience sudden onset of physical and neuropsychiatric symptoms, often causing significant distress. PANS and PANDAS may persist for years in a relapsing-remitting course. Despite an increase in research about the conditions, awareness remains low and a fragmented evidence base currently hampers progress in the field and limits the support available for patients and their families.

We produced an interactive Evidence and gap map (EGM), collating and presenting all published empirical evidence about PANS/PANDAS. We aimed to provide a clear overview of research on PANS/PANDAS, clarifying gaps in the evidence and helping to direct future research.

Methods

We searched 15 bibliographic databases on 11th and 12th August 2025 from inception, with no language restrictions. We also searched relevant websites and performed author searches and forward and backward citation searching. We sought any empirical evidence about PANS/PANDAS (or related terms CANS and PITANDS). Included studies were coded and published in an EGM using EPPI-reviewer/mapper. We sorted studies by research topic (diagnosis, epidemiology, aetiology/pathophysiology, treatment, symptoms, access to services, experiences), and coded details about study design, treatments, symptoms, professionals involved, study settings, equity considerations and participant characteristics.

Screening and coding were performed in duplicate. We engaged with youth diagnosed with PANS/PANDAS and parents of children with the conditions throughout the review. This engagement particularly influenced the design of the coding framework and map and supported our interpretation of the evidence.

Results

After deduplication, we screened 9218 records at title and abstract, and 730 at full text. We included 445 pieces of research in the EGM, of which 107 were conference abstracts. There were five RCTs, and only 14% of studies were prospective cohort studies, 74% of all records being

retrospective or case-based designs. Studies about the experience of PANS/PANDAS began to emerge in 2013, and we included 18 qualitative studies. About half of the evidence came from the USA, with under 5% originating from the UK. Evidence production increased substantially since 2015, and 47% of papers were published since 2020. New primary studies and systematic reviews are needed across all research areas, perhaps most urgently relating to aetiology and pathophysiology, which could then underpin improved diagnosis and treatment. Existing treatments lack rigorous evaluation in PANS/PANDAS patients, but focus on either tackling underlying infections (e.g. antibiotics, tonsillectomy), modulating the immune system (intravenous immunoglobulins, anti-inflammatories) or manifested symptoms (behavioural and psychological therapy, psychiatric medication).

Conclusions

The EGM provides a single point of reference for those seeking information about PANS/PANDAS. It is comprehensive and interactive, opening up the evidence to a range of audiences. The EGM is an important and necessary step to help direct future research about PANS/PANDAS. Research is currently dominated by studies of lower scientific rigour, limiting the extent to which we can understand the conditions, or advance knowledge about diagnosis or treatment.

Plain English summary

Why did we do this study?

Paediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) and Paediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) are related disorders whereby young people, most commonly around the age of seven, suddenly experience several physical and psychiatric symptoms. PANS and PANDAS may persist for years, usually getting much worse at certain points during the year. The symptoms of PANS/PANDAS can be extremely severe and have a huge impact on families.

The amount of research about PANS and PANDAS has been increasing since the conditions were first named in the late 1990s, but there is a lack of consensus about almost all aspects of the conditions. This uncertainty covers the causes and diagnosis of the conditions, how to treat them, and what it is like to live with PANS or PANDAS. This lack of agreement makes it difficult to decide where future research should be focused. It also means that patients, families and suspected patients experience additional challenges beyond those presented by having the conditions.

We conducted an 'Evidence and gap map' (EGM) which is a way of collecting and organising all published evidence about PANS/PANDAS and presenting it in one place via an interactive display. By doing this, anyone using the EGM could find out how much research has been done on any aspect of the conditions, and where there are gaps in the evidence.

The EGM was therefore intended to provide a clear overview of research on PANS/PANDAS. Its purpose was to:

- 1) Allow people with an interest in PANS/PANDAS to see all the research on the topic, and easily find studies
- 2) Make it easy to see where new studies are needed to improve our understanding of PANS/PANDAS
- 3) Help plan future reviews of the evidence, which can provide greater consensus about the different areas of the field (causes, diagnosis, treatment, experiences etc)

What did we do?

We aimed to find every study about PANS/PANDAS that collected some data. To do this, we searched comprehensively and included any type of study, except for letters, opinion pieces, editorials and literature reviews (that weren't 'systematic'). We also searched relevant websites, looked for studies that were in progress or about to be published, and included presentations from conferences. All included studies focused on people with a diagnosis of PANS or PANDAS.

Once we screened out all the irrelevant studies, we went through them all to categorise what they were about. This meant that, once they were in the EGM, they could be found by their key characteristics – for example, map users could search specifically for studies about diagnosis, or those that talk about sleep difficulties as a symptom. We coded dozens of characteristics to make the EGM detailed.

After coding the features of each study, we produced the EGM and made it available online.

Throughout this project, the team of reviewers worked closely with clinical experts, a senior representative of the PANS PANDAS UK charity, young people with the conditions, and parents of young people with the conditions.

What did we find?

We included 445 individual pieces of research in the EGM, of which 338 were full studies and 107 were conference presentations. About half of the studies came from the USA, and there was very little from the UK. A lot of the research was of lower scientific rigour, coming from case studies that describe one patient, or a small number of patients, at a time. This type of evidence is not very useful for patients or healthcare providers. The rate at which evidence has been produced has increased a lot in the last 10 years, but there are still large gaps in the understanding of PANS/PANDAS.

It is evident that much more research is needed on PANS/PANDAS, however by producing the EGM it is now easier to see where this evidence is needed most. Some key findings were:

- 1) There is scope for evidence reviews in almost every area of research, which could help update and solidify understanding in the field.

- 2) New studies are needed in every area, but perhaps most urgently about the causes and clinical features of the conditions. Without this, all other areas of understanding are held back, particularly diagnosis and treatment.
- 3) The treatments tended to focus on tackling the infection that triggered symptoms, or treating symptoms directly. However these were mostly case studies, and there was very little evidence to support these approaches in patients with PANS/PANDAS. There is enough evidence to conduct a new review of these treatments to help inform clinical practice.
- 4) Studies reporting on the experiences of PANS/PANDAS have emerged in the last ten years, and they should be combined in a review, so that we can develop a clearer understanding of what patients, families and clinicians have experienced.

In summary

Overall, there are a lot of studies about PANS and PANDAS, but the vast majority are of low rigour and offer little value when seeking to understand the conditions, or advance knowledge about diagnosis or treatment. However, the recent surge in evidence offers some promise, and at least an increased level of attention. By collating the evidence and presenting it in an EGM, we have provided a valuable resource that will allow patients, carers and clinicians to access research, and help plan for future studies.

Background

Paediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) and Paediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) are related complex disorders characterised by acute onset of multiple somatic and/or neuropsychiatric symptoms in children which may persist for years in a relapsing/remitting course.¹

The term PITANDS (Paediatric Infection-Triggered Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders) was defined by Allen and colleagues in 1995, to describe a subgroup of children with obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) who presented with a sudden onset of their usual psychiatric symptoms, typically following an infection caused by a variety of pathogens.² In 1998, Swedo and colleagues reported on a subset of cases that were initiated by a Group A streptococcal infection (GAS), and the term PANDAS was proposed.³ This was differentiated from other childhood onset OCD disorders by five clinical criteria: 1, presence of OCD and/or tic disorder; 2, pre-pubertal onset of symptoms; 3, acute symptom onset with a fluctuating course (this may be relapsing-relapsing (periods of neuropsychiatric flares followed by a period of remission), episodic, sawtooth, progressing or chronic course, with age of onset, illness duration, comorbidities and patient's sex being contributing factors); 4, association with neurological signs (in particular choreiform movements and motor hyperactivity) and 5, a temporal association with a Group A streptococcal infection (GAS).³

The broader term PANS (of which PANDAS is considered a subset) was first proposed in 2012 by Swedo and colleagues, to define disorders that may be associated with a previous infection, but not limited to GAS, and also acute neuropsychiatric disorders without an apparent infectious cause, i.e. environmental triggers.⁴ The diagnostic criteria proposed for PANS were: 1, abrupt dramatic onset of OCD or severe restricted food intake (<48 hours); 2, concurrent presence of two or more additional neuropsychiatric symptoms, with similarly severe and acute onset; 3, symptoms are not better explained by a known neurologic or medical disorder, such as Sydenham's chorea, systemic lupus erythematosus, Tourette disorder or others.⁵ PANS may follow a relapsing-remitting course.^{5, 6} Despite the availability of definitions for PANS/PANDAS, there is lack of consensus about aetiology, diagnosis and treatment.

Epidemiological data relating to the incidence, prevalence and demographic characteristics of PANS and PANDAS are equivocal, fuelled by an absence of global agreement on the symptomatology and course of the conditions.⁷ Difficulty establishing the association between

the onset/recurrence of symptoms and a GAS infection for PANDAS have been reported,^{8, 9} with some patients asymptomatic carriers of GAS.¹⁰ This is further complicated by uncertainties around the potential lag time between a GAS infection and symptom onset of PANDAS.⁹ Conflicting findings in immunological and epidemiological studies about PANDAS reflect an equivocal evidence base, and this lack of clarity contributes to the potential for underdiagnosis or misdiagnosis.⁸ Furthermore, adult cases of PANS and PANDAS have been described, adding to uncertainties around prevalence, incidence and aetiology.¹¹ There is currently no universally agreed diagnostic biomarker or test that allows for an unambiguous diagnosis of PANS or PANDAS and due to the presentation of symptoms being similar to other neuropsychiatric or neurodevelopmental syndromes or autoimmune diseases, the diagnosis of PANS or PANDAS involves carefully excluding other conditions that share phenotypic overlap.⁸ The absence of a diagnostic biomarker and reliance on accurate and expert application of clinical diagnostic criteria is common for many neuropsychiatric conditions.

Symptoms of PANS or PANDAS can vary extensively in their nature, as can disease trajectory, increasing the difficulty of diagnosis and treatment.¹² Relatedly, misdiagnosis and no diagnosis are documented concerns.^{12,13} Many individuals struggle to get a diagnosis, may experience multiple misdiagnoses or diagnostic overshadowing (especially in those with a neurodivergent diagnosis), and may experience symptoms for years before receiving a diagnosis.¹⁴ The impact on those experiencing PANS/PANDAS and their families can be life-changing, all-consuming, isolating and traumatic.^{12, 15}

Even when diagnosis is made, there is no clear consensus on treatment, which requires multidisciplinary input.⁸ There are two international peer reviewed treatment guidelines for PANS and PANDAS,¹⁶⁻¹⁹ and work towards UK guidelines is in progress.²⁰ Despite these guidelines there are often long delays in obtaining appropriate treatment and care.²¹ There is a lack of robust data about treatment effectiveness from randomised controlled trials (RCTs), which hampers treatment consensus,⁸ and renders some interventions as controversial or experimental.¹⁸ Of published systematic reviews on treatments for either PANS or PANDAS,²²⁻²⁵ not all cover the full range of treatment options, or only focus on one of the two conditions. The review by Sigra and colleagues is perhaps the most comprehensive to date, and while they reported a paucity of RCTs on treatments for PANS/PANDAS, they highlighted a larger number of case reports or case series.²⁵ The dearth of RCT evidence is unsurprising, given the challenges of designing and conducting such trials. These challenges include the ethical considerations when randomising PANS/PANDAS patients to a control group, the relatively low numbers of patients, and the

heterogeneous nature of symptoms. The need for clarity about treatment for PANS/PANDAS is reflected in the James Lind Alliance top 10 priorities for childhood neurological disorders.²⁶

Given the lack of clarity about all domains of understanding of PANS/PANDAS, we aimed to map all empirical evidence about the condition, across the domains of treatment, diagnosis, experiences, and epidemiology. Organising the evidence in an evidence and gap map (EGM) will help inform the direction of further evidence synthesis on PANS and PANDAS, especially regarding treatment, highlighting where future primary research needs to be focussed to help bridge any identified gaps. It will also provide an accessible resource for patients, parents/families/carers, clinicians, health and social care professionals, education professionals, researchers, and organisations alike.

An EGM is a visual, interactive representation of the distribution of evidence about a topic according to predefined characteristics. Correspondingly, it also highlights areas where there is no evidence. Examples of previous EGMs are found below:

- Occupational Health interventions: [EPPI-Mapper](#)²⁷
- Topical steroid withdrawal: [EPPI-Mapper](#)²⁸

Aims and objectives

The aims of this EGM were to:

- Identify all existing empirical evidence related to PANS/PANDAS
- Arrange and display the evidence to highlight areas of abundant research, or gaps in the evidence

The production of a comprehensive EGM on PANS/PANDAS would establish the feasibility and usefulness of one or more focussed evidence syntheses on treatments, experiences or epidemiology of PANS/PANDAS.

Methods

The protocol for this review was prospectively registered and is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17224506>. Production of an EGM involves the following stages:²⁹

- 1) Agree/define a framework
- 2) Comprehensive search for evidence
- 3) Screening of identified studies against predefined inclusion/exclusion criteria
- 4) Extraction of key characteristics from included studies
- 5) Production of the map to display the evidence and its characteristics

Identification of studies

The search strategy was developed by an information specialist (AB) in Medline and translated into other databases. The searches used a combination of controlled vocabulary terms (e.g. Medical Subject Headings, or MeSH) and free text terms. The search strategy used for Medline via Ovid is shown below. All search strategies are shown in Appendix I

. References were managed using Endnote 2025 (Clarivate Analytics, US).

Medline (Ovid) (11/08/25):

1	(P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*).tw.	342
2	(P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	8
3	(P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	1
4	(child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*).tw.	16
5	(child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	0
6	(child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	0
7	(P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	175
8	(P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*).tw.	6
9	(P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	7
10	(child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*).tw.	2
11	(child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	27
12	(child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	6
13	(pans or pandas).tw.	2078
14	(child* or p?ediatric* or juvenile* or youth* or young* or adolesc*).tw.	2996157
15	adolescent/ or exp child/ or exp infant/	4194726
16	14 or 15	5383393
17	13 and 16	562
18	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 7 or 8 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 17	2154
19	(pitand or pitands).tw.	8
20	(obsessive adj2 compulsive* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*)).tw.	19747
21	(abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*).tw.	1993407
22	((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*) adj3 (obsessive adj2 compulsive* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*))).tw.	113
23	(tic or tics or tourette* or food intake*).tw.	71911

24	((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*) adj3 (tic or tics or tourette* or food intake*).tw.	
	479	
25	16 and 24	87
26	(streptococ* or immune* or infect*).tw.	3142217
27	(disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*).tw.	3837671
28	autoimmun* neuropsychiatric*.tw.	369
29	26 and 27 and 28	350
30	Streptococcal Infections/	36316
31	(neuropsychiatric* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*).tw.	23389
32	30 and 31	285
33	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 17 or 19 or 22 or 25 or 29 or 32	
	825	

Fifteen bibliographic databases were searched on the 11th and 12th of August 2025: Medline (from 1945), Embase (from 1974), PsycINFO (from 1806) and Social Policy & Practice (SPP) (from 1890) via OvidSP; CINAHL Ultimate (from 1937) and ERIC (from 1996) via EBSCOhost; SCI-Expanded, SSCI (from 1990), AHCI (from 1975), CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH (from 1990), and ESCI (from 2005) via Web of Science; Epistemonikos and the Cochrane Library, both CENTRAL (from 1908) and CDSR (from 1996). The databases were searched from inception with no date or language restrictions.

For supplementary searching, forward and backward citation searching was performed on all included references using either SpiderCite via TERA (The Evidence Research Accelerator), a platform operated by Bond University and the Institute for Evidence-Based Healthcare, or Scopus. For any references not indexed in SpiderCite or Scopus, Google Scholar was used to perform forward citation searching; and manual backward citation searching was conducted for these references.

Additional supplementary searching was carried out via author searches and website/organisation searches. Three prominent authors in the field –Susan E. Swedo, Jennifer Frankovich, and Tanya K. Murphy– were searched using Google Scholar and ResearchGate (researchgate.net). Swedo was manually searched through their attributed publications list on ResearchGate, whilst Frankovich and Murphy were searched on Google Scholar. Frankovich was searched using the terms *Frankovich PANS PANDAS*, whilst Murphy’s Google Scholar profile was manually searched. Five relevant websites were also searched: PANS PANDAS UK (panspandasuk.org), PANDAS Physician network (pandasppn.org), PANDAS Network (pandasnetwork.org), Child Mind Institute (childmind.org), and Aspire Care (aspire.care).

Supplementary searching was undertaken through the Undermind Research Assistant (undermind.ai), a research retrieval system powered by artificial intelligence. Prompts used for querying Undermind and its responses are available in Appendix I.

Clinical trial records (the registered records of ongoing, planned or completed trials, hosted on trials registries) and protocols retrieved from database searching were investigated to determine if any publications followed trial completion. When a publication was located for a clinical trial record or protocol, the record was removed as a duplicate, and any new publications identified via these methods were screened for eligibility. Clinical trial records and protocols for which no publications could be found were evaluated for inclusion based on any information provided in the record. For clinical trial records or protocols that had no completion date listed, no publications, and no reported results, the Principal Investigators (PIs) of the study were contacted via email to ask for any linked or planned publications.

Inclusion/exclusion criteria

In essence, we included any study reporting empirical evidence about PANS/PANDAS. The detailed inclusion and exclusion criteria are provided in Table 1 in Appendix II, but are summarised below.

Population:

All (children, adolescents, and adults).

Phenomena of Interest:

Studies had to be about Paediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) or Paediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS). Studies where the condition was described as Paediatric Infection-Triggered Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders (PITANDS) or Childhood Acute Neuropsychiatric Symptoms (CANS) were also included, as these terms are synonymous with PANS/PANDAS. We relied on study authors to describe/diagnose patients; as such, studies presenting patients with relevant symptoms, but without diagnosing them with PANS/PANDAS (or related terms) were ineligible.

We used established definitions for PANS,⁴ PANDAS,³ CANS,^{25, 30} and PITANDS.² Elaboration on these definitions is available in the protocol.

We included studies on broader categories of conditions, within which PANS/PANDAS could be captured, such as Postinfectious Autoimmune Encephalopathy (PAE). Similarly, studies exploring patients with tic disorders, or patients with OCD symptoms, were eligible so long as separate data for subsamples of patients with PANS or PANDAS was available.

Along the same themes as above, the following conditions, with some overlap of presentations/symptoms to PANS/PANDAS were ineligible:

- Sydenham's chorea
- Kleine-Levin syndrome

Study design:

All empirical quantitative and qualitative studies were eligible. We included relevant conference abstracts, pre-prints and clinical trial records to capture the most up to date research. Any that were linked with subsequent publications were superseded by them. To be included as a systematic review, a review was required to report the key features, based on criteria set out by Krnic Martinic et al.³¹

Limits and restrictions

There was no limit on date, geographical context or language. Non-English language studies were translated where possible using Google Translate.

Process for applying inclusion criteria.

After piloting inclusion criteria and screening instructions on a sample of 150 records, the title and abstract of each record was screened by two independent reviewers (SF, MN, AS, RW, RA) to identify records that were clearly irrelevant. Disagreements were resolved by discussion. The full text of each record carried forwards was then screened by two independent reviewers (SF, MN, AS, RA, RW, TW, PS) to determine inclusion, with disagreements resolved through discussion, and a third reviewer acting as arbiter if necessary. Articles excluded at the full text screening stage were coded to indicate the first reason for exclusion.

Critical appraisal

No critical appraisal was performed.

Framework development and data extraction

Given the broad and varied research included, the EGM could be structured in a range of ways. As a research team, we considered different possibilities, drew upon relevant recent literature on PANS/PANDAS,^{8, 32} and conferred with the clinical experts (AL, ML) and a representative of the PANS PANDAS UK charity (KH), who were part of the commissioning team for this research. We also met with our PPIE group, to discuss the framework for the EGM. After piloting, and revisiting the coding framework during the coding process, we made further revisions. The final framework is described below:

Dimensions

Date of publication in five-yearly categories was used to form the rows in the map, with 2025 a stand-alone row.

Research topics formed the columns in the map. All the studies in the map were coded to indicate the focus, or research topic, of the study. In some instances, studies were concerned with several topics and so appear in more than one section of the map. The research topics are described as follows, with a full list of sub-categories for each research topic available in Appendix III:

- Diagnosis: studies concerned with diagnosis of PANS/PANDAS, such as establishing diagnostic criteria, using tools to aid diagnosis, or clarifying diagnosis vs other similar conditions.
- Epidemiology: studies which seek to establish the prevalence or patterns of disease, flare onset or relapse. For example, a study which examines rates of PANDAS diagnosis among a larger group of children.
- Aetiology/pathophysiology: studies which seek to identify factors that might cause PANS/PANDAS, or which described the conditions in detail. For example, these studies may look at scans or blood samples to identify biological markers associated with the conditions or describe the onset of symptoms in relation to potential triggers.
- Symptoms: studies in this category are focused on describing specific symptoms associated with PANS/PANDAS.
- Treatment: these studies have evaluated the effectiveness of treatments for PANS/PANDAS.
- Treatment aims: studies in this category are also in the Treatment category but are described here in terms of what the treatments were intended to resolve. For example,

treatments may have aimed to tackle infections, or manage specific symptoms, or resolve flares.

- Access to services: these studies are concerned with issues relating to accessing services, such as obtaining diagnosis, or getting treatment and support.
- Experiences: studies within this category aimed to capture the experiences of PANS/PANDAS. This might be patient, parent or clinician experiences, typically captured through surveys or interviews.

Filters for presentation

The map has the following filters available:

Map Filters	
Condition:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PANS ➤ PANDAS ➤ CANS ➤ PITANDS
Population Age:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Infants (0-3 years) ➤ Children (4-12 years) ➤ Adolescents (13-17 years) ➤ Adults (18+ years)
Countries (list of all countries in map)	
Study Region:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Africa ➤ Asia ➤ Caribbean ➤ Central America ➤ Europe ➤ North America ➤ Oceania ➤ South America
Study Design:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Systematic review ➤ Randomised controlled trial ➤ Prospective cohort study ➤ Retrospective/cross-sectional/observational study ➤ Case report/case series ➤ Qualitative study
Length of follow-up:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Less than 6 months ➤ 6-12 months ➤ More than 12 months
Treatment –classes of drugs:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Antianxiety ➤ Antibiotics ➤ Anticonvulsants ➤ Antidepressants ➤ Antifungals ➤ Antihistamines

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Anti-inflammatory ➤ Antipsychotics ➤ Antivirals ➤ Biologics ➤ Immunoglobulins ➤ Mast cell stabilisers ➤ Mood stabilisers ➤ Other
<p>Treatments (other):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Acupuncture ➤ Adverse/side effects ➤ Behavioural and psychological interventions ➤ Dietary modifications ➤ Plasmapheresis/therapeutic plasma exchange (TPE) ➤ Holistic treatment (e.g. functional medicine) ➤ Homeopathy ➤ Probiotics ➤ Surgery ➤ Vitamins ➤ Other
<p>Treatment aims (same as research topic list)</p> <p>Symptoms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Anxiety ➤ Behavioural/developmental regression ➤ Bladder/urinary issues (e.g. enuresis, urinary urgency and frequency, pain, incontinence etc) ➤ Cognitive/memory issues ➤ Delusions ➤ Depression ➤ Deterioration in school performance ➤ Emotional highs/lows ➤ Facial grimace ➤ Fatigue ➤ Handwriting challenges ➤ Hallucinations ➤ Hyperactivity/attention deficit ➤ Intrusive thoughts ➤ Impulsiveness ➤ Irritability, aggression, rage ➤ Movement disorder ➤ Obsessive/compulsive behaviour/ritualistic behaviour ➤ Pain ➤ Pathological demand avoidance (PDA) behaviours ➤ Restrictive eating ➤ Sensory issues (sensitivity to sound/touch etc) ➤ Separation anxiety ➤ Sleep difficulties ➤ Speech difficulties ➤ Speech repetition (e.g. echolalia, palilalia etc) ➤ Social withdrawal ➤ Suicidal ideation ➤ Swallowing difficulties ➤ Tics (e.g. verbal, motor) ➤ Other
<p>Setting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Community

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hospital ➤ Primary care ➤ Private clinic ➤ Research facility ➤ School/education
Support:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Challenging behaviour ➤ Educational ➤ Financial ➤ Medical
Health Categories (two sections, one for whole study and one for subgroup analysis):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Gender/sex ➤ Race/ethnicity/culture/language ➤ Occupation ➤ Education ➤ Income ➤ Place of residence
Health Professionals:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Allied health professional ➤ Dermatologist ➤ Education/teaching staff (including Special Educational Needs (and Disabilities) Coordinator (SENCO/SENDSCO)) ➤ ENT specialist ➤ Gastroenterologist ➤ General practitioner ➤ Immunologist ➤ Neurologist ➤ Nursing staff ➤ Paediatrician ➤ Psychiatrist ➤ Psychologist ➤ Social worker ➤ Urologist ➤ Unknown ➤ Other
Article Type:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Clinical trial registration ➤ Conference abstract ➤ Journal article ➤ Abstract only

EPPI-Reviewer software³³ was used to create a standardised data extraction coding set, which was piloted and refined before commencement of full coding. The coding set reflected the items described in the framework above. Multiple reports for the same study were treated as one study. Coding was performed by one reviewer and checked by a second, with disagreements discussed within the review team (SF, MN, PS, AS, TW, RW, RA).

Coding clarifications

We applied the following rules and clarifications during coding:

- For a study to be coded with *treatment* as the research topic, there had to be some measure of effectiveness of the treatments described, i.e. quantification or qualification of their effect. For example, in case reports/series, informal descriptions of treatment effectiveness were permitted. Where the topic focus was treatment, but the content was not about effectiveness (e.g. prescribing patterns, experience of treatments), treatment was coded as ‘Other’ and additional coding performed for clarification.
- We coded intravenous immunoglobulins (IVIg), therapeutic plasma exchange (TPE) and plasmapheresis as related treatments within their own category under the *treatments* research topic. They were subsequently coded together as ‘Modulating the immune system’ under the *treatment aims* research topic, however we acknowledge that many, if not all of the mapped treatments could be considered to fit within this category. For other treatments, we coded them according to the primary mechanism of action, as described by study authors, for example, corticosteroids as ‘targeting inflammation’.
- For case reports/series, only contemporary treatments, (i.e. not treatment histories, relative to the circumstances described in the paper) were coded in the *treatment* research topic.
- Studies that were coded in the *experiences* research topic, that incorporated experiences related to treatments, but did not include any effectiveness, had treatments and treatment aims coded, but only as filters.
- Regardless of whether the studies’ aims fell into the research topic of *symptoms*, all symptoms described, whether historical or contemporary, were coded in the *symptoms* filters.
- If a paper incorporated more than one study design, whilst both study designs were coded for the purpose of the ‘bubbles’, coding of the research topic/s was based on the highest-level study design, e.g. if a case report was nested within a retrospective study, research topics were coded according to the retrospective design. However, all symptoms mentioned were coded in the *symptoms* filters.

Methods for mapping and presentation

EPPI-Reviewer software³³ was used to create the EGM. The ‘surface’ or initially visible layer of the map was designed to display the types of study designs, represented by a different coloured bubble (black=Systematic Reviews, yellow=RCTs, green=prospective cohort studies, blue=retrospective/observational/cross-sectional studies, red=case reports/case series, pink=qualitative studies) in a matrix of publication date vs broad research topic.

Sub-categories of research topics can be hidden or expanded, for example evidence relating to *treatments* is divided by treatment type, creating a second layer of the map. The dimensions of the bubbles represent the number of studies/reviews available e.g. larger bubbles indicate more evidence.

Interactive cells in the map display a further layer of information, showing the available evidence for that particular research topic and date category. Clicking on any study/review listed will take the user to the abstract for that item and a link to access the full paper. Filters as described above were made available to allow users to refine their search within the evidence, e.g. for all studies on PANDAS within the UK.

The EGM aims to provide an overview and visual representation of the available evidence. We did not perform critical appraisal or synthesis of studies, nor was it the aim of this map to describe any study findings. We provide an overview of the key characteristics of the overall map, and of each research topic. Within this overview, we summarise key descriptive statistics and highlight where there is an abundance, or dearth of evidence. We explore observations that were considered relevant to the research team, interest holders, or PPIE representatives.

As per our second research objective, this informed suggestions for further evidence synthesis.

Interest holder and PPI Engagement

Aim of the PPIE activity

Parents and young people affected by PANS/PANDAS were involved so that the EGM was informed by lived experience, so that their knowledge and expertise shaped the research, and so the final output was relevant, accessible, and useful to patients, families, and other interest holders.

Methods used for involvement/engagement

The protocol for the map was developed with parents. The focus of the map was refined through discussions with parents about their experiences and priorities. The involvement opportunity was advertised via the PANS PANDAS UK charity website and social media as well as NIHR PenARC's local and national PPIE networks.

Over the course of three online meetings, we met with ten parents who had very wide-ranging experiences of caring for and supporting a child or young person with PANS/PANDAS. Discussions enabled parents' knowledge and expertise to inform decisions about what to include in the research topics and filters in the map. Group discussions were supplemented by individual e-mails to all interested parents (n=14) inviting feedback on the draft protocol and plain language summary of the protocol. This enabled some parents to share insights about specific symptoms that they preferred to raise one-to-one, rather than in a group setting.

The plain language summary of the protocol was shared with Isca Evidence's standing PPIE group, PERSPEX, to utilise a broader public perspective to further refine written materials for clarity and readability. PERSPEX, a group of 12 public collaborators who bring their carer, patient, or public perspective to the work of Isca Evidence. PERSPEX members meet monthly online, and membership is culturally, geographically, and demographically diverse.

A fourth meeting was held with parents to understand how well the map matched with their experiences and where they considered the significant gaps in evidence were. We also discussed experiences of interacting with the map and what support may be needed to enhance usability. A draft version of the completed map was shared with parents prior to meeting. Additional feedback on the map was sought via e-mail.

We held two online meetings with young people who have PANS/PANDAS. Both meetings were supported by PANS PANDAS UK and were advertised to the charity's Youth Board members. The Charity's Youth Support worker co-facilitated the meetings. The first meeting, attended by four young people with an age range of 8–22 years old, focussed on individual experiences and priorities. The second meeting, attended by five young people aged 16-22, presented the map and explored the mapped evidence in relation to individual's experiences, particularly examining gaps in evidence. The group also shared how the usability of the map could be improved. Feedback on the map was also invited within a closed social media app group managed by the Youth Support Worker.

All the involved parents and young people were remunerated for the meetings they attended in accordance with NIHR policies.

Outcomes of the PPIE activities

The PPIE activities made a substantive contribution to the mapping process and led to meaningful changes in its focus. Discussions with parents prompted a stronger emphasis on symptoms, the inclusion of symptoms previously under-represented in the research, and greater consideration of the impact on families. These conversations deepened the research team's understanding of PANS/PANDAS and highlighted the substantial challenges families and young people face when navigating health and support services. The outcomes of the PPIE activity were felt across the whole team, increasing motivation to ensure that the research meaningfully reflected the experiences shared. While the discussions were highly valuable, they also had an emotional impact on the parents, young people and researchers, as some of the content was challenging to share and receive. Overall, the PPIE activity strengthened the relevance and sensitivity of the research and expanded reporting on this can be found in the Impact of Public and Patient Involvement and Engagement section of the results.

Next steps for PPIE

We will continue to meet with parents and young people affected by PANS/PANDAS so that their expertise can support communicating the findings and highlighting areas for future research. We will co-create public facing dissemination materials and co-write complementary media items, such as blogs, to situate the findings within parents' and young people's experiences and share this work with a wide range of interested audiences.

Funding

This project was funded by the NIHR Evidence Synthesis Programme (grant number: NIHR153420) and several authors are supported by NIHR Applied Research Collaboration Southwest Peninsula (PenARC). The views expressed in this publication are those of the authors and not necessarily those of the NIHR or the Department of Health and Social Care.

Results

Study selection

Searches from bibliographic databases produced 5,260 results; 2,087 of these results were removed as duplicates in Endnote before screening began. The 3,173 records remaining after deduplication were screened at title and abstract; 2,506 records were excluded. Full texts were sought for the remaining 667 reports. There were 18 records that were unavailable for retrieval, leaving 649 to screen at full text. From this screening, 56 records were excluded as duplicates, 65 were excluded based on phenomenon of interest, five were excluded based on population, 60 were excluded based on publication type, and 52 were excluded based on study design. This led to 411 records being included in the EGM. All studies excluded at full text, with reasons, are available in Appendix IV.

From supplementary searches, 6,045 records were screened at title and abstract after deduplication. 5,964 records were subsequently excluded at title and abstract, leaving 81 to screen at full text. Of the records screened, 62 came from forward and backward citation searching, 11 from Undermind.ai, and eight from author searching. From this pool of records, three were excluded as duplicates, 23 were excluded for phenomenon of interest, five were excluded for publication type, and 16 were excluded for study design. Thirty-four records were therefore added in the map from supplementary searching. Added to the includes from database searches, the total number of included records in the map is 445. A summary of this information can be found in the PRISMA flow diagram in Figure 1.

Of the 24 clinical trial records and one protocol retrieved and initially included from database searches, eight Principal Investigators (PIs) were identified and contacted to request study results: seven for clinical trials and one for the protocol. Of those contacted, two responded, with one respondent being the PI for the included protocol. For four of the clinical trials without PI contact information, results were requested from the NIH, but none were received. Results were not requested for the remaining 14 clinical trials for the following reasons: 1) if there was no contact information, 2) the trials were found to be duplicates of other included trials, and 3) the trial records were matched with a publication that reported the results. Of the total 25 records of clinical trials and protocol(s), 10 were excluded as duplicates, 13 were excluded because of a lack of empirical data, and two were included.

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart summarising the results of the database search and supplementary searches

Characteristics of studies in the map

The EGM is accessible here: [\(link\)](#). Upon opening, a welcome message is displayed, explaining the map with text, and with a link to a video. Categories are initially collapsed, as shown in Figure 2 (A), and can be fully expanded to show all sub-categories of research topics, and all date categories (Figure 2, B).

(A)

(B)

Figure 2. (A) Screenshot showing the initial arrangement of the map when first accessing and closing the welcome message (full screen view). (B) Screenshot showing the map with all categories expanded, and the view zoomed out.

A total of 445 records were included in the EGM, consisting of 308 (69%) journal articles and 15 (3%) theses, 107 (24%) conference abstracts, 12 (3%) abstracts (where the full text of a journal article was not available, but the study was includable on the basis of the abstract) and one trial registration. There were also two pre-prints, which have not yet been peer reviewed.

The following descriptions apply to all studies except for conference abstracts, which are described separately in the Overview of Conference Abstracts

Evidence was distributed across research topics as shown in Figure 3, with *symptoms* (26%) most often coded, while *treatment effectiveness* (19%), *diagnosis* (18%) and *aetiology/pathophysiology* (19%) coded to a similar extent. *Access to services* was the least coded topic, with a 3% share. Each research topic is discussed in further detail in subsequent sections of the results.

Figure 3. Distribution of evidence by research topic

Publication rate has increased over time, with a combined 98 (29%) publications between 1995-2014, which expanded rapidly in 2015-2019 (24%, 80/338) and 2020-2024 (39%, 131/338). Nearly half (47%) of records were published in 2020 or later. Figure 4 depicts the increasing publication rate, which is currently approaching 50 records per year (projection of 39 papers in 2025 based on 29 records having been identified up to September 2025).

Figure 4. Rate of publications in PANS/PANDAS in papers per year within each date category in the evidence and gap map

However, while the volume of publications has increased rapidly, the majority of the evidence base can be attributed to retrospective/cross-sectional/observational studies and case studies/series (Figure 5). In 1999, there were two RCTs in the field, and by late 2025, there are still only five.³⁴⁻³⁸ Prospective cohort studies have quadrupled in number in the last decade, but still only represent 14% of the evidence. Qualitative evidence about PANS/PANDAS only emerged in 2015, with an interview study by McClelland and colleagues,³⁹ and since then a further 17 studies using qualitative evidence were identified. We found five systematic reviews meeting our inclusion criteria, three with a treatment focus,^{24,25,40} and two concerned with aetiology/pathophysiology and epidemiology.^{41, 42}

Figure 5. Distribution of evidence type by date. Case-case studies and case series; Retro/Cross/Obs-retrospective, cross-sectional and observational studies; Prospective-Prospective cohort studies; RCT-randomised controlled trials- Quali, qualitative

Half of all studies were conducted in North America (51%, 195,380), with Europe the second most common site (31%, 117/380). Eleven percent (42/380) were conducted in Asia, 4% (15/380) in Oceania, and 1% in other regions (Figure 6). Within North America, 96% (187/195) of studies were set in the USA. Only 13 (4%) studies were based in, or captured data from the UK. Typically, studies included children aged 4-12 (278/338, 82%) and adolescents aged 13-18 (61%, 205/338), but 53 (16%) studies included infants aged 0-3, and 75 (22%) studies included adults. PANDAS was the focus in 52% (176/338) of studies, PANS in 25% (85/338), and both conditions in 23% (77/338). Eight studies (2%) considered PITANDS, and one CANS (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Distribution of coding across study regions

Figure 7. Distribution of evidence by condition

A total of 54% (226/418) of studies were coded under *hospital settings*, *research facilities* (17%, 71/418) and the *community* (13%, 56/418) were next most frequently coded, and in 6% (24/418) of records it was not possible to tell where the study was set. The most frequently involved category of professional was psychiatrist (19%, 136/730), but this information was often not declared ('Unknown' in 111 studies, 33%). All categories of professional were coded at least once (Figure 8), but this item was often poorly reported.

Figure 8. Categories of professionals involved in research about PANS/PANDAS

Health equity was infrequently considered, with four records (1%, 4/338) coded as tailoring the study towards equity characteristics, which were *Gender/Sex*,⁴³⁻⁴⁶ *Place of residence*,⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹ *Ethnicity/race/cultural language*,⁴⁹ and *Occupation*.²¹ Analyses that were focused on equity-related characteristics were more common, occurring 38 times (11%, 38/338). Analysis by *Gender/sex* was completed 20 times, with *Income* (seven times), *Ethnicity/race/language* (four times), *Occupation* (once), *Education* (two times) and *Place of residence* (four times) also used to group results.

Overview of studies in the Diagnosis research topic

A total of 140 studies were coded under *diagnosis* as a research topic. Of these, 92% (129/140) of the studies focused exclusively on diagnosis, four examined diagnostic or screening tools alone, and seven were coded to both *diagnosis* and *diagnostic/screening tools*. Most records were full journal articles (96%, 135/140), with five available as abstract-only.

Study designs within this topic were predominantly case reports accounting for 66% (92/140) of the total, followed by retrospective/observational/cross-sectional designs (26%, 36/140), prospective cohort studies (5%, 7/140), and two qualitative studies (1%) (Figure 9). One record was assigned a dual design code, combining case report/series and prospective cohort methods, and focused only on diagnosis.⁵⁰

Figure 9. Distribution of coding of evidence in the diagnosis research topic, by study design

Studies addressing diagnosis were conducted across all global regions, with the largest contributions from North America, which accounted for 61 of the 152 codes (40%), followed by Europe (32%, 49/152) and Asia (21%, 32/152). Central America and Oceania accounted for 1% of the total number of codes each (2/152 codes for each) and Africa and South America were coded one time each (1% each) (Figure 10). The USA contributed the largest number of diagnosis-related studies (n=63), followed by Italy (n=16), India (n=11), Turkey (n=11), and Sweden (n=11).

Figure 10. Distribution of coding across study regions in the diagnosis research topic

Publication years ranged from 1995 to 2025. Six studies were published between 1995–1999, increasing steadily to 10 (2000–2004), 17 (2005–2009), 20 (2010–2014), 31 (2015–2019), 44 (2020–2024), and 12 studies published in 2025. Within these, two studies published between 2015–2019^{51, 52} and four published between 2020–2024^{8, 53-55} were coded to both *diagnosis* and *diagnostic/screening tools*.

Across condition categories, 24 studies addressed diagnosis of PANS only, with a further two focused on diagnostic/screening tools for PANS. For PANDAS, 89 studies related to diagnosis alone, and one study was coded to both *diagnosis* and *diagnostic/screening tools*. Studies addressing both PANS and PANDAS included six coded to both categories, 16 addressing diagnosis only, and two on diagnostic/screening tools only. One study focused on PITANDS² and no studies addressed CANS (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Distribution of coding frequency across the diagnosis sub-categories, by condition

Across population categories, 19 (9%) studies addressed diagnosis among children aged 0–3 years (18 diagnosis only, one diagnostic/screening tool only). In children aged 4–12 years, 111 (51%) studies were coded under *diagnosis* as a research topic, including 101 diagnosis-only studies, four focused solely on *diagnostic/screening tools* and six coded to both of these categories. Among adolescents, 67 studies were included (57 diagnosis only, six both, four diagnostic/screening tool only). Among adult populations, 22 studies were distributed over 18 diagnosis-only studies, one diagnostic/screening tool study, and three coded to both categories.

A small proportion of studies incorporated health equity–related considerations. One study addressed occupation as a health equity factor²¹ and one focused on place of residence.⁴⁸ Subgroup analyses were infrequent, with four studies examining gender, three addressing ethnicity/culture/race/language, two examining education, three analysing income, one addressing occupation, and two considering place of residence.

The studies under the diagnosis research topic were most frequently coded under *hospital* settings, which accounted for 69% of the codes (114/165). *Community*-based settings and *research facilities* each represented 9% of the codes (14/165 respectively), while *private clinics* accounted for 6% (10/165). *School or education* settings were infrequently coded (2%, 4/165), as was *primary care* (1%, 2/165). A small proportion of records did not specify a setting (4%, 7/165). Studies examining diagnostic tools only were similarly coded most frequently in a *hospital* setting

(50%, 7/14), followed by *community* (29%, 4/14), *research facility* (14%, 2/14) and finally, *educational settings* (7%, 1/14). None of these were conducted in private clinics or primary care (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Distribution of coding frequency across settings in the diagnosis sub-categories

Studies coded under the diagnosis research topic most frequently involved psychiatric and neurological professionals. *Psychiatry* accounted for the largest proportion of professional codes (23%, 81/350), followed by *neurology* (15%, 53/350) and *paediatrics* (15%, 51/350). *General practitioners* represented 9% of professional codes (31/350), while *psychology* accounted for a further 8% (28/350). Smaller proportions of studies involved *immunology* (3%, 12/350), *ENT (ear nose and throat) specialists* (3%, 11/350), *nursing staff* (3%, 9/350), *allied health professionals* (1%, 5/350), and *education or teaching staff* (2%, 6/350). In 8% of codes (28/350), the professional group involved was not specified.

A diverse range of additional health and social care professionals were grouped under the 'Other' category, which collectively accounted for 10% of professional codes (34/350). These included medical specialties such as rheumatology (coded 14 times), haematology, genetics, endocrinology, infectious diseases, allergy, dermatology, radiology, neuroradiology, gastroenterology, and internal medicine. Professionals involved in mental health and supportive care were also represented, including Child and Adolescent Mental Health Services (CAMHS), psychotherapists, mental health professionals, OCD therapists, occupational therapists, dieticians, paediatric movement disorder specialists and social care practitioners. In addition,

several studies reported involvement of professionals working in complementary or alternative approaches, such as holistic or functional medicine physicians, naturopathic treatment providers, and alternative medical practitioners, as well as clinical neurophysiologists with expertise in sleep medicine. Figure 13 represents the distribution of the coding for health and social care professionals across the sub-categories under the *diagnosis* research topic.

Figure 13. Distribution of health and social care professionals represented across the diagnosis and diagnostic/screening tool sub-categories of the diagnosis research topic

Overview of studies in the Epidemiology research topic

In this section, 70 individual records (68 journal articles and two abstracts) contained evidence related to epidemiology for PANS/PANDAS. This evidence came predominantly from retrospective/cross-sectional/observational studies (73%, 51/70) with prospective studies making up 17% (12/70) of the total. There were two systematic reviews that included epidemiological data^{42,41} and one RCT.³⁶ Three qualitative studies discussed epidemiology of PANS/PANDAS.^{8, 56, 57} One of these was a Delphi study⁸ and two had dual study designs coded to capture one being mixed-methods⁵⁷ and the other a cross-sectional design.⁵⁶ Three case reports were nested within three of the prospective studies.^{50, 58, 59}

The epidemiology research topic was divided into four sub-categories: *prevalence and incidence of onset*, *patterns for onset*, *prevalence and incidence for flares/relapses* and *patterns for flares/relapses*. Over half of the records (53%, 37/70) were coded for just one of the sub-categories; *patterns for onset* and *patterns for flares* being the largest two groups. Amongst the records that were coded across multiple sub-sections, most (67%, 22/33) were coded in two, and half of these were coded in the two sections relating to onset. There were six records in total that were coded across all four sub-categories.

When looking at the number of codes across the four sub-categories (rather than records), the two sub-sections relating to patterns were coded the most (see Figure 14).

Figure 14. Coding across epidemiology sub-categories

Figure 15 shows the coding of study designs for each sub-category of the *epidemiology* research topic. Evidence was drawn heavily from retrospective/cross-sectional/observational study designs, and across all study designs (except for the one RCT) there was a greater focus on

patterns rather than prevalence. In prospective studies, *patterns for flares/relapses* were coded twice as many times as *patterns for onset*.

Figure 15. Distribution of coding frequency within study designs across the epidemiological sub-categories

As shown in Figure 16, of the records in the epidemiology section that were coded for condition, 38% were focused on patients diagnosed with PANS (49/129), with a slightly smaller number coded for PANDAS, and for PANS and PANDAS (both 29%, 37/129). PITANDS was coded six times and there were no records that coded for CANS in this section.

Figure 16. Number of codes per condition across the epidemiology research topic section

All population categories were represented to some degree in the studies coded for epidemiology and commonly multiple age categories were coded per record, however the two largest population groups were children aged 4-12 (41%, 112/275) and adolescents 13-18 (36%, 98/275). The distribution of coding for population categories across the four sub-categories, (see Figure 17) reiterates *that patterns for onset* and *patterns for flares/relapses* were coded more frequently than prevalence sections, the number coded for *prevalence for onset* in the adult population category being especially low. In contrast to this, the *prevalence for onset* sub-category in the youngest age category (0-3) was the second greatest (and only marginally lower than the greatest) coded sub-category.

Figure 17. Distribution of coding for population category per epidemiology sub-category

North America and Europe are the two regions providing the most evidence on this topic (52% (76/147) and 31% (45/147) respectively). Asia and Oceania are the next two most coded study regions, but these make up only 15% (22/147) collectively. The Caribbean and Central America were the only two regions where no evidence was based. South America was represented in two studies^{57, 60} and Africa in one study.⁶¹ In terms of countries, the USA was the most frequently coded accounting for 39% (70/180) of overall coding, Sweden followed as the next most frequently coded country with 12% (21/180) and then Canada with 7% (14/180). Only four studies (represented by 3% of coding) were UK based or included patients from the UK.^{57, 62-64} The distribution of evidence across study regions between epidemiology sub-categories (see Figure 18) showed that the studies from Asia and Europe have had a greater focus on onset compared to North America where the focus has been more on flares/relapses.

Figure 18. Distribution of coding across study regions broken down by epidemiology sub-category

The rate of publication on epidemiology of PANS/PANDAS has risen significantly in recent years, as highlighted in Figure 19. The largest jump overall was between 2005 and 2014 where evidence across all four sub-sections increased, whereas prior to 2005, evidence about epidemiology was patchy and not all sub-sections were represented in the literature. From 2014 to 2024 evidence relating to patterns for onset and patterns for flares has risen exponentially, patterns for onset being the most frequently coded sub-category by 2024. So far in 2025, patterns for flares/relapses have been coded three times more than patterns for onset. Evidence related to prevalence of flares/relapses first appeared in the literature between 2005-2009 and has grown rapidly until 2019 but then plateaued over the next five years.

Figure 19. Frequency of coding across the years of publication broken down by epidemiology sub-category

Overview of studies in the Aetiology/pathophysiology research topic

A total of 151 unique records (45%) were coded under Aetiology/Pathophysiology, corresponding to 157 study designs. Most were full journal articles (95%, 144/151), with seven available as abstract-only. Retrospective, observational, or cross-sectional study designs were the most common code (62%, 93/151), followed by case reports or case series (32%, 48/151) and prospective cohort studies (8%, 12/151). Two (1%) systematic reviews,^{41, 42} along with one qualitative study,⁸ were also identified. Several records were assigned multiple design codes, including one study⁵⁸ coded to three categories including retrospective/observational/cross-sectional, prospective and case study/case series. Three studies were double-coded across categories: Han⁶⁵ and Cengel-Kultur⁵⁰ were each coded as both prospective cohort studies and case reports/series and Murphy⁵⁹ was coded as both a retrospective/observational/cross-sectional study and a case report/series.

Studies were conducted across all global regions, with the largest contributions from North America (46%, 79/171) and Europe (35%, 59/171), followed by Asia (12%, 20/171), Oceania (4%, 7/171), Central America (2%, 3/171), Africa (1%, 2/171), and South America (1%, 1/171). The USA contributed the greatest number of records (n=75), followed by Italy (n=24), Turkey (n=10), Sweden (n=8), and Australia (n=7). Five studies each originated from the United Kingdom, India, and Canada; all UK studies were retrospective/observational/cross-sectional in design.

Studies predominantly focused on children aged 4–12 years (48%), followed by adolescents aged 13–18 years (35%). Twenty-two studies (8%) involved infants aged 0–3 years, while adults (18 years and above) were included in 24 studies (9%). Across condition categories, 88 studies examined PANDAS, 40 examined PANS, and 21 included both conditions. One study focused on PITANDS² and one record encompassed PANS, PANDAS, and PITANDS.¹⁴ No studies were identified for CANS.

Publication dates ranged from 1995 to 2025. Four studies were published between 1995–1999, increasing to 13 in 2000–2004, 14 in 2005–2009, 22 in 2010–2014, 31 in 2015–2019, and 55 in 2020–2024. Twelve studies were published in 2025. Figure 20 shows the distribution of coding across the years of publication.

Figure 20. Distribution of coding across the years of publication for the aetiology/pathophysiology research topic

Only one study considered health equity factors in the context of aetiology/pathophysiology, addressing race, ethnicity, culture, language, and place of residence.⁴⁹

Overview of studies in the Symptoms research topic

There were two ways that symptoms were captured within the EGM, as a research topic and as a filter. For records to be coded into the *symptoms* research topic, the main focus of the study had to be about symptoms. Symptoms for filters were coded for every record where the individual symptoms were mentioned regardless of which research topic they were coded into.

Symptoms featured in the research topic of 200 records (59%) and was split across the four symptoms sub-categories with *emotional, behavioural, psychiatric symptoms* coded most frequently, featuring in 175/200 records (88%), followed by *physical symptoms* in 156/200 records (78%), *flares* in 82/200 records (41%), and *impact on functioning* in 59/200 records (30%). Figure 21 displays the distribution of all coding across broad symptom categories.

Figure 21. Distribution of symptom types coded in the evidence and gap map

Most of the evidence came from North America (48%, 111/230), Europe (31%, 72/230) and Asia (15%, 34/230); with the rest represented by Oceania (4%, 9/230), South America (1%, 3/230) and Africa (1%, 1/230). There was no evidence from Central America or the Caribbean. Figure 22 shows the distribution of the four symptom categories coded across different study regions. Within North America, 89% of the evidence came only from the USA, the remaining evidence comprised of research across Canada and the US (5%) or just from Canada (5%). Additionally,

the USA was most coded country (106 records), proceeded by Italy (n=23), Sweden (n=17), Turkey (n=13), Canada (n=13) and India (n=12). Evidence from the UK was reported in 10 records, reflecting 14% of evidence from Europe and 5% of evidence on symptoms overall.

Figure 22. The distribution of different symptom types coded across different study regions

Population category was reported in 99% of studies coded under the *symptoms* research topic. Children aged 4-12 and Adolescents aged 13-18 featured most in the evidence in 47% (163/346) and 32% (109/346) of records coded respectively. Adults (12%, 43/346) and Infants (9%, 31/346) were both coded less frequently in symptoms focused studies. The proportion of symptoms coded as *flares* increases alongside the age of participants, going from 42% in infants and children, to 50% in adolescents and finally 56% in adults.

Journal articles comprised 97% of records coded under *symptoms*, with abstracts forming the remaining 3%. Half of the abstracts focused solely on *emotional, behavioural and psychiatric symptoms*, with the other half reporting on multiple symptoms spread across all four symptom categories. Case reports/series were the most coded study design comprising 51% (106/208), followed by retrospective/observational/cross-sectional studies (35%, 73/208), prospective cohort studies (9%, 19/208), qualitative studies (3%, 7/208), plus two systematic reviews and one RCT. There were seven records which were coded for more than one study design. This was most

prevalent within qualitative studies with 50% of qualitative records also including another study design. These mixed-methods papers included cross-sectional surveys^{57, 66} and case studies⁶⁷ alongside qualitative methods. All four symptom categories are represented across the different study designs, except within systematic reviews where *flares* and *impact on functioning* do not feature within research topics.

The number of studies on symptoms has increased significantly over time, following the rapid expansion of the PANS/PANDAS evidence base. Starting at an average of less than one publication per year in 1995-1999, it had increased to 15.6 per year in 2020-2024. This trend continues, with 19 records identified for 2025 so far. Although *emotional, behavioural, psychiatric symptoms* are the most coded overall, they were overtaken by *physical symptoms*, in 2025, which became the most coded symptom that year (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Distribution of coding by date of publication in the symptoms research topic, broken down by symptom sub-category

Individual symptoms for filters, such as anxiety, were coded in 311 records, 64% of which also came under the *symptoms* research topic. The most common symptoms were also more likely to be coded in research topics other than *symptoms* (Figure 24), such as *obsessive-compulsive behaviour/ritualistic behaviour* and *tics*, which often form part of the stated diagnostic criteria.

Consequently, the most coded symptoms appear in most records, despite being more prone to not being wholly captured within the *symptoms* research topic.

Figure 24. The relationship between the number of records coded for each individual symptoms and percentage of records not captured under the symptoms research topic

Across the four symptom sub-categories, the most prevalent individual symptoms are mostly homogenous, with *obsessive compulsive behaviour/ritualistic behaviour* being the most common across all four categories: followed by *tics*, *anxiety* and *irritability, aggression and rage* in the *emotional, behavioural, psychiatric, physical* and *flares* sub-categories. This is reflected in the overall frequency of symptoms coded, as illustrated in Figure 25. The *Impact on functioning* category had more variation; after *obsessive compulsive behaviour/ritualistic behaviour*, the most coded symptoms were *anxiety, sleep difficulties, and tics*.

The ‘Other’ category, under the symptoms filter, was coded in 130 records, making it the 7th most coded symptom. Extraction of the free text within this category revealed 296 symptoms that fell outside the EGM tool. The majority of these were specific physical and psychiatric symptoms (69%), with the most common category being gastrointestinal related symptoms (8%), specific motor or tic related symptoms (6%) like “milkmaid grip”, and self-harm/violence (5%). Patients’

comorbidities and additional psychiatric diagnoses made up 24% of symptoms coded under *other*, ranging from psychiatric conditions like schizophrenia and eating disorders, to neurodiverse diagnoses like autism, and physical conditions such as arthritis. Additionally, symptoms pertaining to functioning and difficulties navigating school and social situations made up 6% of symptoms, describing school avoidance, difficulties socialising and selfcare issues. See Appendix V for full details of all symptoms coded under '*Other*'.

Figure 25. Coding frequency of all symptoms in the evidence and gap map

Overview of studies in the Treatment research topic

There were 152 unique records in the *treatment* research topic, with 154 study designs coded. Of these, three (2%, 3/152) were systematic reviews, eight (5%, 8/152) were RCTs (8 papers from 5 trials), 14 (9%, 14/152) were prospective cohort studies, 24 (16%, 24/152) were retrospective/cross-sectional/observational studies, 104 (68%) were case studies/series, and one was a qualitative study about experiences of treatments. The RCTs evaluated therapeutic plasma exchange (TPE) and intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIg),³⁵ penicillin as prophylaxis,³⁴ prophylaxis with azithromycin or penicillin,³⁶ IVIg,³⁷ and azithromycin.³⁸ Of the three remaining items in the RCT category, two were associated with the 2016 RCT of IVIg by Williams and colleagues; a thesis⁶⁸ and a follow-up paper;⁶⁹ and there was the trial registry report of a terminated RCT of *Panzyga*, a form of IVIg, by OctaPharma.⁷⁰

Figure 26 provides a representation of the focus of *treatment* studies by treatment type and study design, focusing on quantitative evaluations. *Antibiotics* were most often evaluated, however only 4% of the evidence for this treatment was prospective in nature (prospective cohort or RCT design). The area with the most prospectively obtained evidence was Intravenous immunoglobulin therapy (IVIg), therapeutic plasma exchange (TPE)/plasmapheresis (11/59, 19%). The second largest treatment category was *psychiatric medication*, but every study in this category was retrospective in nature (n=5) or a case study/series (n=57). *Behavioural and psychological interventions* (e.g. cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT)) was the second most abundant source of prospective cohort studies (n=4).

Figure 26. Distribution of treatment types by quantitative study design in the treatment research topic. Case - case studies and case series; Retro - retrospective, cross-sectional and observational studies; RCT - randomised controlled trials. IVIg – intravenous immunoglobulin therapy; TPE – therapeutic plasma exchange

Most records included children aged 4-12 (51%, 115/225), with adolescents aged 13-18 years (71/225, 32%) also commonly included (Figure 27). Infants (5%, 13/225) and adults (12%, 26/225) were less likely to have been included in treatment studies. Figure 28 depicts the number of records coded for each of the *treatment* research topics, broken down by the four population categories. The most coded treatment study across all four age groups was *antibiotics*, followed by *IVIg, TPE/plasmapheresis* for *infants, children and adolescents*. For adults, their second most coded treatment study was *psychiatric medication*. Infants were the only age group with no records coded for *anticonvulsants, surgery and biologics*.

Figure 27. Distribution of evidence in the treatment research topic, by patient age

Figure 28. The distribution of the treatment research topic across the four population categories; illustrating the number of records coded for each treatment topic divided by age group. IVIg – intravenous immunoglobulin therapy; TPE – therapeutic plasma exchange.

Patients were diagnosed with PANS in 32 studies (21%, 32/152), PANDAS in 94 studies (62%, 94/152), both PANS and PANDAS in 25 studies (16%, 25/152), and there were three studies (2%, 3/152) where the diagnosis was PITANDS. Some treatment types received greater attention within specific diagnoses, as shown in Figure 29. For example, antibiotics was evaluated with PANDAS patients 63 times, or 30% of all PANDAS treatment evaluations, and PANS patients 11 times, or in 17% of all PANS treatment evaluations. Other treatments tested noticeably more within PANDAS than PANS were surgery and psychiatric medication, while the reverse was true for IVIg, TPE/plasmapheresis, anti-inflammatory therapy, and antihistamines.

Figure 29. For each treatment type, the relative focus of evidence about effectiveness per diagnostic group is displayed - the percentage represents the proportion of evidence focused on evaluating that treatment, for patients with that particular diagnosis. IVIg – intravenous immunoglobulin therapy; TPE – therapeutic plasma exchange.

The majority of evidence came from North America (50%, 79/159) and Europe (31%, 49/159), with 15% (25/159) from Asia. There was no evidence from South America, the Caribbean or Central America. The USA was the most frequently coded country where evidence was evaluated (77 times), with Italy the next most frequent with 17 studies set there. India (n=11) and Sweden (n=9) and were next; the UK was coded across 6 treatments due to a systematic review originating from the country,⁴⁰ but a single case study represented the only primary research conducted in the UK.⁷¹

Consistent with evidence across the EGM, the rate of publication within the *treatment* research topic has accelerated in recent years, moving from 13 records by 2004 to 51 by 2014, and 152 by September 2025. While the number of prospective cohort studies has more than doubled since 2020, from 15 to 32, there have only been three RCTs published since 1999.³⁶⁻³⁸

Overview of studies in the Treatment Aims research topic

The *treatment aims* research topic overlapped almost completely with the *treatment* research topic, as all *treatment* studies had a *treatment aim*. The exceptions were three retrospective/cross-sectional/observational studies capturing patterns related to treatment. They were: a survey about prescription patterns,⁷² a study exploring patterns of treatment amongst a programme for children with tics,⁴⁸ and a study investigating mean time from symptom onset to first immunotherapy.⁴⁵ As the studies were otherwise identical to those in the *treatment* topic, the main demographic characteristics of the studies will not be repeated here.

Treatment aims were usually coded in line with the type of treatment evaluated. For example, antibiotics and tonsillectomy were coded as ‘targeting infection’, IVIg was coded as ‘modulating the immune system’ and anti-inflammatories were coded as ‘targeting inflammation’. *Symptom management* was usually implied, if not stated, and was coded in 34% (140/416) of studies. Aside from symptom management, the most frequently coded treatment aim was *targeting infection* (20%, 85/416; Figure 30). *Flare management* was explicitly targeted in 12% (50/416) of codes, and *managing comorbidities* was coded only 4% (17/416) of the time. *Prophylaxis* was intended in 38 studies (9%, 38/416), and 36 (9%, 36/416) of these studies evaluated antibiotics, including three RCTs.^{34, 36, 38}

Figure 30. Treatment aim codes across 149 treatment studies (symptom management was nearly ubiquitous, so is not shown)

Overview of studies in the Access to services research topic

There were 20 journal articles coded in relation to this research topic. Due to several studies utilising more than one design (e.g. a mixed methods evaluation, or a case study nestled within a larger study), the 20 studies were coded as retrospective/observational/cross-sectional studies 15 times, as prospective cohort studies twice, with one case report, and a further eight qualitative studies. Other than one study published in 2013⁷³ and one in 2015,³⁹ all studies in this research topic were published between 2018 and 2024.

The studies led by Khimani⁵⁷ and LaRusso¹⁵ were based in the USA, but included a multinational survey capturing views from parents based in Asia, Europe, South America and Oceania. Of the remaining studies, two were conducted in Europe,^{66, 74} two in Oceania,^{39, 66} and the rest in North America, and all of these were conducted in the USA. Twelve studies included adult participants, reflecting that parents were often sampled for their perspectives on accessing services; seven of these studies utilised at least some qualitative research methods.^{12, 39, 56, 57, 66, 67, 74}

Across the studies coded to this research topic, access to services was most commonly described in relation to community settings, which accounted for 55% (16/29) of the total setting codes. School or education settings represented the next largest category (21%, 6/29). Hospital-based settings were less commonly reported (10%, 3/29), while primary care, private clinics and research facilities were each infrequently represented (one code each, 3% respectively). One record did not specify a setting (Figure 31).

Figure 31. Distribution of coding for setting of the records within the access to services research topic

Across the entire EGM, a total of nine studies were coded to education settings, of which six focused specifically on access to services;^{47,54,57,66,67,75} there was also a considerable overlap with experience-focused research topics.^{47,66,67,75}

Overview of studies in the Experiences research topic

The Experiences research topic was comprised of a total of 48 unique records, 47 of which were from journal articles and one which was abstract only.⁷⁶ Due to some studies utilising more than one study design, (e.g. mixed-methods evaluation or case report within larger a observational study), the 48 studies were coded as retrospective/observational/cross-sectional study designs 32 times (58%, 32/55), prospective studies four times (7%, 4/55), qualitative studies 18 times (18/55, 33%) and case reports codes just once (2%, 1/55).

Records in this research topic were coded into five possible sub-categories depending on which experiences were captured in the evidence: *clinician/health or social care professional*, *educational professional*, *patient*, *parent/carer* or *sibling*. The distribution of coding across these five sub-categories is shown in Figure 32.

Figure 32. Coding frequency across the five sub-categories of the experiences research topic

Just under half of the records (23/48, 48%) were coded across more than one sub-category and most commonly this was evidence that captured patient and parent/carer experiences (15/23, 65%). There were five studies that collected patient, parent and sibling experiences,^{39, 47, 77-80} one that reported experiences of educational professionals, patients and parents,⁶⁷ and one study that focused on experiences of clinician/health or social care professionals, patients and parents.⁵⁷ Looking at each sub-category individually, most records were coded as *parent/carer* experiences 46% (37/80) or *patient* 38% (30/80). Only one record incorporated *educational professional* experiences, and these were the experiences of one art teacher and

paraprofessional in education.⁶⁷ Three records focussed on experiences of clinician/health or social care professionals.^{8, 57, 81} A breakdown of the types of clinicians/health or social care professionals whose experiences were recorded in the three studies of that sub-category is shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33. Number of codes across job roles of the clinician/health or social care professionals whose experiences were coded in the clinician/health or social care sub-category of the experiences research topic

Focusing on the frequency of coding across the five experience sub-categories based on study design, as shown in Figure 34, evidence was mainly from retrospective/observational/cross-sectional (53%, 50/95) and qualitative designs (37%, 35/95) and patient and parent/carer experiences made up 92% (46/50) of the coding of the retrospective/observational/cross-sectional studies and 74% (26/35) of the qualitative studies. It is only amongst the qualitative studies that all five *experience* sub-categories are covered. No systematic reviews about this research topic were identified.

Figure 34. Distribution of coding across experiences sub-categories based on study design

Fifty percent of the records in the experiences section that were coded for condition were about PANS and PANDAS (44/88). Where the records were about a single condition, there was more evidence about PANS (27%, 24/88) than PANDAS (15%, 13/88) but the evidence about PANDAS did cover all five experience sub-categories. PITANDS was coded seven times and there were no records that coded for CANS in this section either. See Figure 35 for a visual representation of these numbers.

Figure 35. Distribution of coding for condition split between the five experiences sub-categories

Looking at population categories, the two age groups more commonly coded were 4-12 and 13-18 years, making up 33% (66/200) and 31% (61/200) of the total respectively (see Figure 36). For this research topic, the 18+ category was the third most frequently coded age group (27%, 54/200). This however isn't a representation of evidence just about adults with PANS or PANDAS as coding of the 18+ age group would have included records with parent and clinician etc. populations. There was a total of 13 records that captured patient experiences and included 18+ populations with PANS or PANDAS.^{14, 60, 66, 75, 82-90} The study by Schon et al, was focused solely on the experiences of young adults ages 19-34 with PANS.⁹⁰

Figure 36. Number of codes per population category across the experiences research topic

Geographically the coding frequency in the *experiences* research topic mirrored that of other topics in that North America was the dominant region with 61% (66/108) of the total number codes across all sub-categories. The next most coded regions were Europe with 20% (22/108) and Oceania with 10% (11/108). Asia and South America each only made up 4% of the total and there was no evidence from Africa, Caribbean or Central America. In each region where evidence was available, the experiences captured the most were parent/carer. The USA was the country where the majority of evidence came from accounting for almost half of all coding in experiences (34%, 64/190) and all five sub-categories were captured in this evidence. Canada and Sweden were the next most frequently coded countries but substantially lower than the USA with 9% (18/190) and 7% (13/190) respectively. Only three studies (representing 6% of total number of records in this research topic) were UK based or included patients from the UK and the sub-

categories covered in these studies were clinician/health or social care professionals, patients and parents/carer experiences.^{57, 60, 66}

Evidence on experiences related to PANS and PANDAS was first published in 2013, this was a USA based online survey about parent/carer experiences related to daily functioning challenges of their children with PANS and input from occupational therapy services.⁷³ By the end of 2019, there were a further 28 records published on experiences related to PANS or PANDAS and all five sub-categories were captured. In the period of 2020-2024 this number rose further to 45 records. The distribution of coding per five-year period across the five experience sub-categories is shown in Figure 37. Patient and parent/carer have been the two most represented areas of experience over the past 10 years. More evidence about siblings' experiences were published between 2015-2019 compared to 2020-2024, however in the five years between 2020-2024 more evidence focused on clinician/health or social care professional experiences has been published compared to the previous five years. These differences however do just amount to an additional one or two records being published as number of records published generally in this research topic are low.

Figure 37. Distribution of coding across the years of publication broken down by experience research topic sub-sections

When looking at which settings were coded for the records within the *experiences* research topic (see Figure 38) the majority were community based (46%, 55/120), half as many were coded as hospital (23%, 27/120) and 16% coded for school/education (19/120).

Figure 38. Distribution of coding for setting of the records within the experiences research topic

The topic of support (*challenging behaviour, educational, financial or parental*), which was coded as a filter in the map, was coded 101 times within the records in the *experiences* research topic. The support category that was coded the most was *educational support* amounting to 41% (22/53) of the total number of records coded and *parental support* was the next largest represented category with 28% (15/53) (Figure 39).

Figure 39. Distribution of coding of support sub-categories within the research topic of experiences (numbers=percentage studies in this category)

Records that were coded in the *experiences* research topic that reported experiences related to treatments for PANS or PANDAS had these treatments coded as filters (but were not coded in the *treatments* research topics as there was no quantitative measure of effectiveness – see *treatment* research topic section above). Treatments were coded as filters 275 times in total within the records that were coded to the *experiences* research topic, 155 of these related to the treatment filter *classes of drugs* and 120 to the treatment filter *treatments (other)*. A breakdown of this coding across the five sub-categories within the *experiences* research topic are shown below in Figure 40 and Figure 41. *Clinician/health or social care experiences* were the sub-category with the fewest codes (5%, 12/275) across both treatment filters (other than *educational professionals* which were not coded at all for treatments), and *patient/carer* was the sub-category with the most codes (50%, 138/275). The three most coded treatments in the *treatment ‘other’* filter of the *experiences* records (and which also covered all *experience* sub-categories apart from educational professional) were *behavioural and psychological interventions* (20%, 24/120) followed by *TPE/plasmapheresis* (16%, 19/120) and thirdly *dietary modifications* (14%, 17/120). For the treatment – classes of drugs filter, the three most coded drugs of the *experiences* records were *immunoglobulins* (17%, 27/155), *antibiotics* (16%, 25/155) and *anti-inflammatories* (13%, 20/155).

Figure 40. Distribution of coding of treatment ‘other’ filter across sub-categories of the experiences research topic. Treatments captured box included: iron supplements, herbal medicine, ‘wait it out’/tincture of time, and occupational therapy, stem cell transplant

Figure 41. Distribution of coding of 'treatments-classes of drugs' as a filter within the experiences research topic, broken down by sub-categories. Classes of drugs coded in 'other' included: dopaminergic, melatonin, hormonal treatment, mofetil, methotrexate

Overview of Conference Abstracts

There were 107 conference abstracts included in the EGM that were not superseded by subsequent full publications. In total, five abstracts (5%, 5/107) were published from 1995 to 2009, before a sharp rise saw 25 (23%, 25/107) and 38 (36%, 38/107) in the next two five-year periods. Since 2020 a further 39 abstracts (36%, 39/107) have been published. Six abstracts (6%, 6/107) reported on prospective cohort studies, there was one qualitative study (1%, 1/107), and the remaining abstracts were either presenting on retrospective/observational/cross-sectional studies (61%, 65/107) or case studies/reports (34%, 36/107). There were no abstracts reporting on RCTs or systematic reviews. Forty per cent (48/119) of the evidence came from North America, with 36% (44/119) from Europe and 20% (24/119) from Asia, broadly reflecting the distribution seen for other evidence types. There were nine conference abstracts from authors based in the UK.

While the *symptoms* research topic was one of the foci of 66 abstracts, there was an equitable spread between *diagnosis* (coded in 56 abstracts), *aetiology/pathophysiology* (n=48) and *treatment* (n=49). *Epidemiology* was coded in 22 abstracts, and *access to services* and *experiences* were coded once and twice, respectively. The distribution of study designs across research topics is shown in Figure 42. Case studies/series tended to focus on treatment, diagnosis and symptoms, while epidemiological and aetiological investigations primarily used retrospective/cross-sectional/observational designs.

Figure 42. For conference abstracts, the number of study designs coded per research topic. Quali-qualitative evidence; Case-Case studies/series; Retro-Retrospective/observational/cross-sectional studies; Prospective-Prospective cohort studies

Within the 39 most recent conference abstracts (presented since 2020), 16 were coded as *Treatment* studies. However, this included three retrospective analyses of treatment patterns or outcomes,⁹¹⁻⁹³ and 13 case studies/series of varying focus. The one prospective cohort study presented in the last five years involved digital monitoring of symptoms to track the course of PANS/PANDAS.⁹⁴

Ongoing studies.

Four ongoing studies on PANS/PANDAS were identified through searching of the Clinical Trials Registry. Where possible authors were contacted for an update. None of these studies had any linked publications or conference abstracts, and so were not included in the map, but are highlighted here to show what may be published in the future:

- RCT (transcranial direct current stimulation vs risperidone) for children 6-11 years with autism spectrum disorder with rare diseases, genetic problems or PANDAS. Recruitment ended 2025. No further updates. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06368726>
- Prospective cohort - Paediatric Epidemiological Data and Incidence (PEDI) PANDAS study. Incidence and natural history of PANS (PANDAS patients included). Currently recruiting (estimated completion 2027). <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06811935>
- Prospective, single arm study. IVIG in patient with PANS, ages 4-17 years. Currently recruiting (estimated completion end of 2026) <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT04609761#publications>
- Cross-sectional study. Economic Impact Study of IVIG treatment for PANS (part of Unhide project). Currently recruiting. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06811935>

Guidelines

Guidelines were not included as evidence within the map as the focus for the map was on empirical studies. It is however important to highlight that whilst UK clinical guidelines on PANS/PANDAS are currently in development²⁰ there are two sets of internationally peer reviewed guidelines that have been published which include clinical management and treatment.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ The first is made up of three parts on the clinical management of PANS covering: I - psychiatric and behavioural interventions,¹⁹ II – use of immunomodulating therapies,¹⁷ and III – treatment and prevention of infection.¹⁶ The second and most recent guidelines were produced by a Nordic-UK working group and cover clinical guidance on the diagnosis and management of patients with suspected PANS in Nordic countries.¹⁸

Impact of Public and Patient Involvement and Engagement

Table 1 provides a detailed description of PPIE activities and their impact on the project. We describe seven distinct activities with either parents of people with PANS/PANDAS, or young people with the condition. The activities took place at all stages of the project and influenced our understanding of PANS/PANDAS, the development of the protocol, the coding framework of the EGM, and our interpretation of the evidence.

Table 1. Description of PPIE activities, the key points from each activity, and the impact of each activity on the project

Activity, date, method, PPIE involved	Key messages	Impact on project
Initial meeting – listening exercise, 01.08.25, online meeting (1 hour), parent PPIE group (n=5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Symptoms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ extensive and varied between children and with each flare ○ do not always fit diagnostic criteria ● Access <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ difficulties accessing care and treatment for children ○ even more difficult as adults ○ what happens transfer out of paediatric services ● Diagnosis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ widespread lack of awareness/expertise within NHS – not listened to by doctors ○ not seen as part of multidisciplinary team – bounced around from clinician to clinician ○ no UK guidelines on diagnosis/treatment ○ no option other than to seek a diagnosis and treatment privately, sometimes abroad. Financial implications of this ○ misdiagnoses ● Mistrust <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ parents subjected to accusations of fabrication or mistreatment ○ parents not trusted to report on their children’s conditions 	The first meeting with parents was solely a listening exercise and a space for parents to share their experiences and expertise with us as researchers. This gave us valuable insight into the challenges, struggles and battles families have faced (and continue to face), often spanning several years throughout the course of their child’s/children’s condition. This meeting was highly impactful and informative on an emotional level and on providing understanding of the conditions and the complexities associated with them from the parent’s perspective.

Activity, date, method, PPIE involved	Key messages	Impact on project
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Treatment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ families had to work out for themselves what was needed and when, when flares were likely (annual cycle) and how to manage these ○ use of prophylactic medications to limit impact of flares ○ often sent down route of Child and Adolescent Mental Health Services (CAMHS) due to symptoms, but these health professionals then are not looking for inflammation or infection as cause and antibiotics as a treatment option ○ need to support the gut when on longer term anti-biotics ○ importance of treatments ‘beyond medicine’ e.g. acupuncture, homeopathy, music ○ an individualised approach to treatment is needed ● Devastating impact on whole family 	
<p>Meeting to discuss framework ideas for the EGM, 28.08.25 and 29.08.25 online meeting (1 hour), parent PPIE group (28.08.25 n=3, 29.08.25 n=5)</p>	<p>These meetings gave any parents new to the group a chance to share experiences and also to introduce the project and the concept of the EGM. We asked parents for their thoughts on what the structure of the map should include, in particular what research topics (columns in the map) were important and what they would want to find out from the map.</p> <p>Key messages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strong interest in searching the map based on symptoms and treatments ● Need for there to be better understanding of triggers, risk factors, environmental factors, genetics etc. ● Need to capture adults with PANS PANDAS and children diagnosed as children but now adults ● Who are seeing PANS PANDAS children, which health professionals, what are the care pathways 	<p>As a result of the discussions in these meetings, the following were incorporated into the map:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research topics on access to services and experiences ● Sub-categories within the research topic of epidemiology to identify evidence about onset and about flares ● Research topic aetiology/pathophysiology ● 18+ added as a population age category – to capture adults with PANS PANDAS and/or children diagnosed as children but are now adults ● Filters for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ symptoms – members contributed to which symptoms should be listed and the

Activity, date, method, PPIE involved	Key messages	Impact on project
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the links between flare ups and triggers and specific symptoms and triggers • What evidence is there on support; educational, physical (how to manage challenging behaviours), parental • What about underserved communities who are unable to access private healthcare? 	<p>importance of including the lesser well-known symptoms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ treatments – members contributed to which treatments should be listed in the filters and the treatments research topic ○ support (educational, parental, physical, financial) ○ health professionals involved ○ health equity ○ setting
<p>Feedback on draft protocol, September 2025, email, parent PPIE (n=3)</p>	<p>Parents were given the opportunity to review the draft protocol and provide feedback.</p> <p>There were suggestions made for alternative terms to PANS/PANDAS to consider e.g. Infection Triggered autoimmune brain inflammation, autoimmune basal ganglia encephalitis (these were checked with clinical interest holders and reasons for not including provided)</p> <p>It was highlighted how the diagnostic criteria used in literature and medical communities does not capture all symptoms they have experienced.</p> <p>Parents provided additional symptoms and treatments to add to the protocol and the map</p>	<p>The following changes were incorporated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes to wording in the background • Symptoms added to filters: fatigue, PDA, impulsiveness, emotional highs and lows, facial grimace • Mast cell stabilisers added as a treatment option inf research topic and filters • Additional treatment aims added – modulating the immune system, symptom management
<p>Feedback on draft plain language summary, September 2025, email, parent PPIE and PERSPEX</p>	<p>PERSPEX and parent PPIE members were given the opportunity to review and feedback on the draft plain language summary of the protocol.</p> <p>Feedback suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More detail in the background • Use of simpler language throughout • Better explanation of what an EGM is 	<p>Feedback was incorporated into a revised version of the document.</p>

Activity, date, method, PPIE involved	Key messages	Impact on project
<p>Initial meeting with youth members, 26.11.25, online meeting, youth group PPIE (n=4)</p>	<p>Lived experiences of PANS/PANDAS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loneliness and isolation • Invisible symptoms: Symptoms that cannot be seen often lead to misunderstanding or dismissal • Fluctuating and varied presentation: Symptoms differ widely across gender and age groups, contributing to misdiagnosis and inconsistent responses <p>Experiences with diagnosis and healthcare</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short consultations and lack of clinical curiosity • Feeling dismissed or disbelieved, despite persistent symptoms • Dismissal based on normal clinical picture • Symptoms misdiagnosed as anxiety, PTSD, or behavioural • Abrupt loss of care when transitioning from paediatric to adult services • Access to care was often only possible privately, creating inequity <p>Young people wanted professionals to know that they needed more time during appointments, and better treatment responses during flare-ups. They wanted more trust in patient and parent symptom reporting and for there to be a holistic approach to care, not solely based on visible presentation. They also highlighted a strong desire for autonomy and normalcy.</p> <p>Flare days were described in detail highlighting the severity and varied symptoms that can present between youth members and between flares for each youth member.</p> <p>It was highlighted how much the condition impacted on everyday life and on all the relationships they have with those around them.</p>	<p>This meeting enriched our understanding of PANS/PANDAS. The experiences and words shared by these young people, and the sheer weight of them, covering the severity of their symptoms, the impact of these on their everyday lives, their childhoods, and the challenges that they have experienced in accessing healthcare, provided insight that was invaluable and essential to broaden understanding of the condition, the complexities involved and to help understand from those with firsthand experience, what change was needed.</p> <p>The experiences shared made us consider our thinking, for example that impact of separation anxiety on relationships other than just parental.</p>

Activity, date, method, PPIE involved	Key messages	Impact on project
<p>EGM demonstration, 03.12.25, online, youth members (n=5)</p>	<p>EGM presentation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider a simpler format, more accessible colours/better contrasting colours for bubbles • In the ‘About the map’ information, add study design descriptions and highlight key points of the instructions so a younger audience can get straight into searching the map • Add some background colour to the map • Make the search bar more obvious • Options to personalise the font size and colours of the map for the user • Optimise map format for phone use • Quick overview or key facts from data/studies <p>Main thoughts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PANS/PANDAS has been around longer than expected • More evidence than expected from UK • What is the impact of delayed diagnosis/treatment increase likelihood of seizure activity. Especially as seizures aren't part of the diagnostic criteria but seem a relatively common symptom? • Would like PANS/PANDAS to be better seen as something affecting people into adulthood. Currently no doctors who will see adult cases of PANS/PANDAS • Considered by lots of doctors that PANS/PANDAS is a just a psychiatric condition and do not see/consider the physical side. • Interested to find out if evidence about links between Lyme disease and PANS exists in the map • Evidence related to misdiagnoses. Important to know what misdiagnoses people are given before being diagnosed with PANS/PANDAS 	<p>Colours of the bubbles (study designs) in the map selected based on advice from youth group. A revised version of the map with these different colours was shared with the youth group. Some gentle colour was added to the map as requested where possible.</p> <p>Options for a simpler version of the map are being explored outside of the Eppi format.</p> <p>A description of study designs was included in the ‘About this map’ summary in the EGM. Instructions for how to use and search in the map were moved so that they feature as one of the first sections to read in the text and key points were highlighted in bold including how to use the search bar. The instructional video was recorded to include a short version of instructions for those wanting a quick overview followed by a longer explanation and demonstration. A link to more information about the project and an overview of the findings added to ‘About the map’.</p> <p>Areas that the youth members highlighted as being important (e.g. access to services) but were potential gaps in the evidence, have been incorporated into the report write-up and discussion.</p>

Activity, date, method, PPIE involved	Key messages	Impact on project
EGM demonstration and feedback, 12.12.25, online, parent PPIE (n=6)	<p>Parents had been given the map the week before the meeting to allow for time to access it and exploring, along with an accompanying video with instructions.</p> <p>Feedback was asked for on the map, the ‘about the map’ summary and the video instructions.</p> <p>Key points made:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parents were keen to know when the map would be available for sharing • Help with navigating the map was needed • Details were asked about how the coding was completed was and a potential miscoding was highlighted • Parents reported that there was less evidence than they thought there would be showing how little is known about PANS PANDAS. • Lack of biomarkers making clear and accurate diagnosis difficult and where more research needs to be focused. Need to understand causes better to then be able to treat more effectively • Endpoint for parents would be production of clinical guidelines, the creation of a pathway to quicker, accurate diagnosis and quicker, effective treatment 	<p>Mis-coded record was identified and correctly coded.</p> <p>Consideration for additional support documents to be written to help navigate the map.</p> <p>Parental views echoed our interpretation of findings within the EGM, and in particular where more evidence needs to be focused in order for changes in practice to be made.</p>
EGM report shared via email for feedback with parent PPIE group 19.12.25	<p>The first draft of the report was shared with the parent PPIE group for comments along with an invitation to write a foreword.</p> <p>Feedback from one parent:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider re-wording of sentence in the background where the term controversial is used • Suggestion to add examples of well recognised autoimmune or immune-mediated disorders (e.g. psoriatic arthritis) that are primarily diagnosed clinically/diagnosis of exclusion for broader clinical context 	<p>Two parents provided a foreword and these were added to the report.</p> <p>Sentence in the background re-worded and the word controversial removed.</p> <p>Sentence added to the background to highlight that other neuropsychiatric conditions are primarily diagnosed clinically/diagnosis of exclusion.</p>

Discussion

This is the first attempt to comprehensively collate all empirical evidence about PANS/PANDAS. We used rigorous and comprehensive methods to identify relevant evidence, which we collated and displayed in an interactive EGM. Throughout, we collaborated with interest holders, including parents of children with PANS/PANDAS and young people with the condition, which informed key processes during the review process and helped define the final EGM. Despite controversy over the existence of the conditions, we found 445 pieces of empirical research spanning 30 years, all of which involved people with a diagnosis of PANS or PANDAS. Evidence was categorised by research topic, covering Diagnosis, Epidemiology, Aetiology and pathophysiology, Symptoms, Treatment (and Treatment aims), Access to services and Experiences. The EGM served to highlight several crucial points about evidence in the field.

Main findings

There has been a rapid increase in the rate of evidence production relating to PANS/PANDAS since 2015, including forays into experiential research, including the production of qualitative evidence about experiences of the condition. Despite this, the evidence base is still dominated by case-based and retrospective or cross-sectional studies. There have been only five published RCTs, and none since 2017. We identified just five systematic reviews meeting the basic criteria for rigour outlined by Krnic Martinic and colleagues,³¹ which may be a symptom of, or a contributor to, the lack of consensus about all aspects of PANS/PANDAS.

Diagnosis

Parents and children in our PPIE groups revealed distressing experiences of diagnosis, but this section of the map was dominated by case reports/series, offering limited evidence to support advancements in diagnostic accuracy. There were a handful of prospective cohort studies, and two qualitative studies that looked at experiences of clinicians, parents/caregivers or patients, which may be the most valuable sources of evidence. Efforts to produce and validate screening tools were seen in a small number of studies. However, the findings of the EGM suggest there is limited evidence to develop an understanding of how families and patients navigate the diagnostic process and the challenges they face.

Most diagnosis studies were set in hospitals (69%), while primary care (1%) and schools were rarely represented (2%). The nature of PANS/PANDAS, and the severity of symptoms, may mean

families are more likely to seek emergency care, but our data suggest that primary care is almost never involved in diagnosis. Education is a key setting for young people, but only nine studies across the entire EGM included evidence from educational settings.

Numerous professionals were involved in diagnosis studies, including psychiatrists, neurologists, paediatricians, immunologists, rheumatologists, infectious disease physicians, radiologists, CAMHS teams, psychologists, and alternative medicine practitioners. This reflects one of the challenges around diagnosis, whereby patient presentation is unclear and, typically, patients end up seeing a variety of specialists. Additionally, the appearance of holistic, functional medicine, naturopathic, and alternative medical providers in the map reflects the experiences of parents and patients in our PPIE group, who have turned to a wide range of sources, including those outside mainstream healthcare, in an attempt to receive diagnostic clarity.

Aetiology and pathophysiology

There has been a steep rise in production of evidence about the aetiology and pathophysiology of PANS/PANDAS since 2020, however almost twice as many studies focused on PANDAS rather than PANS. In general, across the EGM, there was more research on PANDAS than PANS, perhaps because the term PANDAS is 14 years older than PANS, or perhaps because the association with a GAS is a relatively tractable form of enquiry. Without a clear understanding of the aetiology and pathophysiology of PANS/PANDAS, all other forms of enquiry are hampered. The increased rate of evidence production is therefore reassuring, but further high-quality primary research, and targeted evidence synthesis will be required to advance knowledge.

Epidemiology

Epidemiological evidence should complement endeavours to understand the aetiology and pathophysiology of the conditions. As expected, nearly three quarters of the epidemiological evidence was from retrospective/observational/cross-sectional studies, with two relevant systematic reviews, although these were only coded for patterns for onset. Evidence was largely focussed on patterns of flares or condition onset, rather than prevalence. Where there was evidence about prevalence, it was more often related to prevalence and incidence of onset, rather than prevalence and incidence of flares/relapse. In 2025, there has been more focus on prevalence and incidence of flares, with the number of records in this section already amounting to half of that seen in the preceding five years. Commensurate with the overarching trends in the map, evidence for epidemiology largely focuses on childhood and adolescence, and only four of 71 studies were from the UK, these focusing only on patterns for flares or relapses.

Symptoms

Evidence about symptoms came from 200 records, and the majority of these records focused on emotional, behavioural psychiatric symptoms or physical symptoms, rather than impact on functioning or flares. Evidence was skewed towards case reports and series, with a lack of prospective data. The same top four symptoms (*Obsessive compulsive behaviour/ritualistic behaviour; Tics; Anxiety; Irritability, anger, aggression*) were seen for all symptom sub-categories, including *flares and impact on functioning*, apart from *Sleep difficulties*, which was the third most frequently reported in the latter category. The distribution of evidence suggests that the immediate presenting features, that is, the dominant physical and emotional/psychological/behavioural symptoms, received the greatest attention, while impacts on broader function and targeting flares, which are a major concern to those living with this condition, were not prioritised. With that said, it was observed that coding of flares increased with patient age.

Treatment

Treatment studies have emerged at an increasing rate, alongside all other forms of evidence in the EGM. However, the quality of evidence has not. RCTs are the gold standard approach for determining treatment effectiveness, but a limited population size, and the ethical dilemma of whether to randomise patients with PANS/PANDAS, may explain why they are uncommon in this field. Nevertheless, even prospective cohort studies, which may be more ethically acceptable, are scant in the EGM, only 11% of the evidence about treatments coming from studies using this design. Despite the absence of convincing evidence about treatments specific to patients with PANS/PANDAs, there were 104 case studies/series reporting treatment effects.

Lack of consensus about the aetiology and pathophysiology of PANS/PANDAS means that treatment protocols have yet to be developed, and the observed approaches to treatment frequently attempted to target the underlying infection, boost the immune system, or directly address symptoms. This was usually borne out in the case evidence, where antibiotics, IVIg, TPE/plasmapheresis and psychiatric medications respectively, were most often prescribed – despite direct evidence of efficacy in PANS/PANDAS. In the absence of condition-specific evidence, there is still a need to treat patients, therefore the approach of targeting the underlying infection with antibiotics, for example, is understandable.

Studies examining IVIg provided the most evidence outside of case series/reports, however this treatment is not widely available.^{21,86} Antibiotics were widely evaluated, but only 4% of studies

used RCT or prospective designs. With emotional/behavioural/psychiatric symptoms being widespread, we note that there were 39 behavioural and psychological interventions, including four prospective studies, and 64 evaluations of psychiatric medication, none of which utilised a prospective design.

Experiences and access to services

The last 12 years has seen the emergence of evidence about the experiences that patients, parents, carers and healthcare professionals have had of PANS/PANDAS. We identified 18 studies using qualitative research methods to elicit experience data, out of a total of 48 records about experiences. Three studies captured data from the UK, otherwise evidence was primarily from the USA, and reported on parent or child experiences. There were several studies capturing experiences about treatments; the most coded non-pharmacological treatment was *behavioural and psychological interventions*, and most coded pharmacological treatment was *immunoglobulin*. Despite the availability of primary evidence, particularly a number of qualitative studies using interview and focus group methods, there was no qualitative evidence synthesis.

Closely linked with experiences, as well as diagnosis and treatment, and driven in part by our PPIE groups, we coded any studies that mentioned issues with access to services. Despite this being a major issue for patients and families, it was only mentioned in 20 studies.

Comparison to previous systematic reviews

While this is the first mapping exercise to be conducted in the field, we identified five systematic reviews. There were no reviews or syntheses of qualitative evidence, which represents a gap in the research, given that we identified 18 primary studies using qualitative research methods. There were no systematic reviews covering the topics of diagnosis, or access to services, though detailed examination of the studies coded under *experiences* may yield relevant evidence for the latter. While two reviews were coded in relation to *aetiology/pathophysiology* and *symptoms*, one was concerned with a specific focus on cerebrospinal fluid findings,⁴² and the other conducted searches in 2017⁴¹ and so warrants updating.

The three treatment-focused reviews were either out of date due to the date of their searches,^{25, 40} or had a narrow focus,²⁴ meaning that a review of treatment effectiveness in PANS/PANDAS could be warranted if sufficient new evidence has emerged. Our EGM shows that, while no new RCTs have been published since 2017 there were nine prospective cohort studies and 15 retrospective/cross-sectional/observational studies published in the same period, which could

help to strengthen the evidence base for treatment. For example, we identified nine new studies about IVIg since the review by Sigra and colleagues,²⁵ which included three prospective cohort studies. There were also new studies about antibiotics and CBT that warrant review.

Implications

By establishing the state of the evidence in PANS/PANDAS with this EGM, we were able to identify a scattered evidence base where clear priorities must be established for future research in order to advance the field. All of the research topics we describe feed into one another to an extent, but without better understanding of the aetiology and pathophysiology of PANS/PANDAS, many of the allied endeavours to manage the conditions cannot progress. Effective treatments cannot be designed without knowledge of underlying mechanisms, and diagnosis will continue to be challenging without better evidence. This evidence should include analyses of critical periods for developing PANS/PANDAS, the complex interplay of individual, environmental and pathogen factors that place children at greater or lower risk for PANS/PANDAS, and clearer assessments of health equity factors relevant to development of PANS/PANDAS. A clearer disease model for PANS/PANDAS will provide a clearer basis for developing treatment targets for evaluation.

While treatment research will be hampered until aetiology is better understood, existing and future patients need treatment, and so an updated systematic review of the existing evidence is warranted. Treatments such as antibiotics, CBT, and psychiatric medications, with proven efficacy in other populations, should be evaluated with more rigorous, prospective study designs. There is sufficient primary evidence to produce systematic reviews in several research topics, which would advance understanding in the field and help to direct the conduct of future primary research where it is most beneficial.

By providing a single point of reference for empirical evidence about PANS/PANDAS, this EGM is a valuable resource for individuals wishing to learn more about the conditions. Rather than having to search for evidence themselves, map users can find it in one place, reducing the risk of missing important evidence, or finding unreliable evidence, about an aspect of the conditions. This may be particularly empowering for patients and their families, who may lack the skills or resources to find relevant academic publications on the topic. In turn, this could reduce reliance on social media or other, less reliable sources of information. For clinicians this comprehensive map provides an opportunity to review the evidence base PANS/PANDAS as it stands now, and use the evidence to make informed decisions in the future.

This EGM can benefit organisations such as the PANS Clinical Guideline Development Group,⁹⁵ which seeks to produce a clinical guideline based on existing knowledge and expert consensus. The group aims to enable earlier diagnosis and treatment, address unwarranted variation in practice and improve standards of care whilst knowledge in the field continues to develop, therefore this EGM provides all the relevant evidence to support this activity, in one place.

Limitations

This report was commissioned with a UK focus, however less than 5% of the evidence in the entire EGM contained data from the UK. Although the evidence was international, representing participants from 43 countries, the USA was by far the most productive country, producing around half of the total evidence. This provides important context when attempting to generalise to other countries, particularly the UK. We do however note that there is a desire to encourage and commission further research in the UK, as reflected in the JLA Priority Setting Partnership on Childhood Neurological Conditions,²⁶ which is NIHR-funded, and as part of discussions of the national PANS/PANDAS Steering Group.⁹⁵

We only included evidence where patients were diagnosed with PANS/PANDAS (or related terms). It may have been beneficial to have included evidence for patients with similar conditions, given the emerging nature of the field. This was noted by PPIE participants. However, it could also have added confusion to those accessing the EGM, by including data for patients without a specific diagnosis of PANS/PANDAS.

Certain codes in the map were difficult to record due to poor reporting in studies. We often experienced difficulty establishing study designs, and fields such as healthcare professional and setting were frequently unclear or not reported. Furthermore, later PPIE meetings brought up codes that we might have missed, such as triggers for flares. We also identified some common 'other' symptoms that in hindsight may have warranted their own code, such as gastrointestinal symptoms, 'milkmaid grip' and self-harm.

We acknowledge that there is variation in the language and terminology used between or within different interest holder groups to describe certain aspects of the evidence, such as treatment types or approaches. We chose to be guided by the terminology used by study authors, in conjunction with input from clinical experts (ML, AL), however there is the potential for disagreement over the terminology or categorisation we have used. We would refer evidence

users to our methods section where we openly state any rules and clarifications used during coding.

The limitations of the mapping software meant we were restricted to six study design fields, meaning we had to collapse designs. However, we are confident that single-observation and retrospective studies were validly differentiated from prospective designs, and that case studies and series could legitimately be considered together. In general, the EGM was intended to strike a balance between complexity and simplicity, so could have been lacking in either direction.

It was beyond the scope of this project to evaluate the quality of included studies. In the event, this would have provided minimal added value for the effort required, given that most studies are of inherently low rigour designs.

The colours and presentation of the EGM may not be as accessible as desired for all audiences. We were made aware by our PPIE group that the colours denoting study designs, for example, were not optimal for people with colour-blindness. We have tailored the design of the EGM where possible to account for a broad audience, but acknowledge its limitations.

Conclusion

PANS/PANDAS is a serious condition affecting young people, commonly having a dramatic effect on patients and their families. In an attempt to advance knowledge in the field, and establish priorities for future work, we created an evidence and gap map displaying empirical data about PANS/PANDAS. All empirical studies were eligible, and we used comprehensive search methods, benefiting also from collaboration with a range of interest holders.

Despite identifying 445 pieces of research, the map shows that the field is severely lacking high quality primary evidence. Based on the identified evidence gaps, we make suggestions for future research, highlighting a particular need to establish a disease model for PANS/PANDAS that could inform all other areas of research. With the ongoing need to treat patients with this highly impactful condition, targeted systematic reviews could make use of the increase in publication rate over the last decade and the lack of recent evidence syntheses, to provide further clarity on the existing evidence. Treatments have thus far targeted either the underlying infection, aimed to boost the immune system, or directly addressed symptoms, albeit without compelling evidence in PANS/PANDAS to guide decision-making.

This evidence and gap map is an important stage in the process of advancing knowledge about the causes, diagnosis, treatment and experiences of PANS/PANDAS.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our sincere thanks to the parents and young people who gave their time to support this project. Thank you to Clarise Pattison for organising and facilitating meetings with youth board members. We also thank Kieran Becker for his help with early development of the protocol, and Sue Whiffin and Jenny Lowe for administrative support during this project.

References

1. PANS PANDAS UK. For health professionals 2025 [updated 2025. Available from: <https://panspandasuk.org/support-resources/for-health-professionals/>.
2. Allen AJ, Leonard HL, Swedo SE. Case Study: A New Infection-Triggered, Autoimmune Subtype of Pediatric OCD and Tourette's Syndrome. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*. 1995;34(3):307-11.
3. Swedo SE, Leonard HL, Garvey M, Mittleman B, Allen AJ, Perlmutter S, et al. Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections: Clinical description of the first 50 cases. *American Journal of Psychiatry*. 1998;155(2):264-71.
4. Swedo SE, Leckman JF, Rose NR. From research subgroup to clinical syndrome: modifying the PANDAS criteria to describe PANS (pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome). *Pediatr Therapeut*. 2012;2(2):113.
5. Frankovich J, Thienemann M, Pearlstein J, Crable A, Brown K, Chang K. Multidisciplinary clinic dedicated to treating youth with pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome: Presenting characteristics of the first 47 consecutive patients. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2015;25(1):38-47.
6. Gromark C, Hesselmark E, Djupedal IG, Silverberg M, Horne AC, Harris RA, et al. A Two-to-Five Year Follow-Up of a Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome Cohort. *Child Psychiatry and Human Development*. 2022;53(2):354-64.
7. Prato A, Gulisano M, Scerbo M, Barone R, Vicario CM, Rizzo R. Diagnostic Approach to Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated With Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS): A Narrative Review of Literature Data. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2021;9.
8. Grandinetti R, Mussi N, Pilloni S, Ramundo G, Miniaci A, Turco E, et al. Pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome and pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorder associated with streptococcal infections: a delphi study and consensus document about definition, diagnostic criteria, treatment and follow-up. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 2024;15.
9. Swedo SE, Seidlitz J, Kovacevic M, Latimer ME, Hommer R, Lougee L, et al. Clinical presentation of pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections in research and community settings. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2015;25(1):26-30.
10. La Bella S, Scorrano G, Rinaldi M, Di Ludovico A, Mainieri F, Attanasi M, et al. Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS): Myth or Reality? The State of the Art on a Controversial Disease. *Microorganisms*. 2023;11(10).
11. Bodner SM, Morshed SA, Peterson BS. The question of PANDAS in adults. *Biological Psychiatry*. 2001;49(9):807-10.
12. Dolce JL, LaRusso MD, Abadia-Barrero C. Disruptions and Adaptations in Family Functioning: A Study of Families' Experiences with PANS/PANDAS. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*. 2022;31(3):790-806.
13. Goncalves MVM, Harger R, Braatz V, Parolin LF, Eboni ACB, Fontana MAN, et al. Pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome (PANS) misdiagnosed as autism spectrum disorder. *Immunology Letters*. 2018;203:52-3.

14. Calaprice D, Tona J, Parker-Athill EC, Murphy TK. A Survey of Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome Characteristics and Course. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2017;27(7):607-18.
15. LaRusso MD, Abadía-Barrero C. Developmental Impacts of PANS/PANDAS and Inadequate Support for Children and Families. *Child Psychiatry and Human Development*. 2024.
16. Cooperstock MS, Swedo SE, Pasternack MS, Murphy TK. Clinical management of pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome: Part III—Treatment and prevention of infections. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2017;27(7):594-606.
17. Frankovich J, Swedo S, Murphy T, Dale RC, Agalliu D, Williams K, et al. Clinical management of pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome: Part II—use of immunomodulatory therapies. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2017;27(7):574-93.
18. Pfeiffer HCV, Wickstrom R, Skov L, Sørensen CB, Sandvig I, Gjone IH, et al. Clinical guidance for diagnosis and management of suspected Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome in the Nordic countries. *Acta Paediatrica, International Journal of Paediatrics*. 2021;110(12):3153-60.
19. Thienemann M, Murphy T, Leckman J, Shaw R, Williams K, Kappahn C, et al. Clinical Management of Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome: Part i - Psychiatric and Behavioral Interventions. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2017;27(7):566-73.
20. PANS PANDAS UK. Latest UK Guideline News 2026 [Available from: <https://panspandasuk.org/post/latest-uk-guideline-news/>].
21. Tang AW, Appel HJ, Bennett SC, Forsyth LH, Glasser SK, Jarka MA, et al. Treatment barriers in PANS/PANDAS: Observations from eleven health care provider families. *Families, Systems, & Health*. 2021;39(3):477-87.
22. Cocuzza S, Maniaci A, La Mantia I, Nocera F, Caruso D, Caruso S, et al. Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder in PANS/PANDAS in Children: In Search of a Qualified Treatment—A Systematic Review and Metanalysis. *Children*. 2022;9(2).
23. Farhood Z, Ong AA, Discolo CM. PANDAS: A systematic review of treatment options. *International Journal of Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology*. 2016;89:149-53.
24. Johnson M, Ehlers S, Fernell E, Hajjari P, Wartenberg C, Wallerstedt SM. Anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and immunomodulatory treatment in children with symptoms corresponding to the research condition PANS (Pediatric Acuteonset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome): A systematic review. *PLoS ONE*. 2021;16(7 July).
25. Sigra S, Hesselmark E, Bejerot S. Treatment of PANDAS and PANS: a systematic review. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*. 2018;86:51-65.
26. James Lind Alliance. Childhood Neurological Conditions 2024 [Available from: <https://www.jla.nihr.ac.uk/priority-setting-partnerships/childhood-neurological-conditions#tab-top-10-priorities>].
27. Shaw E NM, Spicer S, Lawal H, Briscoe S, Melendez-Torres G, et al. What multi-disciplinary delivery models for Occupational Health services are effective for whom? An umbrella review. [Internet]: University of Exeter; 2022.
28. Orr N, Rogers M, Stein A, Thompson Coon J, Stein K. Reviewing the Evidence Base for Topical Steroid Withdrawal Syndrome in the Research Literature and Social Media Platforms: An Evidence Gap Map. *J Med Internet Res*. 2024;26:e57687.

29. White H, Albers B, Gaarder M, Kornør H, Littell J, Marshall Z, et al. Guidance for producing a Campbell evidence and gap map. *Campbell systematic reviews*. 2020;16(4):e1125.
30. Singer HS, Gilbert DL, Wolf DS, Mink JW, Kurlan R. Moving from PANDAS to CANS. *Journal of Pediatrics*. 2012;160(5):725-31.
31. Krnic Martinic M, Pieper D, Glatt A, Puljak L. Definition of a systematic review used in overviews of systematic reviews, meta-epidemiological studies and textbooks. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*. 2019;19(1):203.
32. Zych K, Burdan O, Ziomek WN, Białek AB, Wróbel J, Cieślik-Porębska M, et al. Current knowledge of PANDAS and PANS syndromes in paediatric patients-etiology, diagnosis and therapies. *Journal of Pre-Clinical & Clinical Research*. 2024;18(4).
33. Thomas J, Graziosi, S., Brunton, J., Ghouze, Z., O'Driscoll, P., & Bond, M. & Koryakina, A. EPPI-Reviewer: advanced software for systematic reviews, maps and evidence synthesis.2023. Available from: <https://eppi.ioe.ac.uk/cms/About/AboutEPPIReviewer/tabid/2967/Default.aspx>.
34. Garvey MA, Perlmutter SJ, Allen AJ, Hamburger S, Lougee L, Leonard HL, et al. A pilot study of penicillin prophylaxis for neuropsychiatric exacerbations triggered by streptococcal infections. *Biological Psychiatry*. 1999;45(12):1564

EP - 71.

35. Perlmutter SJ, Leitman SF, Garvey MA, Hamburger S, Feldman E, Leonard HL, et al. Therapeutic plasma exchange and intravenous immunoglobulin for obsessive-compulsive disorder and tic disorders in childhood. *Lancet*. 1999;354(9185).
36. Snider LA, Lougee L, Slattery M, Grant P, Swedo SE. Antibiotic prophylaxis with azithromycin or penicillin for childhood-onset neuropsychiatric disorders. *Biological Psychiatry*. 2005;57(7):788-92.
37. Williams KA, Swedo SE, Farmer CA, Grantz H, Grant PJ, D'Souza P, et al. Randomized, controlled trial of intravenous immunoglobulin for pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*. 2016;55(10):860-7.
38. Murphy TK, Brennan EM, Johnco C, Parker-Athill EC, Miladinovic B, Storch EA, et al. A Double-Blind Randomized Placebo-Controlled Pilot Study of Azithromycin in Youth with Acute-Onset Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2017;27(7):640-51.
39. McClelland M, Crombez M-M, Crombez C, Wenz C, Lisius M, Mattia A, et al. Implications for advanced practice nurses when pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections (PANDAS) is suspected: A qualitative study. *Journal of Pediatric Health Care*. 2015;29(5).
40. Hollis C, Pennant M, Cuenca J, Glazebrook C, Kendall T, Whittington C, et al. Clinical effectiveness and patient perspectives of different treatment strategies for tics in children and adolescents with tourette syndrome: A systematic review and qualitative analysis. *Health Technology Assessment*. 2016;20(4):1-289.
41. Nielsen M, Kohler-Forsberg O, Hjorthoj C, Benros ME, Nordentoft M, Orlovska-Waast S. Streptococcal infections and exacerbations in pandas: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal*. 2019;38(2).
42. Pankratz B, Feige B, Runge K, Bechter K, Schiele MA, Domschke K, et al. Cerebrospinal fluid findings in patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder, Tourette syndrome, and PANDAS: A systematic literature review. *Brain, Behavior, & Immunity*. 2024;115:319-32.

43. Brown K, Farmer C, Farhadian B, Hernandez J, Thienemann M, Frankovich J. Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome Response to Oral Corticosteroid Bursts: An Observational Study of Patients in an Academic Community-Based PANS Clinic. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2017;27(7):629-39.
44. Doran PR, O'Hanlon E. How Parents of Students with PANDAS or PANS Perceive the Educational Process. *Journal of the American Academy of Special Education Professionals*. 2019.
45. Gao J, Chan A, Willett T, Farhadian B, Silverman M, Tran P, et al. Sex and Aggression Characteristics in a Cohort of Patients with Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2022;32(8):444-52.
46. Harris EC, Conelea CA, Shyne MT, Bernstein GA. Predictors and Prospective Course of PANS: A Pilot Study Using Electronic Platforms for Data Collection. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2021;31(2):102-8.
47. Dolce JL, LaRusso, Maria, Lombardi, Caitlin, Mauldin, et al. *New Childhood Chronic Illness: Pans/Pandas and the Impact on Family Functioning: University of Connecticut; 2020.*
48. Gabbay V, Coffey BJ, Babb JS, Meyer L, Wachtel C, Anam S, et al. Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcus: comparison of diagnosis and treatment in the community and at a specialty clinic. *Pediatrics*. 2008;122(2):273-8.
49. Kalinowski A, Tian L, Pattni R, Ollila H, Khan M, Manko C, et al. Evaluation of C4 Gene Copy Number in Pediatric Acute Neuropsychiatric Syndrome. *Developmental Neuroscience*. 2023;45(6):315-24.
50. Cengel-Kultur SE, Cop E, Kara A, Cengiz AB, Uludag AK, Unal F. The relationship between group A beta hemolytic streptococcal infection and psychiatric symptoms: a pilot study. *Turkish Journal of Pediatrics*. 2009;51(4):317-24.
51. Gamucci A, Uccella S, Sciarretta L, D'Apruzzo M, Calevo MG, Mancardi MM, et al. PANDAS and PANS: Clinical, Neuropsychological, and Biological Characterization of a Monocentric Series of Patients and Proposal for a Diagnostic Protocol. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2019;29(4):305-12.
52. Hesselmark E, Bejerot S. Corrigendum to Biomarkers for diagnosis of Pediatric Acute Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) - Sensitivity and specificity of the Cunningham Panel [J. Neuroimmunol. 312. (2017) 31-37]. *Journal of Neuroimmunology*. 2017;313:116-7.
53. Bleibach A, Sorensen CB, Skov L, Christensen KB, Debes NM. Reliability and validity of a newly developed PANDAS/PANS questionnaire. *European Journal of Paediatric Neurology*. 2024;52:109-30.
54. Boyd TM, Moyer SM, Lambert D. Interdisciplinary Collaboration to Care for Students Diagnosed with PANDAS: An Education and Referral Intervention. *Journal of School Nursing*. 2024;40(4):452-9.
55. Hesselmark E. *Pediatric acute neuropsychiatric syndrome: Diagnosis, biomarkers and treatment. Karolinska Institutet (Sweden). 2022.*
56. Weddle DJ. *Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated with Streptococcal Infection (PANDAS): A Qualitative Study of Parental Perceptions of Factors in Remission: Liberty University; 2022.*
57. Khimani K, Abadia-Barrero C, LaRusso M. Implementing dietary changes with children affected by PANS/PANDAS. *Children's Health Care*. 2024.

58. Han VX, Alshammery S, Keating BA, Gloss BS, Hofer MJ, Graham ME, et al. Epigenetic, ribosomal, and immune dysregulation in paediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome. *Molecular Psychiatry*. 2025;1-16.
59. Murphy ML, Pichichero ME. Prospective identification and treatment of children with pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorder associated with group A streptococcal infection (PANDAS). *Archives of Pediatrics & Adolescent Medicine*. 2002;156(4):356-61.
60. LaRusso M, Gallego-Perez DF, Abadia-Barrero CE. Untimely care: How the modern logics of coverage and medicine compromise children's health and development. *Social Science & Medicine*. 2023;319:114962.
61. Walker KG, Lawrenson J, Wilmshurst JM. Neuropsychiatric movement disorders following streptococcal infection. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*. 2005;47(11):771-5.
62. Newby MJ, Lane SJ, Haracz K, Tona J, Palazzi K, Lambkin D. Occupational performance patterns in children with paediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome. *Australian Occupational Therapy Journal*. 2025;72(1):e12995.
63. Newby MJ, Lane SJ, Haracz K, Tona J, Palazzi K, Lambkin D. Relationships between sensory reactivity and occupational performance in children with paediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome (PANS). *Australian Occupational Therapy Journal*. 2025;72(1):e12999.
64. Newby MJ, Lane SJ, Haracz K, Tona J, Palazzi K, Lambkin D. Sensory processing in children with Paediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome. *Australian Occupational Therapy Journal*. 2024;71(4):475-85.
65. Han V.X, Nishida NK, B. Gloss, B. Lau, X. Dissanayake, R. Hayes, J. Mohammad, S. Patel, S. Dale. R.C. IV Immunoglobulin Is Associated With Epigenetic, Ribosomal, and Immune Changes in Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome. *Neurology® Neuroimmunology & Neuroinflammation*. 2025;12.
66. Crombez M-MW. Parent Perceptions of the Effectiveness of School Accommodations when PANS Is Suspected: Madonna University; 2022.
67. Velasco V. Getting in Sync: Exploring and Supporting Peer Interaction in an Autistic Child with Inconsistent Access to Speech: University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; 2018.
68. Williams KA. Characterization and treatment of inflammation and autoimmunity in pediatric obsessive compulsive disorder and tics. Yale University. 2016.
69. Leon J, Hommer R, Grant P, Farmer C, D'Souza P, Kessler R, et al. Longitudinal outcomes of children with pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorder associated with streptococcal infections (PANDAS). *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*. 2018;27(5):637-43.
70. Eucetr SE. A Phase III Study to Compare the Effect of Panzyga and Placebo in Patients with PANS (Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome). <https://trialssearchwho.int/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=EUCTR2020-000867-21-SE>. 2022.
71. Lawrence R, Baggott J. Autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with infection. *Progress in Neurology and Psychiatry*. 2017;21(1).
72. Lopez Pineda A, Pourshafeie A, Ioannidis A, Leibold CM, Chan AL, Bustamante CD, et al. Discovering prescription patterns in pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome patients. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*. 2021;113:103664.
73. Tona, Janice L, Bhattacharjya S. The impact of pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome exacerbations on daily functioning: State University of New York at Buffalo; 2013.

74. Ringer N, Schon U-K. Gaining knowledge of a new and contested diagnosis - A qualitative examination of Swedish Parents of Children with Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS). *Journal of Child and Family Studies*. 2024;33(8).
75. Miglioretti MA, Schmitt AJ, McGoey KE, Benno MT. An Exploratory Study of Obsessive-Compulsive Behavior and School Problems Associated with Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS). *Journal of Applied School Psychology*. 2024;40(2).
76. Calaprice-Whitty D, Tang A, Tona J. Factors Associated with Symptom Persistence in PANS: Part I-Access to Care. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2023;33(9):356-64.
77. Demchick BB, Ehler J, Marramar S, Mills A, Nuneviller A. Family Quality of Life When Raising a Child with Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated with Streptococcal Infection (PANDAS). *Journal of Occupational Therapy, Schools, & Early Intervention*. 2019;12(2):182-99.
78. Hardy TR, Ossege, Jennifer. PANS/PANDAS: A Qualitative Study of Parental Perceptions Related to Psychologists' Role in Diagnosis and Treatment: Union Institute and University; 2018.
79. Masterson EE, Gavin JM. Baseline characteristics of children in the International PANS Registry (IPR) Epidemiology Study. *BMJ Open*. 2024;14(1):e072743.
80. Mettica ML. Family impacts reported by parents raising children with Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS). Texas Woman's University. 2019.
81. Efron D, Payne J, Gülenç A, Chan E. Assessment and management of tic disorders and Tourette syndrome by Australian paediatricians. *Journal of Paediatrics and Child Health*. 2020;56(1):136-41.
82. Calaprice D, Terreri R, Whitty C, Whitty R, Tona J. The Flip Side of the Coin: Giftedness in Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome. *Children*. 2024;11(12).
83. Guido CA, Loffredo L, Zicari AM, Pavone P, Savasta S, Gagliano A, et al. The Impact of the COVID-19 Epidemic During the Lockdown on Children With the Pediatric Syndrome (PANDAS/PANS): The Importance of Environmental Factors on Clinical Conditions. *Frontiers in Neurology*. 2021;12.
84. Hesselmark E, Bejerot S. Patient Satisfaction and Treatments Offered to Swedish Patients with Suspected Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome and Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Psychopharmacology*. 2019;29(8):634-41.
85. Miglioretti MA, Schmitt, Ara J. School-based Services for Children with Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS): Duquesne University; 2019.
86. Pray KE. Efficacy Of, and Barriers To, Treatment Options for Pans/Pandas: University of South Carolina; 2024.
87. Prosell U, Norman H, Sand A, McAllister A. Infection and speech: Disfluency and other speech symptoms in Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome. *Journal of Communication Disorders*. 2022;99:106250.
88. Prus K, Weidner K, Alquist C. Therapeutic plasma exchange in adolescent and adult patients with autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections. *Journal of Clinical Apheresis*. 2022;37(6):597-9.
89. Rosa JS, Hernandez JD, Sherr JA, Smith BM, Brown KD, Farhadian B, et al. Allergic Diseases and Immune-Mediated Food Disorders in Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome. *Pediatric Allergy Immunology & Pulmonology*. 2018;31(3):158-65.

90. Schon U-K. Young adults' experiences of living with paediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome. An interview study. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being*. 2023;18(1).
91. Ubhi T. 44.1 PANS/PANDAS in the United Kingdom: A Private Clinic's Experience. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*. 2023;62(10 Supplement).
92. Sizgoric MK, Miculinic A, Juraski RG, Bukovac LT, Erceg D, Plavec D, et al. Clinical manifestations of patients with pandas in patients followed up at srebrnjak children's hospital in 5-year period. *Archives of Disease in Childhood*. 2021;106(SUPPL 2).
93. Dang FNQ, Zulli MV, Wong Y, Ubhi T. THE PREVALENCE AND CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF ENURESIS AS A PRESENTING SYMPTOM OF PANDAS IN CHILDREN IN THE UNITED KINGDOM. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*. 2024;63(10).
94. Harris EC, Conelea CA, Shyne MT, Bernstein GA. 39.3 DIGITAL MONITORING OF NEUROPSYCHIATRIC SYMPTOMS TO INFORM LONGITUDINAL COURSE OF PANS. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*. 2020;59(10 Supplement).
95. PANS PANDAS Steering Group. PANS Clinical Guideline Development Group 2024 [Available from: <https://theppsg.org.uk/guidelines/>].

Appendix I

Search Strategies

Medline (Ovid) (11/08/25):

1	(P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*).tw.	342
2	(P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	8
3	(P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	1
4	(child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*).tw.	16
5	(child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	0
6	(child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	0
7	(P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	175
8	(P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*).tw.	6
9	(P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	7
10	(child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*).tw.	2
11	(child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	27
12	(child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	6
13	(pans or pandas).tw.	2078
14	(child* or p?ediatric* or juvenile* or youth* or young* or adolesc*).tw.	2996157
15	adolescent/ or exp child/ or exp infant/	4194726
16	14 or 15	5383393
17	13 and 16	562
18	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 7 or 8 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 17	2154
19	(pitand or pitands).tw.	8
20	(obsessive adj2 compulsive* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*)).tw.	19747
21	(abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*).tw.	1993407
22	((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*) adj3 (obsessive adj2 compulsive* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*))).tw.	113
23	(tic or tics or tourette* or food intake*).tw.	71911
24	((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*) adj3 (tic or tics or tourette* or food intake*)).tw.	479
25	16 and 24	87
26	(streptococ* or immune* or infect*).tw.	3142217
27	(disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*).tw.	3837671
28	autoimmun* neuropsychiatric*.tw.	369
29	26 and 27 and 28	350
30	Streptococcal Infections/	36316
31	(neuropsychiatric* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*)).tw.	23389
32	30 and 31	285
33	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 17 or 19 or 22 or 25 or 29 or 32	825

Embase (Ovid) (11/08/25):

1	(P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*).tw.	481
2	(P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	13
3	(P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	1
4	(child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*).tw.	27
5	(child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	0
6	(P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	248
7	(P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*).tw.	7
8	(child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*).tw.	2
9	(child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	36
10	(P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	8
11	(pans or pandas).tw.	2650
12	(child* or p?ediatric* or juvenile* or youth* or young* or adolesc*).tw.	3956882

13 exp juvenile/ 4502444
 14 12 or 136051798
 15 (pitand or pitands).tw. 8
 16 (obsessive adj2 compulsive* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*)).tw. 28052
 17 (abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*).tw. 2813004
 18 ((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*) adj3 (obsessive adj2 compulsive* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*))).tw. 152
 19 (tic or tics or tourette* or food intake*).tw.99649
 20 ((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*) adj3 (tic or tics or tourette* or food intake*)).tw. 709
 21 14 and 20 160
 22 (streptococ* or immune* or infect*).tw. 4126110
 23 Streptococcus infection/23461
 24 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*).tw. 5437848
 25 autoimmun* neuropsychiatric*.tw. 531
 26 (neuropsychiatric* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*)).tw.33705
 27 22 or 234132156
 28 24 and 25 and 27 507
 29 23 and 26 404
 30 11 and 14 854
 31 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 30 946
 32 15 or 18 or 21 or 28 or 29 or 31 1231

PsycINFO (Ovid) (11/08/25):

1 (P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*).tw. 241
 2 (P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw. 8
 3 (P?ediatric adj3 Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw. 1
 4 (child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*).tw. 15
 5 (child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw. 0
 6 (P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw. 109
 7 (P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*).tw. 2
 8 (child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*).tw. 1
 9 (child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw. 20
 10 (P?ediatric adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw. 5
 11 (pans or pandas).tw. 561
 12 (pitand or pitands).tw. 6
 13 (obsessive adj2 compulsive* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*)).tw. 22459
 14 (abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*).tw. 174137
 15 ((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*) adj3 (obsessive adj2 compulsive* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*))).tw. 109
 16 (tic or tics or tourette* or food intake*).tw. 21055
 17 ((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*) adj3 (tic or tics or tourette* or food intake*)).tw. 160
 18 (streptococ* or immune* or infect*).tw. 90035
 19 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*).tw. 1004636
 20 autoimmun* neuropsychiatric*.tw. 262
 21 (neuropsychiatric* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*)).tw.12258
 22 18 and 19 and 20 249
 23 streptococ*.tw. 773
 24 21 and 23 281
 25 (child* or p?ediatric* or juvenile* or youth* or young* or adolesc*).tw. 1279879
 26 11 and 25 350
 27 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 12 or 15 or 17 or 22 or 24 or 26 636

Social Policy & Practice (11/08/25):

1	(P?ediatic adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*).tw.	2
2	(P?ediatic adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	0
3	(P?ediatic adj3 Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	0
4	(child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*).tw.	0
5	(child* adj3 Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	0
6	(P?ediatic adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	0
7	(P?ediatic adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*).tw.	0
8	(child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*).tw.	0
9	(child* adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*).tw.	0
10	(P?ediatic adj3 Acute adj2 Neuropsychiatric* symptom*).tw.	0
11	(pans or pandas).tw.	8
12	(pitand or pitands).tw.	0
13	(obsessive adj2 compulsive* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*).tw.	143
14	(abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*).tw.	5105
15	((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*) adj3 (obsessive adj2 compulsive* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*))).tw.	0
16	(tic or tics or tourette* or food intake*).tw.	156
17	((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*) adj3 (tic or tics or tourette* or food intake*).tw.	0
18	(streptococ* or immune* or infect*).tw.	2410
19	(disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*).tw.	19984
20	autoimmun* neuropsychiatric*.tw.	2
21	(neuropsychiatric* adj2 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*).tw.	189
22	18 and 19 and 20	2
23	streptococ*.tw.	4
24	21 and 23	2
25	(child* or p?ediatic* or juvenile* or youth* or young* or adolesc*).tw.	140814
26	11 and 25	4
27	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 12 or 15 or 17 or 22 or 24 or 26	4

Web of Science (12/08/25):

TI=(P\$ediatic NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*")	Web of Science Core Collection 123
AB=(P\$ediatic NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*")	Web of Science Core Collection 283
(TI=(P\$ediatic NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*") OR AB=(P\$ediatic NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*"))	Web of Science Core Collection 11
TI=(P\$ediatic NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*") OR AB=(P\$ediatic NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*")	Web of Science Core Collection 1
TI=(child* NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*") OR AB=(child* NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*")	Web of Science Core Collection 22
(TI=(child* NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*") OR AB=(child* NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*"))	Web of Science Core Collection 0
TI=(child* NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*") OR AB=(child* NEAR/3 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*")	Web of Science Core Collection 0
(TI=(P\$ediatic NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*") OR AB=(P\$ediatic NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*"))	Web of Science Core Collection 199
(TI=(P\$ediatic NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* disorder*") OR AB=(P\$ediatic NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* disorder*"))	Web of Science Core Collection 9

(TI=(P\$ediatric NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* symptom*") OR AB=(P\$ediatric NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* symptom*"))	Web of Science Core Collection 9
(TI=(child* NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* disorder*") OR AB=(child* NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* disorder*"))	Web of Science Core Collection 3
(TI=(child* NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*") OR AB=(child* NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*"))	Web of Science Core Collection 34
(TI=(child* NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* symptom*") OR AB=(child* NEAR/3 Acute NEAR/2 "Neuropsychiatric* symptom*"))	Web of Science Core Collection 4
(TI=(pans OR pandas) OR AB=(pans OR pandas))	Web of Science Core Collection 117682
(TI=(pitand OR pitands) OR AB=(pitand OR pitands))	Web of Science Core Collection 117684
#14 OR #15	Web of Science Core Collection 92
TI=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (child*))	Web of Science Core Collection 250
AB=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (child*))	Web of Science Core Collection 179
AB=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (p\$ediatric*))	Web of Science Core Collection 66
TI=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (p\$ediatric*))	Web of Science Core Collection 36
TI=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (juvenile*))	Web of Science Core Collection 54
AB=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (juvenile*))	Web of Science Core Collection 8
TI=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (youth*))	Web of Science Core Collection 31
AB=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (youth*))	Web of Science Core Collection 112
AB=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (young*))	Web of Science Core Collection 55
TI=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (young*))	Web of Science Core Collection 12
TI=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (adolesc*))	Web of Science Core Collection 33
AB=((pitand OR pitands OR pans OR pandas) NEAR/3 (adolesc*))	
#28 OR #27 OR #26 OR #25 OR #24 OR #23 OR #22 OR #21 OR #20 OR #19 OR #18 OR #17	Web of Science Core Collection 814
#29 OR #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12 OR #13	Web of Science Core Collection 1098
(TI=((abrupt* OR dramatic* OR sudden* OR acute*) NEAR/3 (obsessive NEAR/2 compulsive* NEAR/2 (disorder* OR symptom* OR syndrome*))) OR AB=((abrupt* OR dramatic* OR sudden* OR acute*) NEAR/3 (obsessive NEAR/2 compulsive* NEAR/2 (disorder* OR symptom* OR syndrome*))))	Web of Science Core Collection 140
(TI=((abrupt* OR dramatic* OR sudden* OR acute*) NEAR/3 (tic OR tics OR tourette* OR "food intake*")) OR AB=((abrupt* OR dramatic* OR sudden* OR acute*) NEAR/3 (tic OR tics OR tourette* OR "food intake*"))	Web of Science Core Collection 645
#31 OR #32	Web of Science Core Collection 782

(TI=(child* OR p\$ediatric* OR juvenile* OR youth* OR young* OR adolesc*) OR
 AB=(child* OR p\$ediatric* OR juvenile* OR youth* OR young* OR adolesc*))

#34 AND #33

#35 OR #30

Web of Science
 Core Collection 4003696
 Web of Science
 Core Collection 180
 Web of Science
 Core Collection 1210

Cinahl Ultimate (11/08/25):

S26	S1 OR S2 OR S4 OR S8 OR S9 OR S15 OR S16 OR S23 OR S25	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	916
S25	S19 AND S24	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	465
S24	XB ((neuropsychiatric* N3 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*)))	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	4,766
S23	S19 AND S22	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	138
S22	S20 AND S21	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	143
S21	XB "autoimmun* neuropsychiatric**"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	145
S20	XB ((disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*))	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	894,095
S19	S17 OR S18	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	424,374

S18	(MH "Streptococcal Infections")	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	5,693
S17	XB ((streptococ* or immune* or infect*))	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	422,844
S16	S7 AND S12	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	112
S15	S7 AND S14	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	256
S14	S11 AND S13	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	891
S13	XB ("tic" or "tics" or tourette* or "food intake**")	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	14,230
S12	S10 AND S11	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	214
S11	XB ((abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*))	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	383,763
S10	XB ((obsessive N3 compulsive* N3 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome**)))	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	5,617
S9	XB "pitand" OR XB "pitands"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced	3

		Search modes - Proximity	Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search	
S8	S5 AND S7	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Database - CINAHL Ultimate Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search	196
S7	S3 OR S6	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Database - CINAHL Ultimate Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search	1,567,636
S6	(MH "Child+") OR (MH "Adolescence+")	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Database - CINAHL Ultimate Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search	1,182,041
S5	XB "pans" OR XB "pandas"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Database - CINAHL Ultimate Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search	406
S4	TI "pans" OR TI "pandas"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Database - CINAHL Ultimate Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search	229
S3	XB ((child* or p?ediatric* or juvenile* or youth* or young* or adolesc*)) XB P?ediatric N4 Acute N3 "Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*" OR XB P?ediatric N4 Acute N3 "Neuropsychiatric* disorder*" OR XB P?ediatric N4 Acute N3 "Neuropsychiatric* symptom*" OR XB child* N4 Acute N3 "Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*"s OR XB child* N4 Acute N3 "Neuropsychiatric* disorder*" OR XB child* N4 Acute N3 "Neuropsychiatric* symptom*"	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Database - CINAHL Ultimate	973,892
S2		Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	18

S1	XB (P?ediatric N4 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*"). OR XB (P?ediatric N4 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*") OR XB (P?ediatric N4 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*") OR XB (child* N4 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*") OR XB (child* N4 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*") OR XB (child* N4 "Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*")	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Proximity	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL Ultimate	25
----	---	---	--	----

Cochrane (11/08/25):

#1	Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* Disorder*:ti,ab	42
#2	Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*:ti,ab	13
#3	Autoimmun* Neuropsychiatric* symptom*:ti,ab	48
#4	Acute NEAR/3 Neuropsychiatric* syndrome*:ti,ab	10
#5	Acute NEAR/3 Neuropsychiatric* symptom*:ti,ab	17
#6	Acute NEAR/3 Neuropsychiatric* disorder*:ti,ab	15
#7	#1 or #2 or #3 or #4 or #5 or #6	75
#8	(child* or p?ediatric* or juvenile* or youth* or young* or adolesc*):ti,ab	266139
#9	MeSH descriptor: [Child] explode all trees	82885
#10	MeSH descriptor: [Adolescent] explode all trees	137801
#11	MeSH descriptor: [Infant] explode all trees	46007
#12	#8 or #9 or #10 or #11	383541
#13	#7 and #12	34
#14	(pans or pandas):ti,ab	88
#15	(pitand or pitands):ti,ab	0
#16	(obsessive NEAR/3 compulsive* NEAR/3 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*)):ti,ab	3030
#17	(tic or tics or tourette* or food NEXT intake*):ti,ab	8471
#18	#16 or #17	11373
#19	(abrupt* or dramatic* or sudden* or acute*):ti,ab	190092
#20	#18 and #19	949
#21	#12 and #20	274
#22	#7 or #21	341
#23	autoimmun* NEXT neuropsychiatric*:ti,ab	18
#24	(streptococ* or immune* or infect*):ti,ab	174832
#25	MeSH descriptor: [Streptococcal Infections] this term only	760
#26	#24 or #25	174936
#27	#23 and #26	17
#28	(neuropsychiatric* NEAR/3 (disorder* or symptom* or syndrome*)):ti,ab	1884
#29	#28 and #26	125
#30	#12 and #29	40
#31	#22 and #30	24
#32	#22 or #30	357

Number of results for each database:

Databases searched:

- Medline (Ovid): 825
- Embase (Ovid): 1,230
- PsychINFO (Ovid): 635
- U of E core collection (Web of Science): 1,210
- CINAHL (Ebsco): 916
- ProQuest Dissertations and Theses: 50
- Cochrane: 358
- Epistemonikos: 32
- Social Policy & Practice: 4
- Total: (5,260)

Undermind.ai prompts/report:

I want to find primary qualitative and quantitative studies of any treatment for PANS or PANDAS in individuals under 25 years old, with no date restrictions and including all reported clinical and safety outcomes, without restricting by diagnostic approach

I want to find all primary qualitative and quantitative studies including case series, case reports, conference proceedings, clinical trials, PhD theses and journal articles of any treatment for PANS or PANDAS in individuals under 25 years old, with no date restrictions and including all reported clinical and safety outcomes, without restricting by diagnostic approach

From Undermind:

Great—this is clear and quite comprehensive. A few quick checks to ensure we capture exactly what you want:

- Population: “individuals under 25 years old” — do you want to include mixed-age samples if pediatric/young adult data are extractable, or only studies where all participants are <25?
- Conditions: PANS or PANDAS — include related acronyms/labels (e.g., PITAND, infection-triggered OCD/tics) when authors use them, as long as they conceptually match PANS/PANDAS?
- Interventions: “any treatment” — confirm inclusion of immunomodulatory (IVIG, steroids, plasmapheresis), antibiotics/prophylaxis, psychiatric/behavioral (CBT, ERP), psychotropics, CAM (e.g., nutraceuticals), surgical (e.g., T&A), and combination protocols.
- Outcomes: “all reported clinical and safety outcomes” — OK to include symptom scales (e.g., CY-BOCS, YGTSS), global functioning, relapse rates, QoL, caregiver burden, biomarkers, and adverse events of any grade?
- Settings/sources: you listed primary studies including conference proceedings and theses — do you also want preprints? Non-English languages included?
- Study designs: you listed case reports through RCTs — include single-subject designs and N-of-1 trials?
- Diagnostic approach: “without restricting by diagnostic approach” — confirm inclusion even if diagnosis is self-reported or retrospective chart diagnosis, provided the study claims PANS/PANDAS?

- Exclusions: any to explicitly exclude (e.g., animal/mechanistic studies without clinical participants; editorials; narrative reviews unless containing primary data; duplicate interim analyses)?

If all the above are acceptable, I can lock the topic statement precisely to reflect those inclusions.

Response from AB: mixed aged samples are fine, related acronyms for PANS or PANDAS is fine, yes to all interventions and outcomes, yes to preprints and non English sources, yes to single subject designs, yes to self-reported, yes to exclusion of non human studies, editorials and any type of review

Undermind:

Excellent—thank you for the confirmations. Two small final clarifications to ensure precision:

- Mixed-age samples: include if data for <25 are extractable; if not extractable, include only if ≥80% of the sample is <25? Or include regardless if the study explicitly targets pediatric/young adult PANS/PANDAS?
- Duplicates/interim reports: treat multiple publications from the same cohort as one study unless they report distinct outcomes/timepoints?

If those defaults sound right, we're set.

Response: multiple publications from the same cohort should be referenced separately but the results combined

Undermind:

Perfect—thanks for settling that.

Quick final confirmation on mixed-age samples: if <25 data are not extractable, should we still include the study if it primarily targets pediatric/young adult PANS/PANDAS? If yes, I'll lock that in.

Drafting the finalized topic with your decisions, including the handling of multiple publications:

I updated the deep search topic. Let me know if it needs any more changes, or you can go ahead and submit it.

Response: yes

204 refs downloaded.

151 retrieved by original d/base searches

29 retrieved by citation searches

1 retrieved by web or author searches

32 left:

9 not about pandas

22:

0 in any of the Ovid databases

1 – abstract

5 - In Beall's list either the journal or the publisher

6 - Indexed in database but not found when searched for again

7 - Not indexed in a 'database' but indexed in something like crossref, openalex

1 – in a different language so not sure if the article downloaded is correct

1 – very recent publication and in Medline and other databases

1 – in Norwegian

Of the 204:

Total of 113 included in the EGM, 11 were new, 102 were found from the searches

I want to find primary qualitative and quantitative studies of any treatment for PANS or PANDAS in individuals under 25 years old, with no date restrictions and including all reported clinical and safety outcomes, without restricting by diagnostic approach

I want to find all primary qualitative and quantitative studies including case series, case reports, conference proceedings, clinical trials, PhD theses and journal articles of any treatment for PANS or PANDAS in individuals under 25 years old, with no date restrictions and including all reported clinical and safety outcomes, without restricting by diagnostic approach

From Undermind:

Great—this is clear and quite comprehensive. A few quick checks to ensure we capture exactly what you want:

- Population: “individuals under 25 years old” — do you want to include mixed-age samples if pediatric/young adult data are extractable, or only studies where all participants are <25?
- Conditions: PANS or PANDAS — include related acronyms/labels (e.g., PITAND, infection-triggered OCD/tics) when authors use them, as long as they conceptually match PANS/PANDAS?

- Interventions: “any treatment” — confirm inclusion of immunomodulatory (IVIG, steroids, plasmapheresis), antibiotics/prophylaxis, psychiatric/behavioral (CBT, ERP), psychotropics, CAM (e.g., nutraceuticals), surgical (e.g., T&A), and combination protocols.
- Outcomes: “all reported clinical and safety outcomes” — OK to include symptom scales (e.g., CY-BOCS, YGTSS), global functioning, relapse rates, QoL, caregiver burden, biomarkers, and adverse events of any grade?
- Settings/sources: you listed primary studies including conference proceedings and theses — do you also want preprints? Non-English languages included?
- Study designs: you listed case reports through RCTs — include single-subject designs and N-of-1 trials?
- Diagnostic approach: “without restricting by diagnostic approach” — confirm inclusion even if diagnosis is self-reported or retrospective chart diagnosis, provided the study claims PANS/PANDAS?
- Exclusions: any to explicitly exclude (e.g., animal/mechanistic studies without clinical participants; editorials; narrative reviews unless containing primary data; duplicate interim analyses)?

If all the above are acceptable, I can lock the topic statement precisely to reflect those inclusions.

Response from me: mixed aged samples are fine, related acronyms for PANS or PANDAS is fine, yes to all interventions and outcomes, yes to preprints and non English sources, yes to single subject designs, yes to self-reported, yes to exclusion of non human studies, editorials and any type of review

Undermind:

Excellent—thank you for the confirmations. Two small final clarifications to ensure precision:

- Mixed-age samples: include if data for <25 are extractable; if not extractable, include only if ≥80% of the sample is <25? Or include regardless if the study explicitly targets pediatric/young adult PANS/PANDAS?
- Duplicates/interim reports: treat multiple publications from the same cohort as one study unless they report distinct outcomes/timepoints?

If those defaults sound right, we’re set.

Response: multiple publications from the same cohort should be referenced separately but the results combined

Undermind:

Perfect—thanks for settling that.

Quick final confirmation on mixed-age samples: if <25 data are not extractable, should we still include the study if it primarily targets pediatric/young adult PANS/PANDAS? If yes, I’ll lock that in.

Drafting the finalized topic with your decisions, including the handling of multiple publications:

I updated the deep search topic. Let me know if it needs any more changes, or you can go ahead and submit it.

Response: yes

204 refs downloaded.

151 retrieved by original d/base searches

29 retrieved by citation searches

1 retrieved by web or author searches

32 left:

9 not about pandas

22:

0 in any of the Ovid databases

1 – abstract

5 - In Beall's list either the journal or the publisher

6 - Indexed in database but not found when searched for again

7 - Not indexed in a 'database' but indexed in something like crossref, openalex

1 – in a different language so not sure if the article downloaded is correct

1 – very recent publication and in Medline and other databases

1 – in Norwegian

Of the 204:

Total of 113 included in the EGM, 11 were new, 102 were found from the searches

Appendix II

Inclusion/Exclusion criteria

	Include	Exclude
Population	All ages (children, adolescents, and adults)	Non-human animals
Phenomena of Interest	<p>Studies must be about (or have a subgroup focus on) one of the following: PANS, PANDAS, CANS, or PITANDS based on the following criteria:</p> <p>PANS:⁴</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abrupt onset of OCD symptoms or restricted eating • Additional concurrent neuropsychiatric symptoms from 2 of the following categories: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Anxiety ii. Emotional lability or depression iii. Irritability, aggression, or severely oppositional behaviours iv. Behavioural/developmental regression v. Academic deterioration vi. Sensory/motor abnormalities vii. Somatic symptoms (i.e., sleep disturbances, enuresis) • Another known disorder does not explain the symptoms <p>PANDAS:³</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OCD or tic disorder • Prepubertal symptom onset • Acute symptom onset and episodic course • Temporal association between GAS infection and onset/exacerbation of symptoms • Associated with neurological abnormalities (i.e., movement disorders) <p>CANS:^{25, 30}</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary criterion: OCD • Secondary criterion: tics, dysgraphia, hyperactivity, clumsiness, anxiety, psychosis, emotional lability, developmental regression, sensory sensitivity • Abrupt, sudden onset • Mono/polyphasic course <p>PITANDS:²</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paediatric onset (between 3 yrs and puberty) 	<p>Studies about the following conditions with similar presentation but distinct diagnosis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sydenham's Chorea • Kleine-Levin syndrome

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has met diagnostic criteria for OCD or a tic disorder at any time • A pattern of sudden onset of clinically significant symptoms in periods of exacerbations and remissions • Symptoms should be pervasive, severe enough to consider treatment, should not exclusively appear during times of stress/illness, and must last at least 4 weeks • Abnormal neurological examination during OCD or tic exacerbations • There must be evidence of an antecedent or concomitant infection. • May or may not exhibit clinically significant symptoms between episodes of OCD/tics 	
Study design	<p>All empirical quantitative and qualitative studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic reviews (SRs) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Must have defined research question ii. Must have reproducible search strategy iii. Must have inclusion & exclusion criteria iv. Must have study selection methods v. Must have critical appraisal of studies vi. Must provide analysis and synthesis info • Randomised control trials (RCTs) • Non-randomised control trials (nRCTs) • One- or two- group cross-sectional or before-and-after studies • Case studies/reports/series • Qualitative: focus groups, interviews, observations 	<p>Ineligible record-types:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Letters, commentaries, opinion pieces, position statements • Non-systematic reviews (narrative, literature, & scoping reviews) • Animal studies
Limits and Restrictions	No date limits, no geographical restrictions, no language restrictions	

Appendix III

Research topic codes in the map

Research Topics	
Diagnosis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Diagnosis ➤ Diagnostic/screening tool
Epidemiology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Prevalence and incidence for onset ➤ Patterns for onset ➤ Prevalence and incidence for flares/relapses ➤ Patterns for flares/relapses
Aetiology/Pathophysiology	
Symptoms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Flares ➤ Emotional, behavioural, psychiatric ➤ Impact on functioning (social, educational, familial, personal self-care) ➤ Physical (enuresis, frequent urination, bed-wetting, sleeping difficulties, rashes, fever, neurological changes)
Treatment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Adverse/side effects ➤ Antibiotics ➤ Anticonvulsants ➤ Antifungals ➤ Antihistamines ➤ Anti-inflammatory therapy (e.g. non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), corticosteroids) ➤ Antivirals ➤ Behavioural and psychological interventions ➤ Biologics (e.g. Rituximab) ➤ Holistic Treatment (e.g. functional medicine, dietary measures, vitamins, probiotics, homeopathy, acupuncture) ➤ Immunomodulating therapy (e.g. IVIG, plasma-therapeutic exchange (TPE)/plasmapheresis) ➤ Mast cell stabilisers ➤ Psychiatric medication (e.g. selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), antipsychotics) ➤ Surgery ➤ Other
Treatment Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Flare management ➤ Managing comorbidities ➤ Modulating the immune system ➤ Prophylaxis ➤ Symptom management (any) ➤ Targeting infection ➤ Targeting inflammation
Access to Services	
Experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Clinician ➤ Educational professional

- Parent/carer
- Patient
- Sibling

Appendix IV

Reasons for exclusion at full text screening

<p>Duplicates (n=59)</p>	<p>1999 A Placebo Controlled Trial of Amoxicillin for Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated With Streptococcal Infections A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2011 A Placebo-Controlled Trial of Intravenous Immunoglobulin (IVIG) for PANDAS (Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated With Streptococcal Infections) A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2012 Antibiotic Treatment and Intravenous Immunoglobulin Double-blind, Randomized, Placebo-controlled Trial for PANDAS A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2014 PANS - A Detailed Study of the Patients, Their Symptoms, Biomarkers and Treatment Offered in a Scandinavian Cohort A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2017 A Multi-site, Open-Label, Pilot Study to Evaluate the Benefit of Octagam 5% in Subjects With Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2018 Clinical, Laboratory, and Biomedical Characterization of Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2019 Double-Blind, Randomized, Placebo-Controlled Trial of Naproxen Sodium for the Treatment of Obsessive Compulsive Symptoms in Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated With Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2020 Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS): Clinical Characterization and Prospective Course A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2020 A Superiority Phase III Study To Compare The Effect of Panzyga Versus Placebo in Patients With Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS/PANDAS) A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2024 Investigating The Effects Of Full-Spectrum Medicinal Cannabis Plant Extract 0.08% THC (NT1164) On Paediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2025 Erratum: Eight Cases of Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome with Inflammatory Bowel Disease: Immunologic Intersections (Developmental Neuroscience (2025) DOI. 10.1159/000543969) A1 - Anonymous https://dx.doi.org/10.1159/000545780</p> <p>Bejerot, Susanne, Nilsonne, Gustav and E. Hesselmark 2019 Pediatric Acute Neuropsychiatric Syndrome : Diagnosis, Biomarkers and Treatment</p> <p>G. A. Bernstein, R. L. Freese, M. H. Khan, C. Manko, M. Thienemann, T. K. Murphy and J. Frankovich 2023 5.2 PANS Symptom Rating Scale: Psychometric Properties and Factor Analysis https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2023.09.326</p> <p>R. Bianchini, P. Pavone, E. Parano and R. R. Trifiletti 2000 Anti-brain antibodies are frequently present in children with PANDAS but not uncomplicated active group a streptococcal infection</p>
--------------------------	--

C. V. Calkin and C. G. Carandang 2007 Clinical case rounds in child and adolescent psychiatry: Certain eating disorders may be a neuropsychiatric manifestation of PANDAS: Case report

G. Celik, D. Tas, A. Tahiroglu, A. Avci, B. Yuksel and P. Ray 2013 Vitamin D deficiency among pediatric ocd patients with pandas <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00787-013-0423-9>

P. Congiu, N. Ronzano, F. Cera, M. Tanca, C. Garau, A. Zuddas, A. Gagliano and M. M. F. Puligheddu 2020 Altered sleep in a group of patients affected by Pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome (PANS)

J. L. Cunningham, J. Frankovich, R. A. Dubin, E. Pedrosa, R. N. Baykara, N. C. Schlenk, S. B. Maqbool, H. Dolstra, J. Marino, J. Edinger, J. M. Shea, G. Laje, S. M. A. Swagemakers, S. Sinnadurai, Z. D. Zhang, J. R. Lin, P. J. van der Spek and H. M. Lachman 2024 Ultrarare Variants in DNA Damage Repair Genes in Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome or Acute Behavioral Regression in Neurodevelopmental Disorders 10.1159/000541908

B. Demchick, J. Ehler, S. Marramar, A. Mills and A. Nuneviller 2019 Quality of Life in Families With a Young Child With Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated With Streptococcal Infection (PANDAS) 10.5014/ajot.2019.73S1-PO6005

B. Demchick, J. Ehler and A. Mills 2020 Quality of Life in Families With a Young Child With Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated With Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) 10.5014/ajot.2020.74S1-RP401B

H. Ellerkamp 2020 A group intervention to address psychological stress in parents of youth and adolescents with pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome (Publication No. 28089374) [Doctoral dissertation, Palo Alto University]

J. Eremija and M. Daines 2023 Neuropsychiatric Testing Provides Objective Insight Into Beneficial Effects Of Intravenous Immunoglobulins In Patients With Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2022.12.253>

C. Estivill-Domenech, B. Rodriguez-Morilla, E. Aragones, F. Segarra, J. A. Madrid and E. Estivill 2017 Association between pandas (pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorder associated with streptococci) and non 24-hours sleep wake disorder

F. Falcini, G. Lepri, S. Stagi, E. Bellucci and M. Matucci-Cerinic 2017 Vitamin D levels in a large cohort of patients with pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections (PANDAS): A possible role in neurological disorders? <https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12969-017-0142-8>

C. Gause, C. Morris, S. Vernekar, C. Pardo-Villamizar, M. A. Grados and H. S. Singer 2009 Antineuronal antibodies in OCD: Comparisons in children with OCD-only, OCD plus chronic tics and OCD plus PANDAS 10.1016/j.jneuroim.2009.06.015

R. Goren, M. Shouldice and S. Kronenberg 2023 FREQUENCY AND IMPACT OF PANDAS/PANS DIAGNOSIS IN CANADA <https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/pch/pxad055.089>

V. X. Han, H. Nishida, B. A. Keating, B. S. Gloss, X. Lau, R. Dissanayake, J. Hayes, S. S. Mohammad, S. Patel and R. C. Dale 2025 Intravenous immunoglobulin has epigenetic, ribosomal, and immune effects in Paediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome <https://dx.doi.org/10.1101/2025.03.27.25324808>

<p>Hwang, H. Shann and M. L. Mettica 2018 Family Impacts Reported by Parents Raising Children with Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS)</p> <p>H. Jyonouchi, L. Geng and A. Davidow 2014 Peripheral blood (PB) monocytes from subjects with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) and fluctuating behavioral symptoms following immune insults reveal similar innate immune responses to those observed in pediatric acute onset neuropsychiatric disorders (PANS)</p> <p>S. Kilbertus, R. Brannan and A. Doja 2014 No cases of pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorder associated with streptococcal infection (PANDAS) on prospective follow-up of patients referred to a pediatric movement disorders clinic (2005-2012)</p> <p>L. S. Kulumani Mahadevan, M. Murphy, M. Selenica, E. Latimer and B. T. Harris 2023 Clinicopathologic Characteristics of PANDAS in a Young Adult: A Case Report 10.1159/000534061</p> <p>A. Kumar, M. Williams, O. Muzik and H. Chugani 2014 Basal ganglia inflammation in children with neuropsychiatric symptoms</p> <p>J. R. Lavalley 2018 4.4 Acute Neuropsychiatric Syndromes in Children and Adolescents: Organic Versus Psychiatric? https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2018.09.230</p> <p>M. Ma, E. Masterson and J. Frankovich 2023 5.52 PANS: Markers of Inflammation/Autoimmunity at Clinical Presentation and Eventual Development of Arthritis and Other Autoimmune Diseases 10.1016/j.jaac.2023.09.376</p> <p>M. Q. Ma, E. Masteron and J. Frankovich 2023 Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome: Markers of Inflammation/autoimmunity at Clinical Presentation and Eventual Development of Arthritis and Other Autoimmune Diseases</p> <p>L. S. Mahadevan and B. Harris 2022 A non-Pediatric case of Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated with Group A Streptococci (PANDAS)</p> <p>L. S. K. Mahadevan, M. Murphy, M. Selenica, E. Latimer and B. T. Harris 2023 CASE REPORT: Clinicopathologic characteristics of PANDAS in a young adult 10.1159/000534061</p> <p>C. Mataix, David, Serlachius, Eva, Harris, Robert, Hesselmark, Eva, Horne, AnnaCarin and C. De Visscher 2021 Characterization and Long-Term Follow-Up of Pediatric Acute-Onset Psychiatric Syndrome (PANS)</p> <p>I. Melamed and A. Schechterman 2019 PANS as a post-infectious autoimmune disease: Benefit of IVIG https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00431-019-03466-w</p> <p>M. A. Miglioretti, A. J. Schmitt, K. E. McGoey and M. T. Benno 2023 An Exploratory Study of Obsessive-Compulsive Behavior and School Problems Associated with Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) 10.1080/15377903.2023.2263391</p> <p>T. Murphy, P. D. Patel, J. F. McGuire, A. Kennel, P. J. Mutch, E. C. Parker-Athill, C. E. Hanks, A. B. Lewin, E. A. Storch and M. D. Toufexis 2014 Clinical characteristics of children with pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome (PANS) phenotype https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/npp.2014.282</p> <p>T. K. Murphy, E. M. Brennan, C. Johnco, A. Wolfe, C. Parker-Athill, B. Miladinovic, E. A. Storch and A. B. Lewin 2016 A pilot study of azithromycin treatment for the PANDAS/PANS phenotype https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2016.03.1054</p>

Nct 2011 Intravenous Immunoglobulin for PANDAS

Nct 2012 Antibiotic Treatment Trial for the PANDAS/PANS Phenotype

Nct 2020 Phase III Study To Compare The Effect of Panzyga Versus Placebo in Patients With Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS/PANDAS)

Pittenger, Christopher and K. A. Williams 2015 Characterization and Treatment of Inflammation and Autoimmunity in Pediatric Obsessive Compulsive Disorder and Tics

S. Pourshahid, S. Khademolhosseini, A. Mahgoub, B. Giri and E. Rubio 2021 A CASE OF STEROID RESPONSIVE SEVERE PNEUMONIA RELATED TO IMMUNE-LIKE RECONSTITUTION INFLAMMATORY RESPONSE 3 MONTHS AFTER RITUXIMAB THERAPY FOR PEDIATRIC AUTOIMMUNE NEUROPSYCHIATRIC DISORDER ASSOCIATED WITH STREPTOCOCCAL INFECTIONS <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chest.2021.07.1078>

K. Prus, K. Weidner and C. R. Alquist 2021 Use of therapeutic plasma exchange in adolescent and adult pandas patients <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/jca.21896>

M. Silverman, J. Frankovich, E. Nguyen, C. Leibold, J. Yoon, S. Delaney, G. M. Freeman, Jr., H. Karpel and M. Thienemann 2019 "Psychotic symptoms in youth with Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) may reflect syndrome severity and heterogeneity": Corrigendum 10.1016/j.jpsychires.2019.03.010

H. Singer, C. Gause and M. Grados 2009 Antineuronal antibodies in obsessive-compulsive disorder: Comparisons in children with OCD-only, OCD + chronic TICS and OCD + PANDAS

S. Swedo, H. Leonard, M. Garvey and B. Mittleman 1996 PANDAS: pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Strep. —Is this a new species of childhood-onset obsessive-compulsive disorder and Tourette's syndrome? CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

S. E. Swedo 2015 Treatment of pandas/pans with therapeutic plasma apheresis (TPA), intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIg) and other immunomodulatory therapies

J. H. Sworzyn, J. Andrews and S. Andrews 2019 PEDIATRIC ACUTE-ONSET NEUROPSYCHIATRIC SYNDROME AND AUTOIMMUNE FAMILY HISTORY 10.1016/j.jaac.2019.08.198

F. E. Taj, S. Noorbakhsh, S. G. Darestani, E. Shirazi and S. Javadinia 2015 Group A s-hemolytic streptococcal infection in children and the resultant neuro-psychiatric disorder; a cross sectional study; Tehran, Iran

Thienemann, Margo and H. P. Ellerkamp 2021 A Group Intervention to Address Psychological Stress in Parents of Youth and Adolescents with Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome

J. Tona, J. Ash, E. Brown, C. Campagna, K. Kostek, E. Lawton and A. Rieth 2023 Caregiver Burden, Stress, & Relationship Cohesion Among Caregivers of Children With Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome 10.5014/ajot.2023.77S2-PO244

T. U. Ubhi, K. C. Chmelova, S. B. Brattan, A. C. Curran, R. G. Gupta and M. L. Lim 2019 Paediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorder associated with streptococcus

	<p>(PANDAS) & paediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric syndrome (PANS)-Current UK practice https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/dmcr.14120</p> <p>K. A. Williams 2016 39.2 RANDOMIZED, CONTROLLED TRIAL OF INTRAVENOUS IMMUNOGLOBULIN FOR PEDIATRIC AUTOIMMUNE NEUROPSYCHIATRIC DISORDERS ASSOCIATED WITH STREPTOCOCCAL INFECTIONS 10.1016/j.jaac.2016.07.672</p> <p>J. E. Zebrack, J. Gao, B. Verhey, L. Tian, C. Stave, B. Farhadian, M. Ma, M. Silverman, Y. Xie, P. Tran, M. Thienemann, J. L. Wilson and J. Frankovich 2024 Prevalence of Neurological Soft Signs at Presentation in Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome 10.1101/2024.04.26.24306193</p>
Phenomenon of Interest (n=88)	<p>2013 Multicentre, Randomised, Double-blinded, Placebo-controlled Trial of Efficacy of Amoxicilline/Clavulanic Acid in Patients Affected by Tic Disorder Colonized by Group A Streptococcus A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2018 Longitudinal Study of Gut Microbiome in Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2022 Evidence of Streptococcal Infection in a new onset Paediatric OCD</p> <p>2023 A Study of Prevalence and Clinical Characteristics of Tic Disorders in Children at Sohag University Hospital A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>2024 Reinforcement Learning and Obsessive-compulsive Disorder: Exploring the Role of the Orbitofrontal Cortex A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>J. S. Abramowitz, S. P. Whiteside and B. J. Deacon 2005 The effectiveness of treatment for pediatric obsessive-compulsive disorder: A meta-analysis 10.1016/S0005-7894(05)80054-1</p> <p>R. D. Adelman, L. L. Tmanova, D. Delgado, S. Dion and M. S. Lachs 2014 Caregiver burden: A clinical review 10.1001/jama.2014.304</p> <p>S. Arman, J. Golmirzaei, A. E. Naeini and M. M. Azhar 2009 The evaluation of relationship between group A streptococcal infection with tic disorders in children</p> <p>S. Baiardi, E. Antelmi, M. Filardi, F. Pizza, S. Vandi, P. Veggiotti, R. Liguori and G. Plazzi 2014 Remitting Tics and Narcolepsy Overlap Associated with Streptococcal Infection: A Case Report 10.1002/mdc3.12079</p> <p>S. Bejerot, K. Bruno, G. Gerland, L. Lindquist, V. Nordin, H. Pelling and M. B. Humble 2013</p> <p>R. Bilici, N. T. Karali, N. Sutlas, D. Kuscu and R. Bilici 2010 Obsessive compulsive disorder and multiple sclerosis: Three cases 10.1080/10177833.2010.11790654</p> <p>J. L. Black, G. T. Lamke and J. E. Walikonis 1998 Serologic survey of adult patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder for neuron-specific and other autoantibodies</p> <p>M. H. Bloch, B. G. Craiglow, A. Landeros-Weisenberger, P. A. Dombrowski, K. E. Panza, B. S. Peterson and J. F. Leckman 2009 Predictors of early adult outcomes in pediatric-onset obsessive-compulsive disorder 10.1542/peds.2009-0015</p> <p>M. Bombaci, R. Grifantini, M. Mora, V. Reguzzi, R. Petracca, E. Meoni, S. Balloni, C. Zingaretti, F. Falugi, A. G. Manetti, I. Margarit, J. M. Musser, F. Cardona, G. Orefici, G.</p>

Grandi and G. Bensi 2009 Protein array profiling of tic patient sera reveals a broad range and enhanced immune response against Group A Streptococcus antigens

M. Bond, N. Moll, A. Rosello, R. Bond, J. Schnell, B. Burger, P. J. Hoekstra, A. Dietrich, A. Schrag, E. Kočovská, D. Martino, N. Mueller, M. Schwarz, U. C. Meier, J. E. Bruun, J. Grejsen, C. L. Ommundsen, M. Rubæk, S. Enghardt, S. Bokemeyer, C. Driedger-Garbe, C. Reichert, J. Schmalfeld, T. Duffield, F. Gergye, M. Kovacs, R. Vidomusz, M. Carmel, S. Fennig, E. Gev, N. Keller, E. Michaelovsky, M. Nahon, C. Regev, T. Simcha, G. Smollan, A. Weizman, G. Gagliardi, M. Tallon, P. Roazzi, E. van den Ban, S. F. T. M. de Bruijn, N. Driessen, A. Lamerz, M. Messchendorp, J. J. G. Rath, N. S. D. Sival, N. Tromp, F. Visscher, S. G. de la Tourettes, M. T. Cáceres, F. Carrillo, P. Gómez-Garre, L. Vargas, M. Gariup, S. Stöber, A. Apter, V. Baglioni, J. Ball, N. Benaroya-Milshtein, B. Bodmer, E. Bognár, J. Buse, F. Cardona, M. C. Vela, N. M. Debes, M. C. Ferro, C. Fremer, B. García-Delgar, M. Gulisano, A. Hagen, J. Hagstrøm, T. J. Hedderly, I. Heyman, C. Huyser, M. Madruga-Garrido, A. Marotta, P. Mir, A. Morer, K. Müller-Vahl, A. Münchau, P. Nagy, V. Neri, T. J. C. Openneer, A. Pellico, Á. P. Vasco, K. J. Plessen, C. Porcelli, M. Redondo, R. Rizzo, V. Roessner, D. Ruhrman, M. J. Schwarz, P. R. Silvestri, L. Skov, T. Steinberg, F. T. Gloor, Z. Tarnok, J. Tübing, V. L. Turner, S. Walitza, E. Weidinger and M. L. Woods 2022 Vitamin D levels in children and adolescents with chronic tic disorders: a multicentre study 10.1007/s00787-021-01757-y

N. G. P. Bos-Veneman, J. Bijzet, P. C. Limburg, R. B. Minderaa, C. G. Kallenberg and P. J. Hoekstra 2010 Cytokines and soluble adhesion molecules in children and adolescents with a tic disorder 10.1016/j.pnpbp.2010.06.028

L. Bottoms, M. Prat Pons, N. A. Fineberg, L. Pellegrini, O. Fox, D. Wellsted, L. M. Drummond, J. Reid, D. S. Baldwin, R. Hou, S. Chamberlain, N. Sireau, D. Grohmann and K. R. Laws 2022 Effects of exercise on obsessive-compulsive disorder symptoms: a systematic review and meta-analysis 10.1080/13651501.2022.2151474

J. Buse, J. Rothe, A. Uhlmann, B. Bodmer, C. Kirschbaum, P. J. Hoekstra, A. Dietrich, V. Roessner, E. c. group, A. Apter, V. Baglioni, J. Ball, N. Benaroya-Milshtein, E. Bognar, B. Burger, F. Cardona, M. C. Vela, M. C. Ferro, B. Garcia-Delgar and M. Gulisano 2022 Hair cortisol-a stress marker in children and adolescents with chronic tic disorders? A large European cross-sectional study 10.1007/s00787-020-01714-1

F. Cardona, A. Romano, G. Cundari, F. Ventriglia, P. Versacci and G. Orefici 2004 Colour Doppler echocardiography in children with group A streptococcal infection related tic disorders

F. Cardona, F. Ventriglia, O. Cipolla, A. Romano, R. Creti and G. Orefici 2007 A post-streptococcal pathogenesis in children with tic disorders is suggested by a color Doppler echocardiographic study

A. Catarina Prior, S. Tavares, S. Figueiroa and T. Temudo 2007 [Tics in children and adolescents: a retrospective analysis of 78 cases]

H. T. Chugani, A. Kumar, P. Chakraborty and O. Muzik 2011 Basal ganglia inflammation in children with post-infectious neuropsychiatric manifestations: A positron emission tomography study using [11C]-PK-11195 <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ana.22564>

A. J. Church, R. C. Dale, A. J. Lees, G. Giovannoni and M. M. Robertson 2003 Tourette's syndrome: a cross sectional study to examine the PANDAS hypothesis

L. Cindro Heberle, M. Pavlovic, D. Neubauer and A. Al Tawari 2013 Severe PANDAS-like course: A case report <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1090-3798%2813%2970306-4>

A. Coluccia, F. Ferretti, A. Fagiolini and A. Pozza 2017 Quality of life in children and adolescents with obsessive-compulsive disorder: A systematic review and meta-analysis 10.2147/NDT.S122306

T. Cosco, T. Pillinger, H. Emam, M. Solmi, S. Budhdeo, A. Prina, M. Maes, D. Stein, B. Stubbs and A. Carvalho 2019 Immune Aberrations in Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder: a Systematic Review and Meta-analysis 10.1007/s12035-018-1409-x

R. Creti, F. Cardona, M. Pataracchia, C. von Hunolstein, G. Cundari, A. Romano and G. Orefici 2004 Characterisation of group A streptococcal (GAS) isolates from children with tic disorders

M. W. Cunningham 2008 Pathogenesis of group a streptococcal infections and their sequelae 10.1007/978-0-387-73960-1_3

R. C. Dale, I. Heyman, G. Giovannoni and A. J. Church 2005 Incidence of anti-brain antibodies in children with obsessive-compulsive disorder <https://dx.doi.org/10.1192/bjp.187.4.314>

P. G. de Alvarenga, M. A. de Mathis, A. C. D. Alves, M. C. do Rosário, V. Fossaluzza, A. G. Hounie, E. C. Miguel and A. RodriguesTorres 2012 Clinical features of tic-related obsessive-compulsive disorder: Results from a large multicenter study 10.1017/S1092852912000491

C. De Rosa, O. Ciara, O. Sarah and S. Edward 2012 PANDAS-OCD linked to streptococcal infection and scarlet fever <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eujim.2012.07.841>

A. De Vicente Blanco, B. Orgaz Alvarez, P. Ibanez Mendoza and M. Velasco Santos 2024 Acute obsessive symptoms: case report of a PANDASlike syndrome in an adult patient <https://dx.doi.org/10.1192/j.eurpsy.2024.735>

N. Descalco, R. D. Gomes, A. Maia, B. Barahona-Correa, A. Oliveira-Maia and J. Oliveira 2023 Infections and obsessive-compulsive disorder - results from a systematic review and meta-analysis <https://dx.doi.org/10.1192/j.eurpsy.2023.529>

R. Epifanio, N. Zanotta, S. Borini, M. Molteni and C. Zucca 2008 Non epileptic paroxysmal manifestations associated with streptococcal infections

T. E. Ercan, G. Ercan, B. Sevrge, M. Arpaozu and G. Karasu 2008 Mycoplasma pneumoniae infection and obsessive-compulsive disease: a case report

I. T. Euctr 2012 Multicentre, randomised, double-blinded, placebo-controlled trial of efficacy of antibiotic therapy in patients affected by tic disorder and with group A streptococcal colonization, No-profit study

E. Eynalli, O. Metin, P. C. Ray, A. Y. Tahiroglu and G. G. Celik 2018 Methylphenidate-induced Raynaud's phenomenon <https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/24750573.2018.1467600>

M. Fernandez Ibieta, J. T. Ramos Amador, I. Aunon Martin, M. A. Marin, I. Gonzalez Tome Ma and R. De Simon Las Heras 2005 Neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococci: A case report <https://dx.doi.org/10.1157/13074623>

T. Fidan, S. Ceyhan and V. Fidan 2025 Streptococcal Serology in Children With Stuttering

V. Gabbay and B. Coffey 2003 Obsessive-Compulsive disorder, Tourette's disorder, or pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with Streptococcus in an adolescent? Diagnostic and therapeutic challenges

J. Gadian, E. Kirk, K. Holliday, M. Lim and M. Absoud 2017 Systematic review of immunoglobulin use in paediatric neurological and neurodevelopmental disorders

B. Garcia-Delgar, A. Morer, M. J. Luber and B. J. Coffey 2016 Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder, Tics, and Autoinflammatory Diseases: Beyond PANDAS

S. Gharaibeh, P. Lalwani and O. Al Sokhni Mohamed 2024 UTILIZATION OF INTRAVENOUS IMMUNOGLOBULIN (IVIG) IN A TERTIARY PAEDIATRIC HOSPITAL IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES <https://dx.doi.org/10.1136/archdischild-2024-rcpch.156>

J. N. Giedd, J. L. Rapoport, H. L. Leonard, D. Richter and S. E. Swedo 1996 Case study: acute basal ganglia enlargement and obsessive-compulsive symptoms in an adolescent boy

L. Giulino, P. Gammon, K. Sullivan, M. Franklin, E. Foa, R. Maid and J. S. March 2002 Is Parental Report of Upper Respiratory Infection at the Onset of Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder Suggestive of Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated with Streptococcal Infection? 10.1089/104454602760219199

L. C. Heberle, D. Neubauer, A. Altawari and N. Alothman 2012 A case of severe form of PANDAS-like course <https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1528-1167.2012.03677.x>

Hollan, Douglas and R. B. Lemelson 1999 Re-checking the color of chickens: Indigenous, ethnographic and clinical perspectives on obsessive-compulsive disorder and Tourette's Syndrome in Bali

S. Kala, M. Z. Kara and M. H. Orum 2019 Improvement of Tourette syndrome symptoms with penicillin prophylaxis in two children presenting with severe functional disorder <https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/24750573.2019.1608065>

R. Katsandris, S. Oza, T. Reddy and P. Nair 2023 Help! I Am Having Intrusive Racial Thoughts After a Sore Throat! A Case Report on Possible PANDAS (Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated With Streptococcal Infection) in a Young Adult

R. Komorowska-Pietrzykowska, A. Rajewski and K. Lesniewska 2008 Interferon gamma and interleukin 6 in children with obsessive-compulsive and spectrum disorders

S. K. Kutty, W. A. W. Zaidi, W. N. N. W. Yahya, T. H. Jan, R. Remli and N. Ibrahim 2019 Acute Parkinsonism in a young adult following streptococcal infection: Possible adult variant of PANDAS <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/mdc3.12744>

J. F. Leckman, C. J. McDougle, D. L. Pauls, B. S. Peterson, D. E. Grice, R. A. King, L. Scahill, L. H. Price and S. A. Rasmussen 2017 Tic-related versus non-tic-related obsessive-compulsive disorder 10.4324/9781315561073-12

D. L. Leslie, L. Kozma and A. Martin 2008 Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infection: A Case-Control Study among Privately Insured Children <https://www.lww.com/product/?0890-8567>

L. Lit, A. Enstrom, F. R. Sharp and D. L. Gilbert 2009 Age-related gene expression in Tourette syndrome 10.1016/j.jpsychires.2008.03.012

Y. Maegaki, S. Akaboshi, M. Inagaki and K. Takeshita 2000 Unilateral involuntary movement associated with streptococcal infection: Neurophysiological investigation 10.1055/s-2000-7476

A. Mahapatra, P. K. Panda and R. Sagar 2017 Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infection treated successfully with a course of oral antibiotics

G. Maina, U. Albert, F. Bogetto, C. Borghese, A. C. Berro, R. Mutani, F. Rossi and M. C. Vigliani 2009 Anti-brain antibodies in adult patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder 10.1016/j.jad.2008.11.019

P. Malmborg, K. Dahlstrom, G. C. Kendahl, B. Lundell, B. Eriksson and H. Hildebrand 2001 [Rheumatic fever behind acute chorea in a young girl. A case report]

D. V. Maltsev 2019 Efficiency of a High-dose Intravenous Immunoglobulin Therapy in Children with Autism Spectrum Disorders Associated with Genetic Deficiency of Folate Cycle Enzymes

I. Marschitz, S. Rödl, U. Gruber-Sedlmayr, A. Church, G. Giovannoni, G. Zobel, C. J. Mache, J. Raith and B. Plecko 2007 Severe chorea with positive anti-basal ganglia antibodies after herpesencephalitis 10.1136/jnnp.2006.090555

L. K. Mell, R. L. Davis and D. Owens 2005 Association between streptococcal infection and obsessive-compulsive disorder, Tourette's syndrome, and tic disorder

S. E. Munasipova and Z. A. Zalyalova 2013 On the question of PANDAS <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/mds.25605>

S. E. Munasipova and Z. A. Zalyalova 2014 PANDAS in the structure of tic disorders <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00415-014-7337-4>

T. K. Murphy, E. C. Parker-Athill, A. B. Lewin, E. A. Storch and P. J. Mutch 2015 Cefdinir for Recent-Onset Pediatric Neuropsychiatric Disorders: A Pilot Randomized Trial 10.1089/cap.2014.0010

T. K. Murphy, M. Sajid, O. Soto, N. Shapira, P. Edge, M. Yang, M. H. Lewis and W. K. Goodman 2004 Detecting pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcus in children with obsessive-compulsive disorder and tics

T. K. Murphy, L. A. Snider, P. J. Mutch, E. Harden, A. Zaytoun, P. J. Edge, E. A. Storch, M. C. Yang, G. Mann, W. K. Goodman and S. E. Swedo 2007 Relationship of movements and behaviors to Group A Streptococcus infections in elementary school children

A. H. Nave, P. Harmel, R. Buchert and L. Harms 2018 Altered cerebral glucose metabolism normalized in a patient with a pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorder after streptococcal infection (PANDAS)-like condition following treatment with plasmapheresis: a case report

C. J. Ng, N. Mathers, A. Bradley and B. Colwell 2014 A 'combined framework' approach to developing a patient decision aid: the PANDAs model 10.1186/s12913-014-0503-7

R. Nicolson, S. E. Swedo, M. Lenane, J. Bedwell, M. Wudarsky, P. Gochman, S. D. Hamburger and J. L. Rapoport 2000 An open trial of plasma exchange in childhood-onset obsessive-compulsive disorder without poststreptococcal exacerbations 10.1097/00004583-200010000-00020

S. Noorbakhsh, B. Jalili, A. R. Shamshiri, E. Shirazi, A. Tabatabaei, R. Taghipour and A. M. Fathi 2010 The role of group A beta hemolytic streptococcal infections in patients with tic and tourett's disorders

S. Orlovska, C. H. Vestergaard, B. H. Bech, M. Nordentoft, M. Vestergaard and M. E. Benros 2017 Association of Streptococcal Throat Infection With Mental Disorders: Testing Key Aspects of the PANDAS Hypothesis in a Nationwide Study

B. Pandit, R. N. Oodun, A. K. Singh and J. S. Yadav 2012 PANDAS or Post-streptococcal complex motor tics? A case report & review

A. Pérez-Vigil, L. Fernández de la Cruz, G. Brander, K. Isomura, C. Gromark and D. Mataix-Cols 2016 The link between autoimmune diseases and obsessive-compulsive and tic disorders: A systematic review 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2016.09.025

E. M. Perrin, M. L. Murphy, J. R. Casey, M. E. Pichichero, D. K. Runyan, W. C. Miller, L. A. Snider and S. E. Swedo 2004 Does group A beta-hemolytic streptococcal infection increase risk for behavioral and neuropsychiatric symptoms in children?

G. Plazzi, F. Pizza, V. Palaia, C. Franceschini, F. Poli, K. K. Moghadam, P. Cortelli, L. Nobili, O. Bruni, Y. Dauvilliers, L. Lin, M. J. Edwards, E. Mignot and K. P. Bhatia 2011 Complex movement disorders at disease onset in childhood narcolepsy with cataplexy 10.1093/brain/awr244

M. Reddy, K. Reddy, H. A. Oughli, S. A. Nguyen and H. Lavretsky 2025 Post-Acute Sequelae of COVID-19 Infection Presenting With Neuropsychiatric Symptoms: Diagnosis and Management

J. E. Reid, K. R. Laws, L. Drummond, M. Vismara, B. Grancini, D. Mpavaenda and N. A. Fineberg 2021 Cognitive behavioural therapy with exposure and response prevention in the treatment of obsessive-compulsive disorder: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials 10.1016/j.comppsy.2021.152223

A. Sankaranarayanan and J. K. John 2003 Paediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders (PANDAS): a case report

R. Savino, A. N. Polito, G. Arcidiacono, M. Poliseno and S. Lo Caputo 2022 Neuropsychiatric Disorders in Pediatric Long COVID-19: A Case Series 10.3390/brainsci12050514

W. Schevenels and L. Schrooten 2011 A 15-year-old girl with a brief psychotic disorder after a streptococcal throat infection <https://dx.doi.org/10.2143/TVG.67.17.2001031>

E. Shirazi, S. Noorbakhsh and F. Ebrahimi Taj 2012 The role of streptococcal infection in children with neuropsychiatric manifestations (pandas): A case control study <https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1528-1167.2012.03677.x>

H. S. Singer, C. M. Morris-Berry, M. Pollard, A. Mascaro-Blanco, K. Alvarez, E. Kaplan and M. W. Cunningham 2012 Longitudinal measurements of anti-neuronal biomarkers for sydenham's chorea in children with acute exacerbations of tic and obsessive compulsive symptoms following a streptococcal infection <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ana.23708>

R. Singh, N. Nekrasova and D. Butov 2021 Tourette syndrome or PANDAS—a case report 10.1007/s10354-020-00779-6

M. S. Sokol and N. S. Gray 1997 Case study: an infection-triggered, autoimmune subtype of anorexia nervosa

E. A. Storch, G. R. Geffken, L. J. Merlo, G. Mann, D. Duke, M. Munson, J. Adkins, K. M. Grabill, T. K. Murphy and W. K. Goodman 2007 Family-based cognitive-behavioral therapy

	<p>for pediatric obsessive-compulsive disorder: Comparison of intensive and weekly approaches 10.1097/chi.0b013e31803062e7</p> <p>A. Suddath, A. Franks and H. Winston 2022 Catatonia in Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder: A case study and literature review https://dx.doi.org/10.1192/j.eurpsy.2022.1651</p> <p>N. Weiss-Goldman, B. Ardit, T. Rice and B. J. Coffey 2018 Psychopharmacology of the rage attack phenomenon in a child with obsessive compulsive disorder 10.1089/cap.2018.29150.bjc</p> <p>G. Zai, Y. B. Bezchlibnyk, M. A. Richter, P. Arnold, E. Burroughs, C. L. Barr and J. L. Kennedy 2004 Myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein (MOG) gene is associated with obsessive-compulsive disorder</p>
Population (n=5)	<p>2008 Feasibility Study for Pediatric NeuroDevelopmental Assessment Study (PANDAS) A1 - Anonymous</p> <p>Farley, Jean, Slota, Margaret and T. Fox 2020 Diagnostic Criteria Associated with a Cohort of Children Identified with Symptoms of Postinfectious Autoimmune Encephalopathy (PAE)</p> <p>L. Giulino, P. Gammon, K. Sullivan, M. Franklin, E. Foa, R. Maid and J. S. March 2002 Is parental report of upper respiratory infection at the onset of obsessive-compulsive disorder suggestive of pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorder associated with streptococcal infection?</p> <p>A. Vojdani and C. C. Turnpaugh 2020 Antibodies against Group A Streptococcus, dopamine receptors, and ganglioside GM1 cross-react with a variety of food antigens, potentially interfering with biomarkers for PANS and PANDAS https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.bionps.2020.100023</p> <p>K. Williams 2013 A translation model of autoimmune psychiatric illness https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/cts.12047</p>
Publication Type (n=65)	<p>2005 New study data support PANDAS hypothesis: a link between streptococcal infections and OCD</p> <p>2006 August: New study data support PANDAS hypothesis</p> <p>2006 CBT for PANDAS-related OCD...cognitive-behavioral therapy; obsessive-compulsive disorder</p> <p>2008 PANDAS-AN: a new subtype of anorexia nervosa?...Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal infection associated with anorexia nervosa</p> <p>2012 Erratum: Moving from PANDAS to CANS (Journal of Pediatrics (2012) 160 (725-731)) A1 - Anonymous https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2012.02.017</p> <p>2012 Correction: Moving from PANDAS to CANS (The Journal of Pediatrics (2012) 160(5) (725-731) (S0022347611012145) (10.1016/j.jpeds.2011.11.040)) A1 - Anonymous https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2012.02.019</p> <p>2012 Rare case of PANDAS with Kleine-Levin syndrome hypersomnia</p> <p>2015 Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections (PANDAS) 10.1007/s12098-014-1641-y</p>

2015 PANS consensus conference: Full medical evaluation needed

S. Aguilera-Albesa, R. Sanchez-Carpintero and P. Villoslada-Diaz 2009 Tic resolution against penicillin administration in a patient with PANDAS (pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with Streptococcal infection) <https://dx.doi.org/10.33588/rn.4804.2008586>

Anonymous 2020 Abrupt and Severe Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder in an 11-Year-Old Girl-PANDAS/PANS Syndrome: An Entity to be Considered-Management Implications: Retraction: Erratum

G. A. Bernstein, J. Wilson and L. Breithaupt 2025 Advocating for a 3-Pronged Approach to Treating PANS 10.1542/peds.2025-071886B

H. Blasco-Fontecilla, V. del Rio-Pena, P. Wang, C. Li, M. Martin-Moratinos and M. Bella-Fernandez 2024 TIC-TOC: PANDAS syndrome (pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infection) and psychiatric pathology in children and adolescents <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.psqi.2024.100554>

I. Cabo Lopez, P. J. Garcia Ruiz Espiga, A. Herranz Barcenas and I. Bustamante de Garnica 2010 [PANDAS: adult variant]

A. E. Cavanna, D. Martino, M. Orth, G. Giovannoni, J. S. Stern, M. M. Robertson and H. D. Critchley 2009 Neuropsychiatric-developmental model for the expression of tics, pervasive developmental disorder, and schizophreniform symptomatology associated with PANDAS

A. Chan and J. Frankovich 2019 Infections, Antibiotics, and Mental Health Deteriorations 10.1089/cap.2019.0100

A. Chan, T. Phu, B. Farhadian, T. Willett, M. Thienemann and J. Frankovich 2020 Familial Clustering of Immune-Mediated Diseases in Children with Abrupt-Onset Obsessive Compulsive Disorder

A. J. Church and R. C. Dale 2002 Antistreptolysin-O titers: implications for adult PANDAS. Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections

R. C. Dale, A. J. Church, P. M. Candler, M. Chapman, D. Martino and G. Giovannoni 2006 Serum autoantibodies do not differentiate PANDAS and Tourette syndrome from controls

R. C. Dale, S. Mohammad, V. X. Han, H. Nishida, H. Goel, S. G. Tangye, G. Hollway, E. Tantsis, D. Gill and S. Patel 2025 Pathogenic variants in chromatin-related genes: Linking immune dysregulation to neuroregression and acute neuropsychiatric disorders

P. G. de Alvarenga, A. G. Hounie, E. C. Miguel and R. Kurlan 2008 The role of group A beta-hemolytic streptococcal infection in neuropsychiatric disorders...Kurlan R, Johnson D, Kaplan EL: Tourette Syndrome Study Group. Streptococcal infection and exacerbations of childhood tics and obsessive-compulsive symptoms: a prospective blinded cohort study. Pediatrics. 2008;121(6):1188-97 10.1542/peds.2008-2118

S. K. Demirkaya, M. Demirkaya, C. Yusufoglu and E. Akin 2017 Atomoxetine Use in Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder and Comorbid Tic Disorder in Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections

J. L. Derenne 2009 Abrupt-onset obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) in a child with Crohn's disease

S. Dore, A. Zinellu, D. Satta, G. Boscia, C. Murgia and A. Pinna 2024 Ocular tics in Paediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections (PANDAS) 10.1111/aos.16097

S. Doshi, R. Maniar and G. Banwari 2014 Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12098-014-1641-y>

Z. Dranitzki and I. Steiner 2007 PANDAS in siblings: a common risk?

A. Fernandez-Rivas, M. T. Terreros, J. Ibarria, G. Lantaron and M. A. Gonzalez-Torres 2000 Recurrent depression: Infectious-autoimmune etiology? 10.1097/00004583-200007000-00007

L. Fonseca, J. Guerra, N. Neves and A. Machado 2010 PANDAS (Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated With Streptococcal Infection): a case report

V. Gabbay, B. J. Coffey and L. E. Guttman 2009 Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated With Streptococcus In Reply 10.1542/peds.2008-3123

L. George 2019 THWACK! Be gone PANDAS!

D. M. Gerardi, J. Casadonte, P. Patel and T. K. Murphy 2015 PANDAS and comorbid Kleine-Levin syndrome 10.1089/cap.2014.0064

M. V. M. Goncalves, R. Harger, V. Braatz, L. F. Parolin, A. C. B. Eboni, M. A. N. Fontana, A. Anacleto and Y. D. Fragoso 2018 Pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome (PANS) misdiagnosed as autism spectrum disorder

R. Greenberg 2015 Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections/pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndromes vs. pediatric bipolar disorder - A possible connection? <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.npbr.2015.08.002>

V. X. Han, S. Alshammery, B. A. Keating, B. S. Gloss, M. J. Hofer, M. E. Graham, N. Aryamanesh, L. L. Marshall, S. Yuan, E. Maple-Brown, J. Yan, S. Bandodkar, K. Kothur, H. Nishida, H. Jones, E. Tsang, X. Lau, R. Dissanayake, I. Perkes, S. Mohammad, F. Brilot, W. Gold, S. Patel and R. C. Dale 2025 Epigenetic, ribosomal, and immune dysregulation in Paediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome <https://dx.doi.org/10.1101/2025.03.28.25324649>

B. Z. Katz 2019 Streptococcal Infections and Exacerbation in Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated With Streptococcal Infection: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

M. LaRusso and C. Abadia-Barrero 2021 These doctors don't believe in PANS:” confronting uncertainty and a collapsing model of medical care

G. A. Maguire, S. Agarwal, D. Franklin, S. N. Viele and E. Handler 2010 Stuttering onset associated with streptococcal infection: A case suggesting stuttering as PANDAS

D. Martino, A. J. Church, R. C. Dale and G. Giovannoni 2005 Antibasal ganglia antibodies and PANDAS

<p>L. Masson 2023 PANS -- THE MYSTERY ILLNESS</p> <p>S. J. Mathew 2001 PANDAS variant and body dysmorphic disorder 10.1176/appi.ajp.158.6.963</p> <p>I. Melamed, R. Kobayashi, M. O'Connor, A. L. Kobayashi, A. Schechterman, M. Heffron, S. Canterbury, H. Miranda and N. Rashid 2020 Benefits of IVIG in pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome</p> <p>J. Mink and R. Kurlan 2011 Acute postinfectious movement and psychiatric disorders in children and adolescents</p> <p>B. B. Mittleman 1997 Cytokine networks in Sydenham's chorea and PANDAS</p> <p>S. Mohapatra, V. Agarwal and A. Agrawal 2013 Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders with streptococcus infection: a case report from India</p> <p>K. Moore 2018 N-Acetyl Cysteine and Curcumin in Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome</p> <p>K. O'Rourke 2003 PANDAS syndrome in the school setting</p> <p>S. Otero 2008 [Neuropsychiatric disorders with an autoimmune causation associated to streptococcal infection]</p> <p>M. M. Papachrisanthou and R. L. Davis 2015 Waking Up to a Child With Abrupt Personality Changes...pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections (PANDAS) 10.1016/j.nurpra.2015.07.018</p> <p>P. Pavone, M. Ceccarelli, S. Marino, D. Caruso, R. Falsaperla, M. Berretta, E. V. Rullo and G. Nunnari 2021 SARS-CoV-2 related paediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome</p> <p>M. E. Pichichero 2009 The PANDAS syndrome 10.1007/978-0-387-79838-7_17</p> <p>R. Pons 2013 Sydenham's Chorea, PANDAS, and other post-streptococcal neurological disorders 10.1007/978-1-60761-835-5_13</p> <p>P. C. Ray, D. A. Tas, G. G. Celik, A. Y. Tahiroglu, A. Avci and E. Erken 2013 Periodic fever and hyperimmunoglobulin D syndrome in a boy with pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with group A beta-hemolytic streptococcus 10.1089/cap.2012.0129</p> <p>K. P. Rosenberg 1998 Tourette's syndrome and 'PANDAS'</p> <p>B. Scolnick 2009 Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcus...Pediatrics. 2008 Aug;122(2):273-8 10.1542/peds.2008-2944</p> <p>A. R. Segarra and T. K. Murphy 2008 Cardiac involvement in children with PANDAS</p> <p>I. K. Sharawat, P. K. Panda and R. Gupta 2021 Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome with Capgras Syndrome</p> <p>C. Shimasaki 2016 The autoimmune response and neuropsychiatric disorders</p> <p>H. S. Singer 1999 PANDAS and immunomodulatory therapy</p> <p>S. Swedo, L. A. and M. A. Garvey 2004 Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) 10.1016/B978-044451271-0.50027-2</p>

	<p>S. E. Swedo, A. Schrag, R. Gilbert, G. Giovannoni, M. M. Robertson, C. Metcalfe, Y. Ben-Shlomo and D. L. Gilbert 2010 Streptococcal infection, Tourette syndrome, and OCD: is there a connection? PANDAS: horse or zebra? 10.1212/WNL.0b013e3181d8a638</p> <p>S. K. M. Swedo, B. Latimer and J. Leckman 2021 Pediatric Acute Neuropsychiatric Symptom Scale</p> <p>P. Turowski, K. Fetz, K. Chang and R. Lefering 2025 Pediatric acute neuropsychiatric syndrome (PANS) and Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) in the Context of EMTICS: Methodological Considerations and Misinterpretations</p> <p>E. R. Wald 2019 A Pediatric Infectious Disease Perspective on Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated With Streptococcal Infection and Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome</p> <p>D. A. Waldrep 2002 Two cases of ADHD following GABHS infection: a PANDAS subgroup?</p> <p>K. A. Williams 2019 Defining paediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome</p>
Study Design (n=68)	<p>2020 Corrigendum (Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry (2019) 58(10S) (S206), (S0890856719316557), (10.1016/j.jaac.2019.08.198)) A1 - Anonymous https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2020.10.006</p> <p>2025 New questionnaire effectively screens for PANDAS/PANS</p> <p>S. Bejerot, K. Bruno, G. Gerland, L. Lindquist, V. Nordin, H. Pelling and M. B. Humble 2013 [Suspect PANDAS in children with acute neuropsychiatric symptoms. Infection behind the disease - long-term antibiotic therapy should be considered]</p> <p>H. Ben-Pazi, S. Jaworowski and R. S. Shalev 2011 Cognitive and psychiatric phenotypes of movement disorders in children: a systematic review</p> <p>A. Bottas and M. A. Richter 2002 Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections (PANDAS)</p> <p>G. Brander, A. Pérez-Vigil, H. Larsson and D. Mataix-Cols 2016 Systematic review of environmental risk factors for Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder: A proposed roadmap from association to causation 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2016.03.011</p> <p>E. Burchi and S. Pallanti 2018 Antibiotics for PANDAS? Limited Evidence: Review and Putative Mechanisms of Action 10.4088/PCC.17r02232</p> <p>K. Chang, H. S. Koplewicz and R. Steingard 2015 Special issue on pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome</p> <p>S. Cocuzza, A. Maniaci, I. La Mantia, F. Nocera, D. Caruso, S. Caruso, G. Iannella, C. Vicini, E. Privitera, J. R. Lechien and P. Pavone 2022 Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder in PANS/PANDAS in Children: In Search of a Qualified Treatment-A Systematic Review and Metanalysis 10.3390/children9020155</p> <p>C. da, B. Ricardo Jorge and B. M. P. S. Ferreira 2019 Pandas Revisão Sistemática da Literatura</p>

S. Delaney and B. Fallon 2016 Inflammation in child and adolescent mental illnesses <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2016.07.151>

B. B. Demchick and K. Eglseider 2019 PANDAS: What Occupational Therapy Practitioners Should Know

F. M. V. Dias, A. Kümmer, A. G. Hounie and A. L. Teixeira 2008 Neurobiology of Tourette's syndrome: The autoimmune post-streptococcal hypothesis 10.1590/S0101-60832008000600004

P. R. Doran 2015 Sudden Behavioral Changes in the Classroom: What Educators Need to Know about PANDAS and PANS 10.1177/107429561502400106

I. Drtilkova 2001 Subgroups of OCD and tics in children like a part of pandas. Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections

R. Falsaperla, M. A. N. Saporito, V. Di Stefano and P. Pavone 2017 PANDAS: Tip of the iceberg <https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13052-017-0427-z>

Z. Farhood, A. A. Ong and C. M. Discolo 2016 PANDAS: A systematic review of treatment options

S. B. A. H. A. Fluitman, H. G. M. Westenberg and D. A. J. P. Denys 2004 PANDAS. A link between infection and psychopathology

A. Gagliano, F. Cucinotta, I. Giunta, I. Di Modica, C. de Domenico, C. Costanza, E. Germanò and J. Frankovich 2025 The Immune/Inflammatory Underpinnings of Neurodevelopmental Disorders and Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome: A Scoping Review 10.3390/ijms26167767

D. L. Gilbert, J. W. Mink and H. S. Singer 2018 A Pediatric Neurology Perspective on Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated with Streptococcal Infection and Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome

K. Gilliam 2022 PANS: A mysterious, debilitating pediatric disorder

W. K. Goodman, M. W. Sajid and W. K. Goodman 2006 Immunology of obsessive-compulsive disorder 10.1016/j.psc.2006.02.003

M. Grossman, S. O'Dor and D. A. Geller 2025 Clinical assessment and treatment of PANS/PANDAS <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.comppsy.2024.152551>

P. J. Harrison and M. Taquet 2023 Neuropsychiatric disorders following SARS-CoV-2 infection 10.1093/brain/awad008

H. M. Hart 2009 Recognizing behavioural and psychiatric manifestations of neuroimmunological disorders 10.1111/j.1469-8749.2009.03537.x

T. S. Ipe, E. K. Meyer, K. W. Sanford, S. K. Joshi, E. C. C. Wong and J. S. Raval 2021 Use of therapeutic plasma exchange for pediatric neurological diseases 10.1002/jca.21850

D. A. Kinderlehrer 2021 Does Lyme Disease Cause PANS 10.37871/jbres1201

D. D. Kirprov 2023 A Paradigm Shift in the Utilization of Therapeutic Plasmapheresis in Clinical Practice

L. Kloft, T. Steinel and N. Kathmann 2018 Systematic review of co-occurring OCD and TD: Evidence for a tic-related OCD subtype? 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2018.09.021

I. A. Kostik and M. M. Kostik 2019 Current approaches to PANS/PANDAS diagnostics and management <https://dx.doi.org/10.15690/vsp.v18i5.2055>

R. Kurlan 2004 The PANDAS hypothesis: losing its bite?

S. Leatherman 2025 Nutrition for PANS & PANDAS: The Dietitian's Role in Improving Patient Outcomes

J. Limbrick and S. Anari 2017 PANDAS in otolaryngology <https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/coa.12798>

P. Lojek and M. Rzeszutek 2025 PANS and PANDAS - symptoms beyond OCD and tics - a systematic review

K. J. MacK 2009 Tic disorders and their differential diagnosis in childhood 10.1016/j.paed.2009.08.001

N. Madhusudan and A. E. Cavanna 2013 The role of immune dysfunction in the development of tics and susceptibility to infections in Tourette syndrome: A systematic review 10.1016/j.baga.2013.03.001

J. S. March 2004 Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated With Streptococcal Infection (PANDAS): implications for clinical practice

E. Masterson and J. Gavin 2023 Rationale and Design for the International PANS Registry (IPR; Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome)

C. McCoy, D. Napier, L. Craig and C. W. Lack 2013 Controversies in pediatric obsessive-compulsive disorder

J. W. Mink 2016 Intravenous Immunoglobulin Is Not an Effective Treatment for Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorder Associated With Streptococcal Infection Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder

S. Mora, E. Martin-Gonzalez, P. Flores and M. Moreno 2020 Neuropsychiatric consequences of childhood group A streptococcal infection: A systematic review of preclinical models

A. Morer and J. Massana 2000 Alteraciones inmunológicas asociadas a tics, TOC y PANDAS 10.1016/S0025-7753(00)71395-9

T. Murphy and W. Goodman 2002 Genetics of childhood disorders: XXXIV. Autoimmune disorders, part 7: D8/17 reactivity as an immunological marker of susceptibility to neuropsychiatric disorders

T. K. Murphy, D. S. Husted and P. J. Edge 2006 Preclinical/Clinical evidence of central nervous system infectious etiology in PANDAS

P. Paribello, B. Carpiniello, R. Murgia, A. A. Porcheddu, S. El-Kacemi, M. Pinna, M. Contu, G. Costa, R. Barbarossa, E. Sanna, S. Carucci, A. Zuddas, P. Fadda, S. Dedoni, C. Siddi, P. Congiu, M. Figorilli, M. Fanzecco, M. Puligheddu, A. Gagliano, F. Pinna, M. Scherma and M. Manchia 2023 Identifying Neurobiological Markers in Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder: A Study Protocol for a Cross-Sectional Study in Subgroups of Differing Phenotype 10.3390/app13127306

C. Pittenger 2023 ANTIBODIES AGAINST BASAL GANGLIAL CHOLINERGIC INTERNEURONS IN YOUTH WITH PANS/PANDAS

V. Roessner, A. Becker, T. Banaschewski and A. Rothenberger 2005 Tic disorders and obsessive compulsive disorder: where is the link?

C. L. Sasseville 2016 PANDAS : A Synopsis

N. Schuft 2024 Between brain and immune system: The complex world of pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome (PANS)

H. S. Singer 2004 [PANDAS--Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infection: is it a specific clinical disorder?]

H. S. Singer, D. L. Gilbert, D. S. Wolf, J. W. Mink and R. Kurlan 2012 Moving from PANDAS to CANS

M. F. Siracusano and C. Panza 2013 PANDAS and antibiotic therapy: How many questions for the pediatrician!

J. Stephenson 2002 Strep A, neuropsychiatric disorders tie found

S. Swedo, J. Leckman and N. Rose 2010 From research subgroup to clinical syndrome: Modifying the PANDAS criteria to describe PANS (pediatric acute-onset neuropsychiatric syndrome)

S. Swedo, C. M. Menendez and M. W. Cunningham 2022 Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS)

S. E. Swedo 1999 Recognition and management of a subgroup of OCD and tic disorders

S. E. Swedo 2002 Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections (PANDAS)

S. E. Swedo, J. Frankovich and T. K. Murphy 2017 Overview of Treatment of Pediatric Acute-Onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome

S. E. Swedo, H. L. Leonard and J. L. Rapoport 2004 The pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infection (PANDAS) subgroup: separating fact from fiction

M. Thienemann and J. Frankovich 2017 Sudden onset of tics, tantrums, hyperactivity, and emotional lability: Update on pans and pandas

J. Tona and T. Posner 2011 Pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders

R. R. Trifiletti and A. M. Packard 1999 Immune mechanisms in pediatric neuropsychiatric disorders - Tourette's syndrome, OCD, and PANDAS

Vinagre, B. Catarina Lemos Fernandes Cordovil and I. d. S. Fontes 2020 Perturbação Neuropsiquiátrica Auto-Imune Pediátrica Associada a Infecções por Streptococcus (PANDAS)

B. Vincenzi, J. O'Toole and B. Lask 2010 PANDAS and anorexia nervosa--a spotters' guide: suggestions for medical assessment

	<p>G. Vitaliti, O. Tabatabaie, N. Matin, C. Ledda, P. Pavone, R. Lubrano, A. Serra, P. Di Mauro, S. Cocuzza and R. Falsaperla 2015 The usefulness of immunotherapy in pediatric neurodegenerative disorders: A systematic review of literature data</p> <p>J. P. Whelan 2024 Strep Throat and the Backstory for PANS and PANDAS 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.21636</p> <p>J. P. Windfuhr 2016 Tonsillectomy remains a questionable option for pediatric autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with streptococcal infections (PANDAS)</p> <p>M. Yilanli, S. B. Gokarakonda, A. Veerapandiyan and V. M. Raney 2020 28.9 PROVIDER PREDICAMENT OF BENEFICENCE VS NONMALEFICENCE REGARDING LONG-TERM ANTIBIOTIC USE IN PANDAS: REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND CASE REPORTS https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2020.08.254</p>
--	--

Appendix V

Free text symptoms coded under *other* in symptoms filters

Oppositional related behaviours	GI related	Self-harm, violence towards others	Psychosis/manic symptoms and disorders	Comorbidities/additional diagnoses	Physical symptoms	Eating and weight related	Skin related symptoms	Behavioural/psychiatric	Hypersexuality/hypersexual behaviours	Social/school related issues	Self-care/functioning	Motor disorder and tic related	Epilepsy and seizure related	Somatic (physical and psychological)	Biomedical/microbiological
defiance	constipation	harm to self and others	bipolar disorder	agoraphobia	adenotonsillar hypertrophy	anorexia nervosa	alopecia areata	abrupt personality changes	hyperarousal	academic growth (measure)	difficulty getting dressed in the morning	appearance of jumping	seizures	psychomotor agitation	positive GABHS throat culture
defiance	constipation,	harming others	bipolar	adductor spasmodic dysphonia	ankle swelling and warmth	anorexia nervosa	impetigo infection	adaptive behaviours (measure)	hypersexuality	communication difficulties (difficulties with receptive expressive and written skills)	personal care (measure)	arm wavering	febrile seizures	Somatic symptoms	presence of antibodies against group A beta-haemolytic streptococcus
oppositional behaviour	encopresis	harming self and others,	bipolar and related disorders	ADHD	blurred vision	body dysmorphia	itch	affect was flat and serious	inappropriate sexual behaviour	difficulties in social interaction	poor hygiene	belly twitching	possible epileptiform	Somatic symptoms	presence of anti-streptococcal, anti-enolase and anti-neural

Oppositional related behaviours	GI related	Self-harm, violence towards others	Psychosis/manic symptoms and disorders	Comorbidities/additional diagnoses	Physical symptoms	Eating and weight related	Skin related symptoms	Behavioural/psychiatric	Hypersexuality/hypersexual behaviours	Social/school related issues	Self-care/functioning	Motor disorder and tic related	Epilepsy and seizure related	Somatic (physical and psychological)	Biomedical/microbiological
															antibodies
oppositional behaviours	encopresis	self-harm	mania	agoraphobia	blurred vision	body-image issues	pathergy	agitation	inappropriate touching	giftedness	daily living skills	coprolalia	seizures	somatic symptoms	
oppositional behaviours	encopresis,	self-injury	mania,	agoraphobia	BP alterations,	bulimia nervosa	pseudofolliculitis	altered perceptions		irregular school attendance		darting tongue			
oppositional behaviours	episodic encopresis	self-harm	mania	anxiety disorder	bradycardia	bulimia	psoriasis	anhedonia		peer problems		darting tongue			
oppositional defiant disorder	gastrointestinal disorder	self-harm	psychosis	arthritis	clumsiness	dysmorphophobia	Rash	attention deficit		school absence		fine motor abnormalities			
oppositional defiant disorder	gastrointestinal issues,	self-harm	psychosis	arthritis	Clumsiness	excessive eating	recurrent oral and genital sores	Attention deficit		school avoidance		loss of motor skills			
oppositional defiant disorder	gastrointestinal issues,	self-harm	psychosis	ASD assessment	constant need to urinate	obsession with body image	retroauricular eczema	avoidant behaviours		school refusal		mild milkmaid grip			
oppositional defiant disorder	gastrointestinal problems	self-harm	psychosis	ASD	cutaneous lesions	periodic excessive eating	skin conditions	changes in personality		social difficulties with friends and family		milkmaid grip			
oppositional defiant disorder,	gastrointestinal symptoms	self-harm	psychosis	asthma	dilated pupils	rapid weight loss		confusion		social stress		milkmaid grip			

Oppositional related behaviours	GI related	Self-harm, violence towards others	Psychosis/manic symptoms and disorders	Comorbidities/additional diagnoses	Physical symptoms	Eating and weight related	Skin related symptoms	Behavioural/psychiatric	Hypersexuality/hypersexual behaviours	Social/school related issues	Self-care/functioning	Motor disorder and tic related	Epilepsy and seizure related	Somatic (physical and psychological)	Biomedical/microbiological
oppositional disorder	gastrointestinal symptoms,	self-harm/self-injurious behaviour	Psychotic features	autism	dilated pupils	unexpected increase in food intake		difficulty focusing,		talent/creativity development		milkmaid's grip			
oppositonality	GI problems	self-injurious behaviour,	psychotic symptoms	autism spectrum disorder	dilated pupils	Weight gain		difficulty with spatial functioning		socialisation difficulties		motor issues			
oppositonality,	GI symptoms	self-injurious behaviour	psychotic symptoms	autism	dilated pupils	weight loss		dissociation				piano playing finger movement			
severe oppositional behaviours	intermittent vomiting and loss of taste	suicide attempt	schizophrenia	behavioural disorders	dilation of pupils	weight-loss		dissociative episodes				piano-playing fingers			
severely oppositional behaviours	irritable bowel syndrome	Violence	schizophrenia	Behçet's disease	Effusive otitis media			extreme distress				sporadic high-volume cries, sometimes preceded by "premonitory urge," at high intensity and frequency			

Oppositional related behaviours	GI related	Self-harm, violence towards others	Psychosis/manic symptoms and disorders	Comorbidities/additional diagnoses	Physical symptoms	Eating and weight related	Skin related symptoms	Behavioural/psychiatric	Hypersexuality/hypersexual behaviours	Social/school related issues	Self-care/functioning	Motor disorder and tic related	Epilepsy and seizure related	Somatic (physical and psychological)	Biomedical/microbiological
	loss of sphincter control		schizophrenia spectrum related disorders	catatonia	erratic gait			fear				tongue fasciculation			
	nausea			conduct disorder	fist clenching			global functioning (measure)				wormian tongue movement			
	nausea			COVID-19 related symptoms	hearing (measure)			growing							
	nausea			depressive disorders,	hearing problems (SNHL)			having trouble focussing and solving problems							
	vomiting			disruptive behaviour disorder	heart rate			hissing vocalisations,							
	vomiting			dysgraphia	hiccups			identity development (measure)							
	vomiting			generalised anxiety disorder	hippus			Inattention							
				GJH	joint stiffness			inhibitory control issues,							
				hoarding disorder	joint swelling			internalisation of concerns							
				intellectual disability	lack of energy			irrational behaviour							

Oppositional related behaviours	GI related	Self-harm, violence towards others	Psychosis/manic symptoms and disorders	Comorbidities/additional diagnoses	Physical symptoms	Eating and weight related	Skin related symptoms	Behavioural/psychiatric	Hypersexuality/hypersexual behaviours	Social/school related issues	Self-care/functioning	Motor disorder and tic related	Epilepsy and seizure related	Somatic (physical and psychological)	Biomedical/microbiological
				juvenile idiopathic arthritis	limited mobility			irrational behaviours							
				language delay	loss of muscle			Language development (measure)							
				metabolic disorder	mydriasis			light & sound sensitivity							
				mood disorders	Mydriasis			losing patience							
				mutism	night sweats			losing touch with reality							
				oromotor dyspraxia with tongue thrusting	palatal and abdominal petechiae,			loss of concentration							
				panic disorder	perianal itching			loss of speech							
				postpartum depression	posturing of arms			loss of speech							
				post-streptococcal glomerulonephritis	proprioception (measure)			making unusual statements that were untrue							
				Postural Orthostatic Tachycardia Syndrome	protruding belly			mood dysregulation							
				PTSD	Rhinosinusitis pathology			narcissistic traits							

Oppositional related behaviours	GI related	Self-harm, violence towards others	Psychosis/manic symptoms and disorders	Comorbidities/additional diagnoses	Physical symptoms	Eating and weight related	Skin related symptoms	Behavioural/psychiatric	Hypersexuality/hypersexual behaviours	Social/school related issues	Self-care/functioning	Motor disorder and tic related	Epilepsy and seizure related	Somatic (physical and psychological)	Biomedical/microbiological
				sinusitis	sore throat			negativity							
				social anxiety disorder	stiffness in back, hips and fingers			overthinking							
				specific learning disorder	strawberry tongue			panic episodes							
				substance use disorder	sweating			phobia							
				temporomandibular joint disorders	temp dysregulation			restlessness							
				tourette's and tic disorder	temperature dysregulation			restlessness							
				trauma related disorders	truncal instability			restlessness							
				trichotillomania	unsteady gait/balance issues			restlessness							
				trichotillomania	ventricle hyperfunction (larynx)			restlessness							
					vision (measure)			skin picking							
					weakness			staring							

Oppositional related behaviours	GI related	Self-harm, violence towards others	Psychosis/manic symptoms and disorders	Comorbidities/additional diagnoses	Physical symptoms	Eating and weight related	Skin related symptoms	Behavioural/psychiatric	Hypersexuality/hypersexual behaviours	Social/school related issues	Self-care/functioning	Motor disorder and tic related	Epilepsy and seizure related	Somatic (physical and psychological)	Biomedical/microbiological
					weakness			trying to jump out of moving cars							
								very distressed							
								yelling							
<p>ADHD, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, ASD, autism spectrum disorder; BP, blood pressure; GABHS, group A beta-haemolytic streptococcus; GI, gastrointestinal; GJH; Generalised Joint Hypermobility; PTSD, past-traumatic stress disorder, SNHL, sensorineural hearing loss</p> <p>Key: Blue – physical symptoms (including neurological); Red, psychological/behavioural symptoms; Green, impact on functioning symptoms; Yellow, comorbidities/additional diagnoses; Purple, physical and psychological symptoms</p>															

